

2023 EUROfusion Breeding Blanket Working Group

Report

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II Outline / Terms of Reference

Background

The EUROfusion General Assembly agreed, on its 42nd Meeting on 5 / 6 April 2023, “to mandate a group to discuss and propose a specific strategy for the breeding blanket and fuel cycle development in the context of revised Roadmap, in support of the Group that looks at the new approach to the Roadmap. The group would be based on the EUROfusion part of EU Breeding Blanket Programme Steering Committee, and include additional experts and an observer from the Commission.”

This has to be seen as a reaction of the ITER delays and probable impacts on the TBM programme, as one important building block of European Breeding Blanket qualification, and against the background of the current attempt to revise the EUROfusion Roadmap in order to make it more attractive and more realistic. The respective Working Group and its subgroups are expected to report their findings at the next regular GA meeting mid-July at Cadarache; this also sets the time frame for the new Breeding Blanket Working Group.

Mission

“Review, and make proposals to improve / accelerate, the qualification strategy for the Fusion Fuel Cycle Technology, with particular attention to the Breeding Blanket”

Tasks

- Review / comment on the current testing & qualification strategy for the Fusion Deuterium Tritium Fuel Cycle outside the vacuum vessel.
- Review / comment on the part of the current testing & qualification strategy for the Breeding Blanket which can be done without neutrons.
- Review / comment on the part of the current testing & qualification strategy for the Breeding Blanket which requires neutrons, and make recommendations on a new / improved / accelerated Breeding Blanket neutronic testing and qualification strategy.

→ *Necessary input:*

- *Qualitative compilation of testing / qualification requirements*
- *Quantitative estimate of testing requirements for an instructive example (neutron dose / fluence / flux – exposure time, irradiation volume, number of tests / variants required)*
- *Compilation of neutron exposure facilities (existing, under preparation, or other) and their technical data (neutron flux, irradiation area and volume, time to availability)*
- *Examination of Volumetric Neutron Source as proposed in the draft paper by Gianfranco Federici, with a view to time to availability (concept, design, licensing, construction)*
- *Attribution of neutron exposure facilities to testing / qualification requirements*
- *Qualification impact of / necessities for modelling*

III Starting Point

The European Roadmap to Fusion Energy has reached a critical situation, as on the one hand the projected time schedule cannot be maintained with the present funding, that is on a significantly lower level than what was requested when developing the current version of the Roadmap, and now is being critically challenged by the unforeseeable cost increases triggered by the Russian war on Ukraine. At the same time, with the needs for the supply of green energy rising, the present Roadmap time schedule is at risk of shifting the deployment of fusion energy so far into the future that it could become irrelevant.

The situation is aggravated by the need of defining a new baseline for ITER. While this is not yet finalized and approved, there are clear indications for a significant delay for the first plasma, and possible descoping of the ITER TBM programme. To be more specific, we expect a significant shift of ITER full DT experiments, as well as a reduction of the accumulated neutron damage, and even more relevant, a possible reduction of the overall neutron fluence of a factor 10–100 [1], [2]. Consequently, uncertainties of the TBM testing programme, crucial for qualifying the Breeding Blanket, jeopardise the possibility to perform a full, nuclear integrated test of the Breeding Blanket Systems. Indeed, in order to obtain relevant data from the TBM for extrapolating to DEMO, it is necessary to perform long nuclear testing with a relevant neutron fluence. These conditions seem not confirmed with the new ITER baseline.

The Deuterium Tritium Fuel Cycle and the Breeding Blanket are the nuclear core of any fusion reactor relying on the DT reaction. Although increasing efforts have been spent in EUROfusion on these systems, the overall maturity levels are rather low [3], [4], [5], [6]. This is due to a large extent to the limited access to nuclear testing facilities and lack of dedicated facilities able to address complex synergetic effects at the component level, while an integrated testing and qualification of the breeding blanket at any stage of life can't be executed without a nuclear fusion testing facility. To make DEMO and any subsequent fusion power reactor a success, a high degree of maturity for these systems is indispensable. Any effort towards accelerating the course of the EUROfusion Roadmap consequently will have to give emphasis to the maturation of fuel cycle and breeding blanket systems.

Given that the task “to discuss and propose a specific strategy for the breeding blanket and fuel cycle development in the context of revised Roadmap” assigned to the working group was very broad, it was necessary to break this down in blocks which could be considered separately in a first approximation. These are:

- The testing & qualification strategy for the DT Fuel Cycle outside the reactor vessel (i.e., without any neutron impact)
- The part of the testing & qualification strategy for the Breeding Blanket which can be achieved without neutrons
- The part of the testing & qualification strategy for the Breeding Blanket which requires neutrons

For the development of the Fuel Cycle outside the reactor vessel, as well as for the non-neutronic testing and maturation of the Breeding Blanket, there exist well-defined schedules with identified gaps that can be addressed in time. The full (i.e., including neutronic) qualification of the Breeding Blanket, however, is in a far less mature state – even before considering the ITER re-baselining. Therefore, the focus of the Working Group was on the latter, while doing a critical evaluation of the planning for the first two items (fuel cycle outside the reactor vessel, non-

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neutronic breeding blanket development and testing) on the basis of a concise report and gap analysis of the respective EUROfusion Project Leader.

The neutronic pre-qualification of the breeding blanket for DEMO so far has been built upon two main pillars. First, the qualification of the materials to be used, with a high dose / damage rate, in IFMIF-DONES, which shall provide a good simulation of the fusion neutron spectrum combined with a high neutron flux, and second, integrated testing at “Beginning-of-Life” (BoL) level of the Test Blanket Modules (TBMs) in ITER. In addition, before IFMIF-DONES and ITER become available, some minimum screening of materials damage is foreseen by exposing samples to neutron loads in Materials Test Reactors (MTRs) – with the disadvantage that the neutron spectrum there is different and cannot reproduce all types of damage to be seen in a fusion environment.

This concept implies that any integral testing and qualification of the breeding blanket beyond the BoL level has to be done, in a stepwise approach, with DEMO.

The RoX of the TBM from the Regulatory & Licensing processes, from the standardization /qualification of manufacturing technologies for EUROFER97 as well as the operation/maintenance for the first time in a nuclear device of such complex system remain fundamental RoX from the TBM program for the BB. However, with the expected performance reduction of the ITER TBM testing, not even BoL qualification will be possible via this route. The reason is, that the expected reduced damage dose of < 0.1 dpa will not bring about any significant effects and, moreover, the anticipated reduction in plasma pulse length will by far not allow reaching the TBM operational asymptotic thermal regime at the end of the plasma flat top – i.e., thermal effects from the volumetric neutron heating, and combined effects related to this, cannot be observed. This implies the risk of not achieving the required temperature in the breeder zone, jeopardizing the tritium release from the ceramic breeder (and multiplier).

Even with the original TBM test programme, the Breeding Blanket testing & maturation of the concept to be pursued must be considered as risky. One of the main knowledge gaps is the identification of failure modes and quantification of failure rates of the proposed concept under relevant operating conditions. Combined effects of neutron impact and other ways of degradation during operation (e.g., corrosion, thermos-cycling fatigue, tritium permeation; see Annex 3.1) would be detected in the integral testing until Mid of Life (MoL) and End of Life (EoL) level on DEMO only. Prior screening / testing of such effects on limited scale is not foreseen, as it is not possible to do this with a relevant neutron spectrum using available or projected neutron sources on a timescale that would impact development and design choices according to the current planning.

The recommendations compiled in the following section have to be understood as an attempt to accelerate Fusion Fuel Cycle and Breeding Blanket development and qualification, as a key issue for accelerating the deployment of fusion energy in Europe and for the respective adaptation of the Roadmap. They imply that additional funding may become available, as any attempt to accelerate will require the accelerated realization of infrastructure and / or the parallel realization of additional infrastructure, and the related earlier / additional experimental work.

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References

- [1] Presentation by Giancarli, Merola on Final version on revised PBS-56 milestone - [ITER D 94V33T](#)
- [2] Presentation by Merola, Giancarli on Preparation of the TBM-PT Steering Committee-12 - [ITER D 93LG4](#)
- [3] WP TFV Maturity Matrix - <http://idm.euro-fusion.org/?uid=2Q3S3Y>
- [4] WP TFV Maturity Assessment Review Panel Report - <http://idm.euro-fusion.org/?uid=2QVRX2>
- [5] WP BB Technology Maturation Plan – Release 2022 - [EFDA D 2QKV6Q](#)
- [6] Work Package Maturity Assessment of Breeding Blanket - Preliminary Panel Report [2QCYR9](#)

IV Findings & Recommendations

Integrated Breeding Blanket testing and qualification

- The expected loss of the opportunity for BB integrated testing even at Beginning of Life (BoL) level via the ITER TBMs calls for an alternative, as transferring this task to DEMO will limit and postpone DEMO performance significantly.
- A Volumetric Neutron Source (VNS – see Annex 4.5) could be an option not only to re-establish BoL qualification for the Breeding Blanket before installing and operating it in DEMO, but, if scalability to DEMO parameters is ensured, also for extended BB qualification prior to DEMO, thus significantly enhancing DEMO maturity, availability and performance in time (see Annex 5).
- Successful implementation and operation of a VNS would significantly reduce the risks of a future DEMO reactor, particularly with respect to blanket availability and performance, as well as a number of other important issues related to fuel cycle, safety, etc. (see Annex 3.1).
- A VNS could relieve DEMO from the experimental “component test facility” character.
- Feasibility, conceptual design, cost and time to availability of a VNS are not yet established. As a coarse estimate, time to availability would be ~ 15 years (see Annex 5).
- **With successful realization and operation of**
 - **ITER with TBM RoX**
 - **IFMIF-DONES**
 - **a VNS,****the next fusion device could be a prototype power plant built by industry around 2045.** This would constitute, with the respective adaptation of the Roadmap, a significant improvement of the European perspective to the deployment of fusion energy.
- **In the sense of risk reduction, it is recommended to avoid any early down-selection and to pursue in parallel complementary BB concepts up to a relevant stage of testing / qualification for making the necessary choices in order to realize DEMO, unless a clear show-stopper occurs earlier.**
- **A pre-conceptual design study on a VNS, in order to establish feasibility, configuration, timeline and required resources, should start without delay. An overall effort of 15 FTEs, mostly in the PMU DEMO Central Team, would have to be dedicated to complete this exercise within ~ 1.5 years from its inception (see Annex 5).**

Neutronic screening and pre-qualification of Breeding Blanket elements

- Prior to integrated testing and qualification of a breeding blanket, either in a VNS or in DEMO, single and combined effect characterization will be necessary, along the timeline of the availability of neutron sources (see Annex 3.1).
- The overall need for neutron irradiations, in order to accelerate the development and the informed selection of design choices, is quite huge, and a wide range of facilities has to be considered to fulfil the capacity needs (see Annex 3.1, 3.2 and 7).
- **A study should be launched within WP BB to establish the quantitative needs for neutron irradiations on different levels and time scales on the basis of the matching exercise documented in Annex 7 and the quantitative considerations outlined in**

Annex 3.2. Acknowledging the overall effort associated with this exercise, attention should be given to the sequence of consideration, i.e., to establish near-term needs early, and longer-term needs afterwards.

- Immediate screening of single effects / neutronic response (e.g., activation, T production) can be done in available Materials Test Reactors, with the restriction of the spectral difference. In specific cases, spallation sources may be considered suitable (see Annex 4.1, 4.2, 7).
- **Particularly, the neutron irradiation programme for Breeding Blanket functional materials, that was foreseen with Russia, had to be cancelled, and could so far only partially be recovered with alternative sources, should be re-installed with viable sources in full scope.**
- Screening on short time scales of combined effects in different configurations (blanket concepts, design variants) requiring extended sample volumes, in order to narrow down the choices and to limit to a viable extent the necessary testing campaigns with high-grade (i.e., near fusion) spectrum neutron sources to come into operation later (IFMIF-DONES; potentially SORGENTINA-BMT) could be achieved using dedicated, flexible point sources with relevant neutron energy spectrum to be realized with moderate effort (see Annex 4.3).
- **Depending on the analyses on quantitative neutron exposure needs, the realization on short time scales (< 5 years) and with moderate effort of specific, flexible, small point sources with fusion-relevant neutron energy spectrum should be envisaged, as this could significantly reduce the risks both of DEMO and of a VNS.**
- Focussed pre-qualification campaigns, prior to the availability of either a VNS or DEMO, have to be performed with high-grade spectrum sources like IFMIF-DONES (~ 10 years to availability) and SORGENTINA-BMT (~ 8 years to availability).
- **The realization of the projected second beamline of IFMIF-DONES and, after successful completion of the ongoing feasibility study, of SORGENTINA-BMT should be considered with a view to making the necessary high-grade neutron fluence available, depending on the outcome of the study on quantitative needs for neutron exposure.**
- With a view to the limited irradiation capabilities available so far, and the significant deployment time of IFMIF-DONES, the development of an integrated modelling / “virtual qualification” tool to complement / extend the experimental qualification activities can be considered as a risk mitigation action (see Annex 6).
- **As a first step towards building such “virtual qualification” tool, the review of the methods, experiments and computational studies applied for the development and validation of the DEMO design rules is needed and should be addressed in a joint effort of the Breeding Blanket and the Materials Work Packages.**

Non-neutronic testing and pre-qualification of Breeding Blanket elements

- For the non-neutronic testing required on the development & qualification path for the Breeding Blankets, there is a clear planning & schedule within the WP BB Work Programme. Most of the facilities required are either available or under construction (see Annex 2.1).
- One identified gap refers to the facilities for tritium extraction & recovery (TER) from the BB breeder / purge gas (see Annex 2.1).

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- The different BB concepts require different TER facilities. There are conceptual designs for each case; realization however was postponed, inter alia due to scarcity of resources and the resulting need to focus on a main line following driver-blanket selection.
- For the solid breeder concepts (HCPB, WLCB), the basic choice of the tritium extraction & recovery (TER) concept is clear; evaluation of alternatives in detail is pending. For the liquid breeder concepts (WCLL), there are still several basic options. Evaluation and selection of TER technologies for either blanket concept should be completed by the G2 review 2024/25 (see Annex 2.1).
- **In order to close the existing gaps on the non-neutronic testing & pre-qualification path, and accelerate blanket development & qualification by a parallel approach, TER facilities both for the solid and the liquid breeder blanket concepts should be realized without delay after TER technology evaluation at the G2 review.**
- There is another gap w.r.t. the non-neutronic testing required on the development & qualification path for the Breeding Blankets, that is a concept for the BB attachment to the Vacuum Vessel, as well as a facility to test and demonstrate such concept and the related remote maintenance procedures (see Annex 2.1).
- **A concept study for the attachment of the BB to the Vacuum Vessel, and for a facility to test and demonstrate these along with the related remote handling procedures, should be launched without delay.**
- The breeding blanket will need breeder material enriched in ${}^6\text{Li}$, irrespective of whether a solid or a liquid breeder will be used. A process and a facility for the enrichment of ${}^6\text{Li}$ is missing so far; only concepts exist. As for a DEMO blanket huge amounts of the enriched material will be needed, production has to start early enough, requiring a qualified process and a suitable facility.
- **It is indispensable to start an activity on the stepwise qualification of a ${}^6\text{Li}$ enrichment process, and to timely realize a facility on appropriate scale.**

Development and qualification of the DT Fuel Cycle outside the Vacuum Vessel

- Many qualification aspects rely on the full scope of DIPAK. Due to cost increases, realization of DIPAK has to come in stages, with FP9 so far covering only the stage required for separated (not yet integrated) experiments (see Annex 1).
- **To accelerate full exploitation of DIPAK in FP10, realization of the final stage should be brought back to FP9.**
- Final validation of all Fuel Cycle elements with tritium on relevant scale could be achieved with the Fuel Cycle of a VNS, if realized. For most of the elements, this would be mandatory to operate the VNS, the others still could be added and qualified without harm to VNS operation (see Annex 1).
- Alternatively, and before a VNS could become operational, the combination of DIPAK and the TLK, located side by side, could be exploited to go to full tritium qualification of the Fuel Cycle elements outside the Vacuum Vessel. Still, this could not be implemented before the end of this decade (see Annex 1).
- To go to full tritium qualification of the Fuel Cycle elements outside the Vacuum Vessel on a shorter time scale, the UNITY-2 facility, a full-scale DT Fuel Cycle test bed projected by

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Canadian Nuclear Laboratories in collaboration with Kyoto Fusioneering, would be the closest option (see Annex 1).

- **Synergies with the UNITY-2 facility, and respective collaboration opportunities should be explored with a view to near-term, full-scale Fuel Cycle qualification with tritium.**

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V Table of Annexes

- 1 Overview on the existing testing & qualification strategy for the DT Fuel Cycle outside the vacuum vessel, and possible gaps
- 2.1 Overview on the existing development, testing & qualification strategy for the Breeding Blanket and the related tritium extraction & recovery systems, which can be done without neutrons, and possible gaps
- 2.2 Summary of expected Return of Experience (RoX) from ITER TBM for the BB qualification and timescales
- 3.1 Qualitative compilation of testing-qualification requirements for Breeding Blanket
- 3.2 Quantitative estimates on requirements for instructive examples of Breeding Blanket testing
- 4.1 Characterization of Materials Test Reactors
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- 4.3 Characterization of p/d Accelerator-based Neutron Sources
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- 4.5 Preliminary Considerations on a European Volumetric Neutron Source
- 5 Volumetric Neutron Source as test bed to qualify Breeding blankets for future fusion reactors based on magnetic confinement
- 6 Overview on the requirements for irradiated materials test data input to performance assurance modelling of blanket components
- 7 Matching of neutron-based Breeding Blanket testing / qualification requirements with existing / anticipated neutron exposure facilities

Report Annex 1

Overview on the existing testing & qualification strategy for the DT Fuel Cycle systems outside the vacuum vessel, and possible gaps

- For the directly blanket-related Tritium Extraction & Recovery Systems, see Report Annex 2 -

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Date: 7 June 2023

Executive Summary: The DT fuel cycle is a highly integrated chemical plant. Due to the safety and licensing aspects of the fuel cycle, the components have to come with very high fidelity. This must be achieved by an appropriate testing & qualification strategy.

It is found that the current programme does have maturation gaps, if the technology development shall be driven in a 10-year timeframe to the maximum achievable without having a pilot plant available. Most gaps could be closed by utilizing the fuel cycle of the currently discussed future volumetric neutron source for technology maturation purposes. This includes in particular the technologies for fuelling (gas injection), vacuum pumping (continuous, mercury-based), exhaust processing (membrane separation and reactor), exhaust detritiation (recombiner, wet scrubber), and water detritiation (CECE, distillation). For to close the remaining gaps, cooperation with the UNITY-2 DT fuel cycle demonstration platform could be envisaged, which could in particular provide a near-term tritium testing opportunity of the Direct Internal Recycling related technologies fuel separation (metal foil pump) and isotope rebalancing (temperature swing absorption).

Introduction of the systems and their current maturation status

The most updated DT fuel cycle blockchart¹ is depicted in Figure 1. It contains 15 system blocks, organised in an architecture comprising three different loops with separated tritium processing functions.

¹ TFV Fuel Cycle System Block Diagram - <http://idm.euro-fusion.org/?uid=2Q6TYV>

Fig. 1. TFV (Tritium – Matter Injection – Vacuum) Block diagram.

The Direct Internal Recycling Loop (DIRL) is the innermost loop, handling the machine gas throughput. The inner tritium plant loop (INTL) provides fuel rebalancing. The outer tritium plant loop (OUTL) provides tritium recovery and is integrated with the blanket and its tritium extraction and removal systems. A detailed description of the systems can be found in the DEMO pre-concept design special issue of Fusion Engineering and Design².

In November 2022, the TFV systems were assessed in a technical maturity review³, which is taken as starting point for the testing and qualification strategy outlined in this document. The conclusions from that review are contained in the summary Table 1 at the end of this document. The maturation and qualification strategy of the chosen technologies goes from code development that allows a physically consistent scaling of the technology up to validation of the final component (already at a representative scale, ideally a prototype). This usually comprises 4 steps:

- (i) Code development and its specific validation,
- (ii) Verification of the technology,
- (iii) Validation of the component performance (covers scalability),
- (iv) Demonstration of integrated performance in the process chain (covers reliability).

² Chr. Day et al., The pre-concept-design of the DEMO tritium, matter in jection and vacuum systems, Fusion Engineering and Design 179 (2022) 113139.

³ TFV Maturity Matrix - <http://idm.euro-fusion.org/?uid=2Q3S3Y>. This document is also describing the used definition of the individual technical readiness levels, ranging from 1 to 10.

Outline of testing & qualification strategy

As regards tritium experiments, maturation of tritium technology components does not always require to conduct the full technology development chain with tritium. However, at least a final demonstration will in most cases be needed. The latter shall prove the tritium-compatibility of the design and is often wanted to demonstrate lifecycle time.

Having said that, we define the following five testing & qualification category requirements. All of them lead to the same TRL, but if a technology qualification sits in a higher Q category, more intense tritium testing will be necessary.

- Q1 Completely develop single technologies without tritium where the technology function does not depend on tritium (e.g Xe/Ar separation, He-3 export,)
- Q2 Almost completely develop single technologies with H₂/D₂ where there is confidence for extrapolation to tritium (e.g. mechanical vacuum pumping); do a final test under tritium if felt necessary.
- Q3 Serial Maturation of single technologies with H₂/D₂, discard variants, and do afterwards a complete validation testing of the prime candidate with tritium (e.g. pellet injection, membrane separation).
- Q4 Parallel maturation of single technologies, where the function depends strongly on tritium, for H₂/D₂ and T₂. This involves investigating several variants under tritium (e.g. isotope separation, tritium extraction).
- Q5 Develop technologies that can only be developed with tritium (tritium sensors and instruments).

When allocating the necessary testing & qualification categories to each prime technology in the fuel cycle, it is clearly found that the inner loop systems generally sit in lower Q categories, but have at the same time lower TRL than the systems in the outer loop, which have higher TRL and for many of which there exists already some form of initial industrial supply chain (this role is being played by National Labs such as Savannah River National Lab in US, by Nuclear Institutions such as CNL in Canada, and by plant engineering companies such as Tyne Engineering).

Experimental facilities

The prime facilitators for technology maturation are experimental devices. They can be subdivided in four types.

Type A devices are classical laboratory set-ups, operated without tritium. They are essential steps in early phases of a technology development, but do not provide integrated results.

Type B devices are facilities that provide an integrated test architecture for connected systems, but are not licensed for tritium. The DIPAK facility, currently under construction at KIT, is the most important representative of such devices (included in the running TFV Work Plan). It allows a sound demonstration of the integrated behaviour of all technologies in the two inner fuel cycle loops. However, due to cost increases, DIPAK has to be realized in stages, with a complete deployment only well beyond 2027.

Type C devices allow single technology validation under tritium. This requires the handling of tritium in amounts that allow a representative scalable testing (this is in the range 20-100 g). The Tritium Laboratory at KIT and the H3AT facility in UK (the latter in the R&D area outside

the TIRTL loop) provide such opportunities. Discussions are ongoing in the current TFV programme to check the feasibility of using H3AT for the DT pellet injection validation (requiring of the order of 20-30 g tritium).

Finally, Type D devices allow for integrated testing under DT, they are (partial or complete) fuel cycle demonstrators. This is optionally possible in TLK as well as in the R&D part of H3AT, but expected not to become reality in this decade, definitely not anymore in FP9. The first accessible Type D facility world-wide will be the UNITY-2 testbed, currently being jointly developed by Canadian Nuclear Laboratories (CNL) and the private start-up Kyoto Fusioneering, planned to become operational in 2026.

Also the ITER fuel cycle can be regarded as a type D facility. Although ITER, after re-baselining, is not expected to be able to contribute in time to the maturation programme discussed here, it can add a final validation (however limited only to the technologies used in the ITER fuel cycle). The late availability of ITER is partly compensated by the TIRTL programme in H3AT which is characterizing a 1/20th scale of the ITER fuel cycle.

Gap identification

The yellow boxes in Table 1 below denote gaps that require final additional, currently uncovered efforts with tritium to achieve a high technical readiness.

As indicated in the most right column, most of these gaps could be bridged if the fuel cycle necessary for a Volumetric Neutron Source (VNS) project⁴ is exploited accordingly. The '+' in the corresponding column indicates that the VNS fuel cycle will have identical functions, so testing the technologies behind would come 'automatically'. In particular, the two directly blanket interfacing system blocks 'tritium conditioning' and 'coolant purification' would thus be taken to integrated system demonstration.

As shown in the table, the elaboration of a reactor relevant accountancy system is currently at the lowest technical readiness level, and activities inside TFV are limited (HERA experiment). With regard to available equipment and expertise TLK has equipment and expertise both to tackle the accountancy system R&D for DEMO, as well as for the remaining ITER fuel cycle R&D.

With this, there remain two additional unsolved gaps, namely the validation of the two remaining technologies which do process the DT in mixed form rather than separated isotopes: the metal foil pump for fuel separation, and the temperature swing absorption for rebalancing. These functionalities are not necessary for a dedicated fuel cycle, which is tailored to VNS (understood to be a facility as described in footnote 4). But it could be installed there for test purposes without compromising the main function of a VNS fuel cycle.

Alternatively, to bridge this gap in shorter time, already near-term, cooperation with UNITY-2 could be envisaged. UNITY-2 is a relevant scale demonstration facility for fuel cycle testing (all loops) and operation, where the plasma is replaced by a vacuum vessel with a DT feed stream. It will include a Direct Internal Recycling loop and the opportunities to test and intercompare

⁴ This analysis is preliminary, as the VNS concept is in a very early state. Current assumptions are: (i) small (major radius 2-3 m), low fusion power (< 50 MW) DT fusion device generating a high 14 MeV neutron flux by beam-target interactions; not relying on high plasma confinement ($Q \leq 1$), and (ii) no requirement for tritium breeding self-sufficiency or electricity production. In particular it is assumed that the exhaust gas has to be split down to the full isotopic level, as the feed stream of the NBIs is assumed to be (pure) deuterium while the one of the gas injection to the plasma is assumed to be (pure) tritium. Furthermore, it is believed that fuelling can be done with gas injection only (no need for pellet injection).

different related fuel separation technologies. In this regard, it allows testing fuel cycle systems and functions which will not necessarily be needed in a dedicated VNS fuel cycle.

On a longer time scale (after delivery of the full DIPAK scope by the end of the present decade), it may also be an option to make better use of the situation that DIPAK is located in the neighbouring building of TLK by linking both facilities together, and thus to significantly expand the experimental capabilities of DIPAK to include testing with tritium.

Table 1. Testing & Qualification assessment of fuel cycle technologies. The yellow boxes indicate areas where the necessary tritium testing capability is not covered by the current TFV programme. In cases where ITER is mentioned as maturation opportunity, this refers to the TIRTL ITER relevant tritium loop to be tested in H3AT.

System Block	Function	Prime Technology Choice	TRL	Testing & Qualification Category	Experimental Device for Maturation; Gaps	VNS
Gas distribution control & monitoring	To control conditions of fuel (quantities, pressures, composition) to gas or pellet injection	Process vessel	3	Q1	DIPAK	
Gas injection	To provide gases (different species) to the torus and divertor for edge control, power loss management, radiative seeding of the divertor, and detachment control.	Pipe flows with valves	2 (fast) – 5 (slow)	Q2	DIPAK, followed by confirmative validation with T	+
Pellet injection	To launch pellets into the machine for fuelling and plasma control (pure fuel, fuel doped with core radiator, fuel pellets for ELM pacing if needed)	Extrusion + centrifuge	3.5	Q3-Q4	DIPAK, H3AT (tbc)	
Fuel separation and torus vacuum	To recover and recycle unburnt fuel from the torus exhaust, and assist torus evacuation	Metal foil pump	3.5	Q3	DIPAK, followed by confirmative validation with T	
Vacuum pumping	To evacuate the torus and compress the torus exhaust to plant pressure	Mercury diffusion + ejector + ring pump	4	Q2 (mechanical) Q3 (momentum transfer)	DIPAK, followed by confirmative validation with T	+
Exhaust processing	To separate hydrogen from non-hydrogens, To recover and separate hydrogen from compounds, and separate, To recover PEGs from the torus exhaust	Permeator + reactor + converter	4.5	n.a.	Not needed [ITER (TIRTL) RoX]	+
Isotope rebalancing and protium removal	To remove protium from the fuel and to perform adjustments of the isotope ratio	Temperature swing absorption	3	Q4	DIPAK, and development with tritium in parallel	

Exhaust detritiation	To detritiate gas and air streams from various sources under normal and off-normal conditions and to discharge them to stack or recirculate them	Recombiner, condenser, molsieve, wet scrubber	5	Q4	ITER (TIRTL) RoX, industry, wet scrubber technology needs demonstration with tritium	+
Water detritiation	To recover tritium from water, to purify and detritiate water and provide pre-enrichment for the isotope separation system, to provide final scrubbing of protium from the isotope separation	CECE or water distillation	5	Q5	ITER (TIRTL) RoX, industry, water distillation technology needs demonstration with tritium	+
Coolant purification (system interfacing to WPBB blanket)	To recover hydrogen isotopes from coolant loops (helium coolant); to pre-enrich and route tritiated water to the water detritiation system (water coolant)	Copperoxide/molsieve, CECE, water distillation	3-5	Q4	industry, water distillation technology needs demonstration with tritium	+
Tritium conditioning (system interfacing to WPBB TERS)	To remove tritiated hydrogens from the PbLi purge gas stream and reflux the purge gas (WCLL variant); To remove helium from the tritium carrying streams leaving TERS (HCPB variant)	Permeator, getter (depending on tritium extraction technology used, depending on blanket concept)	3-5	Q4	industry, getter technology needs demonstration with tritium	+
Isotope separation	To detritiate hydrogen streams and to enrich tritium to fuel quality	Cryogenic distillation	5	n.a.	Not needed [ITER (TIRTL) RoX, industry]	+
Gas storage	To store hydrogen isotopologues when the reactor is in maintenance or shut-down modes, to store tritium for import into and export out of the fuel cycle, and to recover He-3.	(Depleted) Uranium-Bed	7	n.a.	Not needed	+
Auxiliary vacuum	To provide vacuum for clients that will never or only in exceptional cases see tritium	COTS vacuum systems	8	Q1	Not needed	

Tritium management & control chain	all tritium measurements relevant to supporting the DEMO licensing and regulatory processes to comply with non-proliferation and accountancy regulations	Accountancy system	2	Q5	Done in Labs, then to be industrialized	+
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Glossary

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Definition</i>
CECE	Combined Electrolysis and Catalytic Exchange
CNL	Canadian Nuclear Laboratories
COTS	Commercial off the shelf
DIPAK	Direct Internal Recycling Integrated Development Platform Karlsruhe (Testbed at KIT)
DIRL	Direct Internal Recycling Loop
ELM	Edge Localised Mode
FP	Framework Programme
H3AT	Hydrogen-3 Advanced Testing (Testbed at UKAEA)
HCPB	Helium Cooled Pebble Bed
HERA	Hydrogen Experiment for Real Time Analysis (Testbed at UKAEA)
INTL	Innner Tritium Plant Loop
OUTL	Outer Tritium Plant Loop
PEG	Plasma Enhancement Gas
RoX	Return of Experience
TERS	Tritium Extraction and Recovery System (of the blankets)
TIRTL	The ITER Reduced Scale Tritium Loop
TLK	Tritium Laboratory Karlsruhe
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
UNITY-2	Unique Test Facility (planned Testbed at CNL)
VNS	Volumetric Neutron Source
WCLL	Water Cooled Lithium Lead

Report Annex 2.1

Overview on existing development, testing & qualification strategy for the Breeding Blanket and the related tritium extraction & recovery systems, which can be done without neutrons, and possible gaps

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Introduction

The EUROfusion Work Package Breeding Blanket (WPBB) focuses on completing the conceptual design of the BB systems, including the Tritium Extraction System (TER), in alignment with the specific requirements and interfaces of DEMO. During the Preliminary Conceptual Design (PCD) Phase, the primary objective was to strengthen the technical foundation and address major technical challenges associated with the candidate blanket concepts. Initially, four blanket concepts developed in Europe underwent review, but as the program progressed, the focus narrowed down to two concepts: the Helium Cooled Pebble Bed (HCPB) and the Water Cooled Lead-Lithium (WCLL). These two concepts were considered more mature and promising as driver blankets for the DEMO power plant. Also, the Test Blanket Module (TBM) program aligned with the choice of these concepts. The aim of the PCD was to consolidate a design by 2020 and identify the technical issues and research and development (R&D) gaps for the next phase of Concept Design (CD).

In order to qualify the selected candidates w.r.t. phenomena not involving fusion neutrons, a large technology R&D program has been deployed since the PCD and continues through the CD phase, basically oriented at assessing critical feasibility questions of the concepts, to reduce uncertainties in design parameters and scale-up on Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the present technologies. For the CD, the need for BB relevant test facilities has been considered central for the process of selecting the primary, i.e., the “driver” blanket for DEMO, which will have a major impact on the overall design and safety features.

The selection of the best option for the DEMO “driver” and “advanced” BBs has been originally planned for 2024/2025. The criteria associated to the selection process will take into account elements provided by the WPBB design and R&D program, by the inputs of the DEMO key interfacing systems and by the Return of eXperience (RoX) of the ITER TBM programme. A selection of “driver” and “advanced” BB will enable to prioritize and carry out the R&D needed to reach the DEMO conceptual plant design in 2027.

Existing non-nuclear validation and qualification testing strategy

In order to execute the aforementioned strategy, the WPBB has been divided in “system design” and “technology” (R&D) legs (S-leg and T-leg, respectively). For the T-leg, validation and qualification testing are fundamental elements. To this respect, a large number of facilities exist throughout the EU for the non-nuclear qualification of BB systems. The qualification tests are subdivided here into the following areas and the facilities available for such qualification testing are described subsequently:

- Helium cooled BB technologies
- Water cooled BB technologies
- Tritium behaviour in materials and tritium extraction technologies
- PbLi technologies and safety
- MHD effects in liquid metals
- Corrosion of structural material
- Manufacturing technologies

The R&D and testing plan is reflected in the WPBB Project Execution Plan (PEP) [1]. The following Table 1 summarizes the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) of the WPBB in the PEP, focusing in the planned validation and qualification needs and plans, providing a link to the aforementioned testing areas.

Table 1: WPBB WBS plan with focus on testing plan and and link to the qualification area

WBS ID	WBS Task	WBS Scope	Link to testing / qualification
BB.S	System Design	Development of BB system design	n/a
BB.S.01	<i>Systems Engineering</i>	<i>Tasks related to the System Engineering</i>	n/a
BB.S.02	<i>System Design</i>	<i>Design activities (BB System Design and TER)</i>	n/a
BB.S.03	<i>HCPB Modelling</i>	<i>Modelling activities in support of the HCPB design.</i>	n/a
BB.S.03.01	Pebble Bed Mechanical modelling	R&D is concentrated in the measurement of thermal and mechanical properties of the pebble beds, on the development of constitutive equation for the materials. The validation of related computational tools is planned by testing in relevant facilities.	Helium cooled BB technologies
BB.S.03.02	Thermo-hydraulics of He flow Modelling	Several numerical codes are used to simulate the cooling performances of the blanket. To estimate and reduce the associated modelling uncertainties generated through the aforementioned numerical codes, a thorough validation and verification procedure is planned in relevant facilities	Helium cooled BB technologies
BB.S.04	<i>WCLL Modelling</i>	<i>Modelling activities in support of the WCLL design. They include tools development and code validations.</i>	n/a
BB.S.04.01	MHD modelling of the PbLi flow	A continuous development and validation of the MHD code is necessary. New tools have to be developed and experiments in relevant WCLL conditions are planned to support the code development.	MHD effects in liquid metals

WBS ID	WBS Task	WBS Scope	Link to testing / qualification
BB.S.04.02	PbLi flow modelling	In the development of the WCLL BB, a particular issue is related to the modelling of the PbLi flow in operational and accidental conditions. This can be achieved by means of codes' coupling capable to manage different simulation scales. Tests are planned to validate these codes. Also, simulation of the He bubbles formation, transport and accumulation is a necessary R&D which requires validation testing in relevant facilities.	PbLi technologies and safety
BB.S.04.03	Thermo-hydraulics of Water flow modelling	Several numerical codes are used to simulate the cooling performances of the WCLL BB. Code's development, verification and validation activities are needed and testing is therefore planned in relevant facilities.	Water cooled BB technologies
BB.S.05	<i>Common Modelling</i>	<i>Modelling activities in common to the two blanket concepts.</i>	
BB.S.05.01	Tritium transport modelling	The development of a reliable T transport model is essential for the design of the BB systems. Large uncertainties affect the model parameters, therefore their validation is key. Different tests are planned in several available facilities.	Tritium behaviour in materials and tritium extraction technologies
BB.S.05.02	Nuclear Data	The scope encompasses nuclear data evaluations and nuclear response files; development of advanced evaluation tools and nuclear models; integral nuclear validation experiments; nuclear cross section measurements and development of measurement techniques.	n/a
BB.T	Technology R&D	Accompanying R&D programme necessary to the driver blanket selection and qualification of the BB Conceptual Design.	n/a
BB.T.01	<i>HCPB R&D</i>	<i>Accompanying R&D programme dedicated to supporting the development of the HCPB BB.</i>	
BB.T.01.01	Solid Breeder development	Solid Breeder materials for the use in the HCPB concept have to be developed and characterization tests are planned in suitable facilities.	Helium cooled BB technologies Tritium behaviour in materials and tritium extraction technologies
BB.T.01.02	Beryllium and Beryllides development	Multiplier materials for the use in the HCPB concept have to be developed and characterization tests are planned in suitable facilities	n/a
BB.T.01.03	Irradiations for CB and Beryllium	This activity is mandatory to conclude the characterisation of the advanced ceramic breeder pebbles and the beryllide rods.	n/a

WBS ID	WBS Task	WBS Scope	Link to testing / qualification
BB.T.01.04	Tritium extraction from Purge Gas.	The reference extraction process for the HCPB in PCP is based on cryogenic batch processes with water adsorption on a reactive molecular sieve bed (RMSB) followed by elemental tritium adsorption at 77 K. To overcome some drawback of the present system, the substitution of the cryogenic system with getter beds will be studied in parallel. Studies are planned to operate at high He pressure and in the optimization of the steam content in purge flow to reduce T permeation to the coolant.	Tritium behaviour in materials and tritium extraction technologies ¹
BB.T.01.05	Helium cooling technology at fusion conditions	Helium cooling technology at fusion conditions is to be qualified here in relevant facilities to demonstrate power dissipation from BB (especially peaks of 1 MW/m ² at the FW).	Helium cooled BB technologies
BB.T.02	WCLL R&D	<i>The accompanying R&D programme dedicated to supporting the development of the WCLL blanket concept.</i>	
BB.T.02.01	Liquid Breeder development	R&D efforts to ensure a future supply of the order of 1000 t as necessary for a reactor or large test facilities. The completion of the data base of PbLi is an important topic planned to be covered by testing in relevant facilities.	PbLi technologies and safety
BB.T.02.02	Tritium extraction from PbLi.	Due to lack of final results in key tests of the possible extraction technologies (PAV, GCL or LVC), the selection of a process for the design of the DEMO TER is still pending and will be completed only in the first phase of the conceptual design. Three PbLi technologies for T extraction are considered (PAV, GLC and LVC) and experiments are planned to support the selection of a reference technology in dedicated test facilities.	Tritium behaviour in materials and tritium extraction technologies ²
BB.T.02.03	Water cooling technology at fusion conditions	The effects of neutron at 14 MeV and gamma on the water properties have to be investigated in view of activation, radiolysis and interaction with chemical additives to control corrosion. The presence of large concentration of T can affect the overall chemistry. Experimental campaigns are planned to consolidate the selected reference water chemistry.	Water cooled BB technologies
BB.T.02.04	Coating development.	The issues related to several different critical topics of coatings are to be tested and qualified in dedicated facilities.	Tritium behaviour in materials and tritium extraction technologies

¹ Only partial qualification possible. The qualification of the HCPB TER system is an identified gap in the R&D

² Only partial qualification possible. The qualification of the WCLL TER system is an identified gap in the R&D

WBS ID	WBS Task	WBS Scope	Link to testing / qualification
			Corrosion of structural material
BB.T.02.05	PbLi purification	PbLi produces several transmutation products and corrodes the surrounding structures dissolving some of the elements, which can be then activated. These transmutation and corrosion and therefore must be also removed from it. Also, ⁶ Li is burned out during operation and has to be refilled to avoid degradation of the TBR. For this, Scope of the R&D in this WBS is to validate performance parameters to design suitable systems of the PbLi loop and their qualification in corresponding facilities.	PbLi technologies and safety
BB.T.03	<i>Common R&D</i>	<i>The common accompanying R&D programme dedicated to supporting the development of the HCPB and WCLL blanket concepts</i>	
BB.T.03.01	Manufacturing Technologies	The main objective is to identify manufacturing routes to allow building BB segments with suitable tolerances and identify suitable technologies to be developed in the engineering phase to manufacture the required components at a sufficient level of reliability and at reasonable costs. Fabrication Mock-Ups (FMU) are planned for manufacturing with relevant technology to demonstrate feasibility and start a qualification program. These FMUs require preliminary verification tests in dedicated facilities.	Manufacturing technologies Helium cooled BB technologies Water cooled BB technologies Water cooled BB technologies
BB.T.03.02	PMU test programme	This WBS plans qualification tests of Prototypical Mock-Ups (PMU) under relevant loading conditions, to verify thermo-hydraulic and structural performance of sub-components at prototypical scale in relevant facilities.	Helium cooled BB technologies Water cooled BB technologies
BB.T.04	<i>New Facilities</i>	<i>The investigation of integral effects requires building new facilities to address such tests.</i>	
BB.T.04.01	HCPB TER Facility	The proposed TER loop prototype facility should to combine He circulators (and several heat exchanger and heaters), T extraction units, make-up units for chemistry control, purification units, regeneration loops. H/D to simulate T behavior. Attention to be provided for instrumentation in order to detect H/D with the necessary accuracy.	Helium cooled BB technologies ³

³ HCPB TER only partially investigated during FP9. Qualification of a TER loop is a gap identified and recommended to be covered for the next phase.

WBS ID	WBS Task	WBS Scope	Link to testing / qualification
BB.T.04.02	WCLL TER Facility	The proposed TER loop prototype facility needs to combine T extraction, He extraction, PbLi pumps, PbLi purification, auxiliary systems for the solubilised H isotopes and He in PbLi. H/D to be used to simulate T behaviour. PbLi instrumentation to be designed and qualified in order to operate in PbLi loop at relevant DEMO operative conditions.	Water cooled BB technologies ⁴
BB.T.04.03	HCPB helium loop at TBM scale	HELOKA facility upgrade (renewal of license and, mainly, updating the control and data acquisition system to account for evolution in the HW (PC) and the associated software)	Helium cooled BB technologies
BB.T.04.04	WCLL water loop at TBM scale	A test section has to be provided for the WCLL qualification test programme at relevant PWR conditions. The construction of a facility capable for this type of qualification is scheduled in the early stage of the CD phase.	Water cooled BB technologies
BB.T.04.05	Ceramic Breeder production Facility	Upgrade of the KALOS process for the semi-industrial production of ceramic pebble bed.	n/a
BB.T.04.06	PbLi Breeder Zone Test Bed	Construction of a facility dedicated to the study of the BZ of the WCLL Blanket.	Water cooled BB technologies

Existing facilities for the qualification of helium-cooled BB technologies

The HELOKA facility (KIT) is a helium loop for large scale single-effects testing of relevant helium-cooled breeding blanket mock-ups and sub-components. It consists of 2 loops:

- HELOKA-HP: for qualification of BB relevant mock-ups (vacuum chamber of 21 m³, capable of testing a 1:1 TBM) at a temperature range of 100 °C to 500 °C, with mass flows between 0.2 kg/s and 1.3 kg/s, pressures from 40 bar to 90 bar, capable of reproducing heat fluxes of 0.3 – 0.5 MW/m² (e.g. on a FW) and volumetric heating of 10 kW (extendible to 1 MW).
- KATHELO: qualification of BB small mock-ups and He-cooled divertor, available mass flow rate from 0.05 kg/s to 0.2 kg/s and temperature range from 100 to 800 °C, equipped with a 800 kW Electron Gun, capable of achieving volumetric heating of 50 kW (extendible to 1 MW).

The HE-FUS3 loop (ENEA) is a helium loop designed to study the cooling circuit of the HCPB or HCLL TBMs in ITER and relevant BB components and sub-assemblies at a maximum design pressure of 10.5 MPa, a maximum design temperature of 530 °C and a mass flow rate between 0.05 kg/s – 0.35 kg/s. The EBBTF facility is coupled to the HE-FUS3 facility and aims at modelling tool development and validation platform.

⁴ WCLL TER only partially investigated during FP9. Qualification of a TER loop is a gap identified and recommended to be covered for the next phase.

It is capable of testing components of the HCPB BB concept and TBM mock-ups under relevant conditions.

The DIADEMO loop (CEA) is a small He loop operating at 80 bar and a mass flow rate of 30 g/s, at temperatures between 300 – 500 °C for the qualification of relevant BB sub-components (e.g. cooling plates) also under cyclic loading.

Existing facilities for the qualification of water-cooled BB technologies

For the qualification of the WCLL BB concept at relevant scale, as well as the WCLL TBM, the W-HYDRA platform is being projected at ENEA Brasimone. As part of this platform, the Water Loop facility is a water loop at Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) conditions, which should offer similar capabilities as HELOKA but for water-cooled concepts, including a 800 kW Electron Gun to represent high heat fluxes in subcomponents (e.g. FW).

The HELCZA loop (IPP.CR) is a water-cooled high heat flux electron-beam (800 kW) facility to perform high heat flux tests on FW mock-ups and/or BB module mock-ups (4 m² testing area, 2.45 m diameter vacuum chamber) at 50 bar and maximum water temperature of 150 °C (normal operating conditions, non PWR-like conditions).

The HIVE loop (UKAEA) is a water-cooled loop for small component thermohydraulic qualification testing (20 mm x 20 mm) at high heat fluxes (up to 20 MW/m²) by direct induction heating (10 kW). The loop works at low pressure water (non PWR conditions) and can be adapted for other coolant media. For larger test articles (1.67 x 0.96 x 0.46) m³, the CHIMERA facility is being built by UKAEA. This is a combined-effect facility in which relevant water-cooled mock-ups can be tested under high magnetic fields (4 T) taking into account as well PbLi flow. This facility will allow a surface heating of 0.5 MW/m² over 1.67 m x 0.46 m and a volumetric heating of 100 kW and PWR water conditions.

The HADES facility at CEA permits the qualification of high heat flux removal from plasma facing components of water-cooled BB concepts. The facility can cover thermal fatigue tests, critical heat fluxes and thermal shocks and has been designed to provide maximum performance and flexibility for the qualification of plasma facing components, e.g. the FW, yet at non-PWR conditions. The facility includes an electron gun of 150 kW.

For the qualification of optimized water chemistry set-ups, the HTHP facility in ENEA is available.

Existing facilities for the qualification of tritium behaviour in materials and extraction technologies

The TLK facility (KIT) has a large infrastructure that allows to carry out experiments with tritium at concentration levels that are DEMO relevant. Significant activities are under development with respect to extending the infrastructure with experimental rigs for processing PbLi especially targeting the processes for tritium recovery from PbLi. This facility can aim at validating methods and technologies with respect to mitigating

tritium permeation related to the HCPB and WCLL and can provide performance validation using tritium of key components of the technology for the tritium extraction system relevant for the chosen BB option. Examples of past activities: tritium extraction from He purge gas at small scale with tritium using membranes and tritium extraction from low velocity PbLi at small scale with tritium using vacuum sieve tray.

The TRIEX facility (ENEA) aims at qualification testing of tritium extraction technology from PbLi. It aims at testing all major tritium extraction technologies from PbLi, namely the Permeator Against Vacuum (PAV), the Gas Liquid Contactor (GLC) and the Vacuum Sieve Tray (VST) extraction at medium scale.

The PERI II facility (ENEA) allows qualifying the performance of anti-permeation coating with the measure of permeation reduction factor (PRF). This facility operates with hydrogen at a maximum temperature of 650 °C.

The HyFraMe facility at the ENEA Membrane Laboratory allows small-scale experimental set-ups for testing gas permeability in metal and ceramic membranes (in the single tube test section) and the qualification of separation and recovery processes from gaseous and liquid streams in a Pd-Ag membrane reactor, e.g. to perform experiments of hydrogen isotopes removal from a gas stream characteristic of the HCPB BB. Also, the Hyper-QuarCh II facility permits the qualification of advanced hydrogen permeation sensors.

Additionally, hydrogen and deuterium solubility, measurement of the PbLi Sievert's constant, permeation tests and qualification of sensors for the measure of HT concentration in PbLi can be performed at the Hydrogen Laboratory at ENEA.

Several facilities exist at CIEMAT for the qualification of tritium behaviour and tritium extraction from PbLi:

- The Van der Gaals electron accelerator is an irradiation facility (2 MeV electron accelerator) for thermal-desorption spectroscopy (TDS) during/after irradiation (ceramic breeder characterization)
- The Ion implanter facility is an irradiation facility (60 kV ion implanter) to perform H isotope implantation at a controlled temperature. Ceramic breeder characterization can be performed then through ionoluminescence and ceramic breeder H isotope release can be measured through TDS.
- The RIPER facility is a permeation system coupled to a 2 MeV electron accelerator which permits to evaluate permeation during irradiation as a function of temperature, pressure and dose rate. It is also possible to measure radiation induced deuterium absorption/desorption processes.
- The Thermoperm facility is a permeation test facility where H isotope permeation (0.1-1000 mbar, 20-550 °C) can be assessed through thermos-diffusion characterization. TDS up to 1000 °C after H isotope loading or implantation can be performed to qualify H isotope release from ceramic breeder.
- The CLIPPER facility permits the qualification of tritium extraction from PbLi with PAV technology by means of hydrogen/deuterium tests on the test rig simulating this process. Different permeator concepts as well as different materials for the membrane of the PAV process can be tested. The loop is

constructed to adapt the test section to different extraction technologies (e.g. VST).

- The COOPER facility aims at the qualification of co and counter permeation effects.

Existing facilities for the qualification of PbLi technologies and safety

The LI-FUS5/Mod3 facility at ENEA aims at the safety qualification of Loss-of-Coolant Accidents (LOCAs) relevant for BBs working with PbLi and water cooling (e.g. WCLL). It is composed of two independent test sections: A and B. Both test sections are able to inject water at the pressure up to 200 bar and up to 350 °C. The interaction vessel of the test section B is qualified at 500 °C and 200 bar, whereas test section A is qualified at 430 °C and 155 bar. Currently, Test section B is dedicated to investigate the issue of the catastrophic tube rupture in the WCLL BB. It can measure temperature, pressure, strain and hydrogen. Maximum data acquisition frequency is 10 kHz, which allows to detect the propagation of the pressure waves in the vessel and the consequent material strains. In this configuration, it is suitable for code model development and validation (i.e. SIMMER). Test section A is currently involved in R&D activities related the small leakage dection for Gen.IV reactors.

The IELLLO PbLi loop at ENEA permits the qualification of the thermo-fluid dynamics of relevant BBs working with PbLi (e.g. WCLL, HCLL), including the characterization of instrumentation, auxiliary circuits and components relevant to PbLi loops. At the moment, the facility is planned for execution of tests on WCLL-TBM prototypical mock-ups. IELLLO is coupled with HE-FUS3 to form the so-called EBBTF facility, in order to test relevant components of the HCLL blanket concept, testing of former HCLL TBM mock-ups in ITER relevant conditions and as experimental platform for development of modelling tools and their validation.

In order to qualify PbLi purification technologies, the VOSA, COSA, MELILOO and HELELIA facilities (the latter still under construction) have been erected at IPP.CR. These facilities are dedicated to the testing the removal of volatile, active contaminant products from PbLi (e.g. Zn, Hg), the determination of solubility of dissolved steel elements in PbLi (e.g. Cr, Fe), the determination of the He solubility in PbLi to understand the transport and desorption of He into clusters towards the qualification of the technology for the outgasing of He from PbLi.

Existing facilities for the qualification of MHD effects in liquid metals

The MEKKA facility at KIT aims at the qualification of MHD phenomena in BBs working with liquid metals under fusion relevant magnetic fields. A closed NaK loop (200 l) with a 2.1 T magnet and mass flow of 25 m³/h makes the facility suitable for fundamental as well as mock-up qualification tests.

The MAPLE-U facility at KIT (formerly at UCLA) aims as well at the qualification of MHD phenomena in BBs working with liquid metals under fusion relevant magnetic fields. The difference with MEKKA is that this facility directly works with PbLi and has a tilting mechanism to obtain different orientation of the mock-ups in order to study

the effect of gravity in the liquid metal flow, i.e. it allows qualification testing of multiple-effect phenomena.

The CHIMERA facility at UKAEA aims at qualification tests of complete sub-modules (1:1 TBM-like size) of BB concepts working with PbLi and water cooling with multiple load combinations targeting at multiple-effect testing, i.e., nuclear heating, surface heating, high magnetic field (static and dynamic) and nuclear heating. The facility operates with both low (5 MPa) and high (15.5 MPa, PWR-like) water pressure.

Existing facilities for the qualification of corrosion of structural material

The PICOLO loop at KIT consists of a PbLi loop for corrosion qualification testing of small articles (cylindrical samples of about 10 mm diameter) of RAFM-steels and coatings under PbLi flows. The test section can operate at a PbLi temperature range of 350 °C – 550 °C at flow speeds between 0.01 m/s and 1 m/s.

The CiCLO facility at CIEMAT aims at studying the corrosion behaviour of RAFM steels with PbLi. The main characteristic of the loop is that the pipework has been coated with tantalum. As a result, corrosion products in the loop pipework are avoided, making no influence in the corrosion phenomena in the test section, thus providing clean data of the corrosion behaviour of the test article under PbLi flow.

The RACHEL laboratory at ENEA permits the test of alumina coatings exposed to PbLi flows to evaluate the influence in the hydrogen isotope anti-permeation performance of these coatings after the exposure and chemical interaction of the coatings with PbLi.

The LOOP facility at the IPUL is a PbLi loop with the capability of studying corrosion processes under magnetic fields (multiple-effect testing). The loop can operate at relevant steel temperatures (550 °C) at strong magnetic fields (1.7 T).

Existing facilities for the qualification of manufacturing technologies

For the qualification of manufacturing technologies, all water and helium cooled facilities able to test subcomponents at relevant surface and volumetric heating conditions (e.g. HELOKA, HE-FUS3, Water Loop, etc) are available to the qualification of manufacturing technologies through thermo-mechanical testing.

Additionally, 2 facilities are available in UKAEA specialized in mechanical testing, fabrication and qualification of manufacturing technologies. On one side, the Materials Technology Laboratory (MTL) houses 2 tensile test frames capable of testing at high temperature (up to 750 °C) and inert/vacuum conditions (e.g. for high temperature testing of joints including fatigue and creep). Micro hardness machines, material characterization furnaces and thermal conductivity measurements are also available in this facility. On the other side, the Special Techniques Group (STG) is a manufacturing facility specialized in components for ultra-high vacuum using vacuum brazing, welding and diffusion bonding. Development of post welding heat treatment processes could be performed by close linking the MTL and STG facilities.

Possible identified gaps

On the qualification of the TER system

The reference tritium extraction process developed during the PCD for low pressure He purge flow for the HCPB is based on cryogenic batch processes with water adsorption on a reactive molecular sieve bed (RMSB) followed by elemental tritium adsorption, mainly as HT form, at 77 K. To overcome some drawback of the present system (e.g. costs) the substitution of the cryogenic system with getter beds will be studied in parallel. Prior to design work on a 1:10 scale getter bed mock-up, an experimental assessment of NEG (“non-evaporable getter”) materials and characterization of residual tritium inventories is planned due to the risk of non-favourable results on “heels”. Also, studies are being carried out to operate at high He pressure and in the optimization of the steam content in purge flow to reduce T permeation to the coolant. However, the qualification of the whole HCPB TER system to validate the technology choices in a holistic manner is not yet included in the plan and will require appropriate funding to realize a prototype of such system in representative dimensions and functionality after G2.

Similarly, after the selection of the appropriate Tritium Extraction Unit (TEU) technology for the PbLi (among Permeation Against Vacuum - PAV, Gas-Liquid Contact - GLC or Liquid-Vacuum Contact - LVC technologies), a proper qualification testing of the WCLL TER system is mandatory by means of a prototype facility representative of the main processes involved in the PbLi loop. This not only involves the TEU, but also the subsystems dedicated to the purification of PbLi from activated corrosion and volatile products, removal of He from Li transmutation and the online “refuelling” of PbLi from burned up ${}^6\text{Li}$, the chemical control of PbLi and the control of permeated tritium and corrosion control by means of the coatings in the BB and TER loop. The demonstration of the operation of all these subsystems in a holistic way in a prototype test facility will qualify this system for DEMO. Therefore it is a required step towards the validation of key selected technology choices to take into account after G2, providing for it appropriate funding.

On the blanket attachment to the Vacuum Vessel

Another key aspect of the BB concepts is the system of mechanical supports to the vacuum vessel (VV). During FP8, the architecture of the BB concepts has been re-designed to introduce back the so-called “single module segments” (SMS), instead of “multi-model segments” (MMS). In the MMS, TBM-like size modules are conceived to be individually attached either to the VV or to a supporting structure. In the SMS, the BB segments are a single, long, slender, prismatic structure attached to the VV by mechanical supports. The requirements on this supporting system in terms of structural integrity and alignment/tolerance capability are very severe. Currently, simplified thermal-structural analyses are performed for the design of the attachment system. However, a facility is still missing in the roadmap capable of representing SMS attachment with an appropriate set of mechanical supports to validate the concept experimentally and qualify the BB supporting concept against the load combinations.

On the provision of enriched lithium

For any blanket concept, natural lithium (with an isotopic composition of about 7.6% Li-6 and 92.4% Li-7) as breeder material will not lead to a local tritium breeding ratio large enough for reactor self-sufficiency. The only possible solution to overcome this problem is benefitting from the larger cross-section of Li-6 for the 1n-reaction, by using lithium that is significantly enriched in the content of Li-6.

For example for the WCLL blanket of a 2 GW fusion power device, a need of 1400 m³ (or 13'700 tons) of eutectic lithium-lead (PbLi), is assumed, comprising lithium enriched to 90% in Li-6. With a mass ratio of lithium in PbLi of $6.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$, this refers to an amount of 88 tons of pure Li-6. The consumption of Li-6 depends on the tritium production rate and is small compared to the large total lithium inventory (112 kg Li-6 consumption per full power year and GWfus). The same orders of magnitude hold also for other blanket concepts.

Today, the global market is still supplied mainly by what has been produced in the cold war times in the Y-12 National Security Complex in Oak Ridge. Typical current market prices for the small amounts sold on the market are in the order of ~ 50 k€/kg (95% enriched). Obviously, to make fusion a viable solution for energy supply, it is indispensable to build up a supply chain for enriched lithium.

The most efficient technology that was also used in Y-12 is based on isotopic exchange between lithium amalgam and an aqueous lithium hydroxide solution, flowing in large counter current columns (COLEX process). In Y-12, environmental contamination with mercury from the process plant turned out to be an issue as mercury was handled in open columns and vessels and released without further treatment in waste streams. Since that time, technology has been enhanced and environmental protection and monitoring as well as occupational health and safety have become an intrinsic element of each chemical plant development process. As consequence, if a process applying lithium amalgam as working fluid shall be applied today, no environmental issues would be expected (or the process would not be licensed at all).

For lithium isotope separation, there are various alternative processes described in literature, but many of them rely on organic working fluids and/or work in aqueous phase which is not tritium compatible and hence exclude re-processing of used tritiated blanket lithium, another important requirement on the to be chosen technology. And none of them has ever been demonstrated to the scale which would be needed to consider it as candidate for fusion.

It is therefore recommended to (re-)develop the mercury-based process towards a process that is improved in operational control, environmentally friendly, optimized in terms of reduced mercury inventory, and sufficiently robust⁵. Following the known development stages in chemical engineering, a production plant with relevant throughput can become available in 10 years from now, if a fast way to deployment is followed.

⁵ Such process has been introduced in literature as ICOMAX Process (Improved COlumn-based Mercury Amalgam eXchange), see: Th. Giegerich et al., Development of a viable route for lithium-6 supply of DEMO and future fusion power plants, Fusion Engineering and Design 149 (2019)111339.

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Report Annex 2.2

Summary of expected Return of Experience (RoX) from ITER TBM for the BB qualification and timescales

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Date: 16/June/2023

Introduction

The EU TBM Program so far, i.e., before concluding the ongoing process of ITER re-baselining, is closely aligned with the DEMO Program and aims to validate the DEMO Breeding Blanket (BB) design to the fullest extent possible. This involves designing, manufacturing, and operating the WCLL (Water-Cooled Lithium lead) and HCPB (Helium-Cooled Pebble Bed) TBS (Test Blanket System) to support the demonstration of compliance with the technical requirements of the DEMO blanket design. This validation process is not limited to experimental campaigns in ITER but encompasses all phases of the TBM Program, from conceptual design to installation and operation in ITER. The validation of the DEMO blanket design is an ongoing process, providing continuous feedback and potentially triggering design evolution based on the maturity of different design areas and accompanying research and development efforts. Stable DEMO blanket requirements are crucial to enable the TBM Program to define and execute the best strategy for demonstrating compliance with those requirements, which can involve technology performance assessment, return on experience, or recommendations. This is a brief overview on the return of experience (RoX) from the TBM Programme expected to feed the BB development programme in EUROfusion, also highlighting the schedule uncertainties potentially affecting this RoX.

Areas of Return of eXperience (RoX): expected information from the ITER TBM Programme for the BB development

Despite the criticality of the BB to the development of fusion power, no breeding blanket has ever been built or tested. It is widely accepted that ITER represents a unique testing opportunity for the BB by means of the TBM Programme. This programme is committed to validate at the maximum possible extent the DEMO BB design, offering a key RoX from it [1].

The information provided with the RoX can be classified into the following areas:

- Regulatory & Licensing process
- Project Management
- Design of the TBM & Ancillary Systems
- Safety & Rad-waste aspects
- Manufacturing of the TBM & Ancillary Systems
- Operation at ITER & Maintenance
- R&D

These RoX areas are briefly described in the following (more detailed presentation in [1] and [2]).

RoX from the Regulatory & Licensing process

As a nuclear pressurized equipment, the TBM system has to undergo a complete licensing process covering the full consultation cycle with an Agreed Notified Body and the ASN (French Nuclear Safety Authority). This will set jurisprudence for the DEMO BB and will represent the first licensing process on BB specific issues (materials, technologies and safety provision). For this, the implementation follows the French/European Regulation on (nuclear) Pressure Equipment (ESP(N)) Directive (PED, 2014/68/EU), ESPN Order (Arrêté du 30 décembre 2015).

The licensing process will be a first experience in risk/hazard analysis on BB relevant components & material, as well as experience in the conformity evaluation procedures (methodology), according to the level and risk category of the Nuclear Pressure Equipment (NPE). This means experience in preparation of requested information (e.g. hazard analysis, inspectability, traceability, compliance with technical references, etc) and experience in the interaction with a Regulator (ASN in this case) and a Notified Body at different stages of the licensing process.

RoX from Project Management

The BB is a complex, interdisciplinary system with multiple functional, geometrical and system interfaces, requiring concurrent multi-physics engineering. As a scale-down system, the TBM shares all these characteristics as well. Therefore, the experience in system engineering, requirement and verification, integration and interface management for TBM will be of value for DEMO or FPP BB. Also, the procurement of the TBM, the Product Lifecycle Management and the Quality Assurance and Control, in particular for the manufacturing of the TBMs will be also a valuable relevant experience for the BB.

Rox from the Design of the TBM & Ancillary Systems

The TBM falls under the ESP(N) equipment regulation and it is expected that an equivalent one will be applied for the BB in DEMO or FPP. The experience in the design under selected reference codes and standards (RCC-MRx) for the TBM is fundamental for the design of the DEMO BB, which is based at the moment on the same code selection. A dedicated DEMO Design Code (DDC) is under development,

but it contains most of the damage modes already known in RCC-MRx and follows equivalent calculation rules to that one.

The experience in engineering modelling, analysis and simulation for the determination of performance and operational domain and optimization of the TBMs are relevant for DEMO/FPP BB. This includes selection of appropriate constitutive models for specific phenomena (e.g., thermo-mechanics of pebble beds, turbulence modelling for inner flow in blanket components, etc.), selection of empirical correlations (Nu correlations for helium with turbulence promoters, critical heat flux correlations for water, interfacial heat transfer in pebble beds, etc.) and selection of numerical modelling tools, which required extensive verification and validation campaigns that can be transferred and used to the design of the BB system.

Finally, the experience collected in the integration of sensors and instrumentation and on nuclear maintenance plan and optimization and in the engineering design of mock-ups for validation of predictive tools in TBM is very valuable and applicable for BB.

Rox from Safety & Rad-waste aspects

The experience collected in the safety demonstration and approach for the licensing of the TBMs is a fundamental RoX from this programme to the BB project. This includes also the identification of Protection of Important Activities (PIA), the determination and classification of accidental events, together with the assessment and analysis of accidents, the tritium management (e.g. tritium permeation issue), the concept of instrumentation & control (I&C) for safety functions implementation and estimation of radioactive inventory and analysis of radioactive waste.

Rox from the Manufacturing of the TBM & Ancillary Systems

Due to the complex shape of the vacuum vessel, the BB topology strongly diverts from conventional nuclear or non-nuclear pressurized equipment. Therefore, the development of manufacturing technologies capable to produce complex shapes and subcomponents is another fundamental RoX from the TBM programme for the BB. This includes the development of advanced (non-conventional) fusion welding (laser, TIG, EB) & diffusion welding (Hot Isostatic Pressure, HIP) joints, high precision machining, experience in the control of distortions, standardization and qualification of manufacturing technologies for EUROFER97 components and structures, testing according to regulatory requirements and industrial standards (destructive and non-destructive examination – DE and NDE –, respectively), acceptance tests (e.g. determination of methodology for testing conditions like pressure tests) and cost of manufacturing and timing (also useful for preliminary cost estimations for BB).

RoX from the Operation at ITER and Maintenance

Despite the fundamental differences between the ITER and DEMO or a FPP with respect to plant architecture, systems and functions, the TBM programme still brings a valuable experience in the testing of blanket relevant components and materials in an integrated, multi-field, multi-physics testing environment. ITER offers a fusion relevant

environment where the operational verification of technological feasibility is still a relevant RoX for the BB.

The TBM programme will validate the neutronics, the tritium breeding predictive capability and modelling tools predictions, which is a key RoX of the TBM programme. In-service inspections, maintenance plans for TBS subsystems and the validation of the maintenance strategy in the TBM will be also a valuable precedent for the BB.

RoX from R&D activities

A vast number of R&D activities in the TBM programme are synergistic to the BB to the point that many are integrated in the Work Package BB in EUROfusion, both programmes taking advantage of the collaborative approach due to common objectives. Examples of relevant, common R&D are:

- EUROFER97 development and qualification
- Thermo-mechanics of pebble beds
- Solid/breeder development (fabrication, characterization and supply)
- Be-based neutron multiplier development
- Irradiations for CB and Beryllium/berryllides
- Tritium extraction from purge gas and PbLi
- MHD and PbLi flow modelling
- Thermal-hydraulics of water flow modelling
- Tritium transport modelling
- Coating development

Uncertainties in current schedule and impact

The current strategy foresees to begin the construction of DEMO once: (1) the physics scenario of DEMO and a FPP is qualified (by demonstrating $Q=10$) and (2) when the tritium breeding processes will be qualified by means of the TBMs, i.e. the ability to produce and extract tritium is demonstrated. This means that the TBM is in the critical path for DEMO and delays in the ITER schedule and/or descoping of the TBM objectives represents a fundamental danger to start the DEMO mission.

Indeed, the recent assembly issues encountered during the construction of ITER will necessarily delay the ITER schedule by several years, which in turn will delay having all the RoX elements to achieve the qualification of the TBMs, thus postponing the construction of DEMO. Moreover, and even more important, it is likely that ITER will be forced to reduce its fluence target (0.3 MW yr/m^2 , 1-3 dpa) significantly. Furthermore, it is questionable whether the operation scenario with plasma pulses of several minutes duration can be maintained, which are actually required to reach TBM operational asymptotic thermal regime at the end of the plasma flat top. This implies the risk of not achieving the required temperature in the breeder zone, jeopardizing the tritium release from the ceramic breeder (and multiplier). This could represent a major setback for the TMB mission, which would be descoped in its performance, and therefore, jeopardizing the fundamental objective of demonstrating the tritium breeding processes.

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Report Annex 3.1

Qualitative compilation of testing-qualification requirements for Breeding Blanket

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Date: 23/06/2023

Executive Summary

In this report, the work done by Prof. Abdou et al. in the 80s [1][2] is analysed and readapted to the needs and developments of the European Breeding Blanket development program. Special attention has been devoted to the breeding blanket issues, considering various aspects such as structure, coolant, breeder, and their interactions.

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
BB	<i>Breeding Blanket</i>
BOL	<i>Beginning of Life</i>
DCT	<i>Design Central Team</i>
EOL	<i>End of Life</i>
FW	<i>First-Wall</i>
MOL	<i>Middle of Life</i>
NWL	<i>Neutron Wall Load</i>
VNS	<i>Volumetric Neutron Source</i>

1 Introduction

In this report, the work done by Prof. Abdou et al. in the 80s [1][2] is analysed and readapted to the needs and developments of the European Breeding Blanket development program.

Special attention has been devoted to the breeding blanket (BB) issues, considering various aspects such as structure, coolant, breeder, and their interactions. This focus is detailed in Chapter 2. Moving forward to Chapter 3, the requirements for testing and qualifying the breeding blanket are emphasized. This includes the identification of specific preliminary tests that should be given high priority to effectively address the BB issues outlined in Chapter 2.

2 Breeding blanket Issues

2.1 Structure

2.1.1 Changes in properties and behaviour of materials

The interaction of neutrons with structural materials causes various changes, including the displacement of lattice atoms from their original sites, nuclear transmutation of original elements, and the production of helium and hydrogen. These changes affect many material properties, which depend on several variables like temperature, environment, and material grain size. For fusion reactor designers, the properties related to structural integrity and mechanical stability are the most important, such as tensile strength, ductility, density, fracture toughness, creep, and crack initiation and growth. Accurate knowledge of these properties is essential to design a safe reactor structure since neutron irradiation can alter them. Therefore, **property changes need to be measured as a function of neutron dose under the appropriate operating conditions.**

The potential impacts of not understanding how material properties change with neutron irradiation are critical, including system failure with serious safety implications and failure affecting machine operation, reliability, and maintainability. For instance, an increase in the ductile to brittle transition temperature of ferritic steels, with increasing neutron dose, could lead to brittle fracture of the first wall during lower temperature maintenance periods. Another example is the nuclear transmutation that introduces new elements into the material lattice that may significantly affect the material behavior and properties. Helium, for example, will be produced in significant quantities in fusion neutron spectra and is believed to strongly affect the nucleation and distribution of neutron-induced voids that, then, can compromise the structural integrity (e.g. swelling) and/or act as traps for tritium building up an inventory in the Breeding Blanket. This effect, for instance, represents a combined effect where material damages together with particular phenomena (e.g. tritium diffusion in the lattice) might produce a safety (e.g. build-up inventory) and waste management concern.

Therefore, it is critical to measure material properties and behavior in a neutron environment because virtually all material properties change considerably with increasing neutron irradiation. **The properties and behavior of structural materials are sensitive to virtually all environmental parameters, including temperature, stresses, flux, and fluences, etc. Therefore, the testing program must include and reproduce the range of these parameters expected to exist in the reactor concept being designed.**

To achieve this, the primary indicators are atomic displacements, gas production (mainly hydrogen and helium), and nuclide transmutation. However, the calculation of these indicators is currently limited by uncertainties resulting from inadequate modelling and deficient nuclear data. The potential impact of large uncertainties in radiation damage indicators is significant, as it can make it challenging to calibrate theoretical models and extrapolate experimental irradiation data to different conditions. This can result in significant risks, particularly for structural materials and ceramic breeders.

To address this issue, it is crucial to use representative fusion spectra neutrons in the operating environment to accurately predict radiation damage effects on materials.

2.1.1.1 Deformation and/or breach of components

In a fusion reactor, both primary and secondary stresses can cause component distortion and failure. Primary stresses result from mechanical loads, such as coolant pressure, vacuum loading, and electromagnetic loads, while secondary stresses arise from thermal gradients, swelling, and thermal and irradiation creep. The cyclic nature of a fusion reactor, along with the interaction of these phenomena, results in complex stress histories in first wall/blanket components that are dependent on time, temperature, and neutron fluence. This can lead to large stresses, distortions, or failure. Swelling is the most likely cause of excessive component deformation. Moreover, large deformations may cause local neutron streaming and maintenance issues.

2.1.1.2 Effect of FW heat flux and cycling on fatigue or crack-related failure

These BB components are subjected to a range of extreme conditions, including high temperatures, thermal gradients, coolant pressures, corrosive environments, and radiation. As a result, they will encounter cyclic stress conditions that can cause cumulative damage and decrease their overall lifetime.

The changes in first wall (FW) loading and cycling have the potential to affect the operation and availability of the system. The level of concern for these changes is described as critical, as excessively short component lifetimes could seriously impact the design window. The neutrons, then, are a source of heating and materials damage, and, therefore, the testing is required to determine the effects of changes in wall loading and cycling on stresses and life.

The extreme conditions and cyclic stresses that these components encounter require careful consideration and testing to ensure their long-term reliability and performance.

2.1.1.3 Magnetic forces within the structure (including disruptions)

Metallic structures placed in time-varying magnetic fields are subject to induced electric currents and interactive magnetic forces that can create complex states of stress due to the component geometry. Plasma disruptions result in enhanced radiation and particle flux, rapid changes in magnetic fields, and heating of the first wall, which can cause significant stress in the structure in less than one second. Irradiation embrittlement and changes in the ductile-to-brittle transition temperature can also reduce the first wall's ability to withstand disruptions, leading to premature failure after a limited number of events.

The combination of elevated temperature, complex induced stresses, altered material properties, and intricate geometry leads to a high level of uncertainty. The detailed interaction between plasma and the structure during a plasma disruption remains unclear, which poses a substantial risk to the fusion device.

The overall level of concern for this issue is high as very little is known about the severity of plasma disruptions on the scale anticipated for commercial fusion devices. The operating environment parameters that are critical for assessing the interaction between the plasma and the FW include the magnetic field, rapidly changing magnetic field, temperature (for failure modes), first wall geometry, and stress. Neutron spectrum and fluence may affect failure and component lifetime.

Ferromagnetic alloys exhibit significant magnetically induced primary stresses in their structural components, which makes predicting failure complex and necessitates testing of similarly-shaped modules. Designing to accommodate magnetostatic forces increases the cost and complexity of the design, and when combined with other loads already present, may lead to reduced lifetime.

The impact of neutrons on material properties will change the material's responses to magnetic loading, including deformation and failure modes. Spectrum, fluence, and flux

are important test parameters. Given the complexity of electromagnetic loading in full components, a similarly shaped or full-scale module is necessary to simulate electromagnetic loads accurately. It is also necessary to explore the entire operating temperature range during testing.

2.1.1.4 Premature failure at welds and discontinuities

There are several factors that could contribute to the failure of a first wall/blanket component at a weld. Welds are typically located at areas of stress concentration, which can lead to high stresses at the weld. Moreover, the weld region may behave differently than the parent material in an irradiation environment, due to differential swelling and localized build-up of helium and gas.

If a weld fails, it could have serious safety implications and potentially force a reactor shutdown, as tritium-containing coolant could be released. This issue is generic to all designs using welds in first wall/blanket components and is a major concern since welds are the most likely location for failure.

Testing using neutrons is necessary to produce material damage and determine the effects of differential swelling between the weld and parent material. Testing parameters including neutron flux, spectrum, fluence, temperature, and atmosphere are required to properly resolve this issue.

2.1.1.5 Failure due to hot spots

The presence of local hot spots within the first wall/blanket module can result in failure. These hot spots generate high thermal gradients that cause elevated thermal stresses, which can lead to failure through fatigue or crack growth. The risk of failure is particularly high because of the cyclic nature of a fusion reactor, and the rate of crack propagation is temperature-dependent and is therefore greater at hot spots. Other causes of hot spots include stagnation points in the coolant flow channels, improper location of coolant channels, solid breeder separation from the blanket coolant, and local cracking in the solid breeder.

The potential impact of local failure at a hot spot is significant, as it has the potential to limit the design window for the first wall/blanket and decrease its lifetime. Redesigning the first wall/blanket would be necessary to eliminate hot spots, and system failure would affect system operation and availability. Given the safety implications, hot spots leading to failure have a high level of concern.

To obtain hot spots typical of a specific blanket concept, neutron heating may be required as a source of specific reactions (such as He production) and material damage. Neutron effects contribute to the material properties and are therefore an important environmental condition for reproducing failure modes. The operating environment/parameters necessary for assessing the effects of hot spots on failure include the geometry of the first wall/blanket, expected operating temperature (300-600°C), neutron spectrum, flux, and fluence, heat flux, coolant velocity, and magnetic fields (in liquid metal blankets).

2.1.1.6 Interaction of primary and secondary stresses and deformation

Primary stresses are stresses that arise due to mechanical loadings, such as coolant pressure, vacuum loading, and electromagnetic loads. On the other hand, secondary stresses are stresses that relieve themselves as deformation occurs, with examples being thermal stresses and swelling. In tokamak FWs, secondary stresses in the plastic regime may occur. Deformation can result from both primary and secondary loadings. When designing a first wall/blanket for a fusion reactor, there is a trade-off between stresses and deformation. If deformation is problematic, additional constraints can be added. However, as additional constraint is added, stresses increase, and the life of the component will decrease. Swelling is the most probable source of excessive deformation in a fusion environment.

Swelling can cause stresses in the component by three different means. First, differences in the swelling rate for different parts of the structure, resulting in increases in stresses, similar to thermal gradients producing thermal stresses. Second, overall constraint of the component restricts the ability of swelling stresses to be relieved by expansion. If swelling stresses are high, buckling or crippling of the component can occur. Third, stresses can be imposed on the component by differential swelling rates between different materials.

Understanding the interaction between primary stresses, secondary stresses, and deformation is necessary before designing BB for maximum life, as low BB lifetime is a significant contributor to system costs. The potential safety hazard makes the level of concern high. The effects of irradiation on the behavior of a first wall/blanket module are unknown and require testing.

For testing to resolve this issue, neutrons are required as a source of heating, to produce specific reactions and to produce material damage. The testing parameters required to resolve this issue are flux, neutron spectrum, neutron fluence (>10 dpa), surface heat flux (>0.2 MW/m²), geometry (needed to model constraint of the BB), temperature (300-600°C), and stress (design allowable stress level for the material being tested).

2.1.1.7 Effect of swelling, creep and thermal gradients on stresses concentrations

The point of highest likelihood for a failure to occur in the BB is at a stress concentration, which typically occurs at points of abrupt changes in cross section, discontinuities in the structure, or any existing cracks. The degree of localized stress at a stress concentration is influenced by factors such as the state of stress, stress gradient, temperature, and rate of straining. Swelling of the BB can exacerbate stresses at discontinuities by altering the state of stress and stress gradients, which is dependent on the thermal gradients and constraint on the structure at the stress concentration. While irradiation creep can reduce stresses at the discontinuity, these stresses can reverse during shutdown and cause cracking. Thermal gradients also generate thermal stresses at the stress concentration and differential swelling stresses.

Swelling creep and thermal gradients can significantly increase stress intensities at a discontinuity, leading to failure at the stress concentration, which can greatly impact the operation, availability, and lifetime of a fusion reactor. System cost will also be affected.

The effect of stress concentrations on the BB in a neutron environment is of medium priority. To address this issue, neutron sources are necessary to produce specific reactions and material damage for testing. Testing parameters required to address this issue include neutron spectrum, neutron fluence (>10 dpa), surface heat flux (>0.2 MW/m²), geometry (necessary for modelling the constraint of the BB), temperature (300-600°C), and stress (design allowable stress level for the tested material).

2.1.1.8 Failure due to shutdown residual stresses

During a plasma burn, the first wall of a structure may experience compressive thermal stresses, which are not likely to cause damage or failure. However, the stresses will relax during the burn, resulting in residual tensile stresses during the non-burn portion of the cycle. These cyclic tensile stresses may lead to flaw growth and possible failure of the structure or coolant leakage. Additionally, the residual tensile stresses increase the risk of brittle failure during downtime, where stresses exceed the material's ultimate strength or stress intensities exceed fracture toughness in the region of a crack.

If shutdown residual stresses lead to failures, it can negatively impact operation and increase system cost. The initial stresses at the start of reactor operation are usually relieved by creep mechanisms, and this creep relaxation is responsible for the residual stresses upon shutdown. Later in the reactor's life, swelling will affect the residual stresses. While the phenomena of creep and swelling are understood, accurately predicting initial stresses in a complex geometry is uncertain.

To resolve this issue, testing is required in an operating environment with specific reactions and material damage caused by neutrons. **Testing parameters required to address this issue include neutron spectrum, neutron fluence (>10 dpa), surface heat flux (>0.2 MW/m²), geometry (necessary for modelling the constraint of the BB), temperature (300-600°C), and stress (design allowable stress level for the tested material).**

2.1.1.9 Interaction between surface effects and first wall failures

The surface of the FW in a fusion reactor is vulnerable to various forms of damage such as sputtering of atoms, blistering caused by implantation, and transmutations resulting from exposure to charged particles, neutrons, neutral atoms, and electromagnetic radiation. If the FW is eroded excessively, it can lead to increased primary stresses, potentially leading to rupture, and affecting the operation and availability of the fusion reactor. This damage can increase the frequency of replacement of the BB, reducing component lifetime, and increasing system cost. Surface effects are a generic concern for all BB concepts.

Neutrons are only required for potential material damage, and testing parameters required to resolve this issue include plasma interactions, surface heat flux (>0.2 MW/m²), operating time, temperature (300-600°C), stress level in the FW, magnetic field, and neutron fluence.

2.1.1.10 Self-welding of similar and dissimilar metals

Excessive deformation of components may cause them to come in contact and self-weld. Additionally, dissimilar metals may also weld together due to other phenomena (e.g. corrosion). If such self-welding occurs, removing the welded components for maintenance or replacement will be difficult or even impossible, impacting the availability and operation of a fusion reactor. The self-welding can result in reduced reactor availability, affecting scheduled downtime and increasing system costs.

Self-welding is a low concern overall, but if excessive swelling forces components to touch and weld together, it can adversely affect reactor availability and increase system costs.

Neutrons are required to resolve this issue as they are a source of heating and can produce specific reactions, which can cause material damage and affect a given material's response. Testing parameters required to address this issue include flux, neutron spectra, neutron fluence, operating temperature, stress level, and component geometry.

2.1.2 Tritium permeation through the structure

2.1.2.1 Effectiveness of tritium permeation barriers

Barriers of various types may be employed at critical locations to minimize tritium permeation, such as surface coatings in the FW, coolant tubes, BB breeder units, etc. However, the effectiveness of these barriers is uncertain.

If the tritium permeation barriers fail to function as intended, it can result in increased tritium permeation into primary/secondary coolant or tritium leakage to the reactor room, leading to serious safety implications or requiring additional tritium processing systems for coolant or room air.

This issue is common to all blanket designs, but the importance of the issue varies with design specificity.

Due to the potential for unacceptable safety consequences, the level of concern for this issue is critical.

Radiation damage affects the effectiveness of the barriers, and the structural integrity of the composite material, including barriers, must be tested under neutron and gamma irradiation that can produce significant changes in the barrier structure (e.g. amorphous → grains, and vice-versa). Parameters that influence tritium permeation should also be considered (chemical compatibility between material barriers and fluids, operating temperature, thermal cycling, etc.).

2.1.2.2 Effect of radiation on tritium permeation

Radiation has been observed to impact the movement and trapping of tritium in non-metal materials like solid breeding materials and oxide coatings on metal structures. Neutrons can also affect tritium permeation and trapping in metal structures. Some experiments suggest that gamma-ray irradiation may even enhance tritium permeation in metals.

The potential impacts of this are significant. If radiation increases the trapping of tritium, the tritium inventory could become too large and lead to economic penalties. Conversely, if radiation enhances tritium permeation into the coolant or reactor room air, it will pose a safety concern.

This issue is generic to all designs. The level of concern is considered high because the damage from neutrons is particularly important in this regard, as well as stress may also affect crack growth, which could further impact tritium release.

2.1.3 Structural activation product inventory and volatility

DEMO will be exposed to a significant amount of 14 MeV neutrons, which will activate the structures near the plasma. Therefore, it is important to determine the isotope inventory that will be produced for various reasons, such as maintenance exposure, release during corrosion and sputtering, release during accidents, and waste management/decommissioning. Experiments are necessary to verify the neutron calculations of blanket materials. The key uncertainties in this process include the production cross sections of long-lived isotopes and the actual levels of impurities in engineered materials, which correspond to their activities. If there are incorrect predictions of very long-lived isotopes, it could lead to inaccurate assessment of waste management and decommissioning needs and costs. Similarly, if there are incorrect predictions of activation products resulting from impurities, it could lead to wrong assessment of several maintenance and safety issues and the corresponding costs.

The level of concern is low as uncertainties associated with near-term materials in DEMO are relatively low. The operating environment requires neutrons with sufficient fluence and the right energy to measure cross sections for long-lived isotope production. Neutrons with sufficient fluence are also necessary for activation analysis of engineered materials to determine actual impurity levels and the corresponding produced isotopes. The operating environment parameters include the spectrum, fluence, and impurities.

2.2 Metal liquid breeder-multiplier

The pressure drop caused by MHD in liquid metal BB can be significant enough to exceed the structural materials' strength at the inlet, which may result in primary stresses. To reduce the pressure drop, fluid velocity can be reduced, but this may increase the temperatures in the blanket. Therefore, the MHD pressure drop is closely related to the thermal hydraulic and structural behavior of the blanket. The main source of uncertainty in the total MHD pressure drop value arises from geometric complexities, including end effects, non-uniformities along the flow path, channel bends, and others. Temperature-related effects may also be important due to the temperature dependence of properties and the existence of thermoelectric MHD effects. Time-dependent changes in electrical properties due to corrosion and irradiation materials damage may also play a role.

The neutron heating may be required since temperatures affect the MHD pressure drop. Changes in material properties due to neutron irradiation have not been estimated, but they could be significant, particularly if the electrical properties at the fluid/structure interface were altered.

The exact geometry is critical, and other important test conditions include magnetic field strength, fluid velocity, and temperature. Certain dimensionless parameters must also be considered.

2.2.1 MHD pressure drop and pressure stresses

In blanket designs, the coolant flows through multiple parallel paths. If the flow is not evenly distributed among the channels, the difference between the highest and average temperatures in the blanket increases. In solid breeder blankets, nonuniform flow often results from geometric nonuniformity due to the large number of channels and small dimensions. On the other hand, in liquid metal blankets, flow distribution of the liquid breeder, for instance, might be dominated by magnetic field effects.

Neutrons are not needed for beginning-of-life flow distribution problems, while solid breeder flow sensitivity to dimensional changes requires neutrons. Geometry is critical for all blanket types, and the liquid metal velocity is important. Magnetic field is an essential parameter for liquid metal blankets.

2.2.2 Geometric effects on flow distribution

The solid breeder blanket concepts that serve as reference designs are cooled using either H₂O or He, but both coolants are prone to flow instabilities under the employed conditions. In the case of helium, the flow is limited to multiple small parallel channels at high speed, which can result in flow-induced vibration depending on the specific design. For water, many parallel tubes are utilized, and in addition to the problem of flow-induced vibration, there is the possibility of flow oscillations between channels, especially when a two-phase coolant exists, such as in a channel that is hotter than average. These instabilities can cause premature structural failure due to fatigue caused by mechanical stress or fretting resulting from vibration, or cyclic thermal stresses. Furthermore, coolant flow oscillations can impact temperature-dependent phenomena, such as hot spots.

The potential impact of this issue is significant, as it can lead to systematic premature failure of components near or in the cooling system, resulting in decreased availability, increased maintenance cost, and reduced system performance if coolant conditions are adjusted in an attempt to decrease instability severity. This issue is primarily generic to H₂O and He coolants.

The level of concern for this issue is high because, as seen in other engineering area (e.g. steam generator design), the flow instability can be expected in early designs, and the consequences are likely to occur unless addressed. Tests to address this issue must simulate various parameters such as local heating rates, surface heat loads, geometry, temperature, velocity, mechanical stress, and coolant pressure.

2.2.3 Stability/kinetics of tritium oxidation in the coolant

It is necessary to understand the kinetics of reactions that modify the chemical form of tritium released from the breeders while it resides in the purge gas or coolant in the blanket. If tritiated water is converted into elemental form, it can cause an increase in tritium permeation into the steam generator or containment, which can lead to potential safety hazards. In such cases, safety measures like tritium permeation barriers, coolant processing, or emergency gas clean-up systems need to be provided, which may add an economic penalty. The problem is most severe in blanket systems that use He as the purge gas or coolant.

The operating environment parameters like temperature, chemical composition, velocity of the purge gas or coolant, and gamma radiation are crucial in this regard. Neutrons are not required for the operating environment.

2.2.4 Helium bubble formation leading to hot spots

Liquid metal breeders exposed to a neutron flux will produce both tritium and helium, but the concentration of these gases is expected to be very low under normal conditions. While tritium can be removed from the liquid metal, there are limited methods for separating helium, which can concentrate into bubbles in areas such as stagnated coolant regions or blocked channels. These gas pockets can create local hot spots and reduce surface heat transfer, potentially leading

to a high-temperature related failure mode that could reduce the lifetime of the blanket. This issue is common to liquid metal blankets, but the overall level of concern is low since helium bubbles are not typically considered a factor in blanket design.

The operating environment for studying helium bubble formation includes neutron flux or externally supplying helium to the blanket, while the most important parameters are geometry and flow conditions.

2.2.5 Activation products in PbLi

Neutron irradiation of PbLi leads to a gradual alteration of its composition over time due to transmutation reactions that result in the formation of various species. The activation products that arise from these reactions are the primary sources of radiation exposure for workers and the environment, and among these products, T, ^{210}Po , and ^{203}Hg are considered the most hazardous. Since the activation products are relatively volatile, they tend to evaporate from the hot liquid PbLi and for this reason can become of particular concern.

To address this issue, it is crucial to use representative fusion neutron flux and spectra in the operating environment to accurately predict activation product in liquid metal.

2.3 Breeder and purge

2.3.1 Tritium recovery and inventory in solid breeder materials

In the recovery of tritium from solid breeders, the tritium is extracted from the solid phase where it is generated. This process involves a steady-state or equilibrium tritium concentration, which includes tritium dissolved, chemically bound, and physically trapped in the solid. There is uncertainty in the thermodynamics of these systems. To achieve reasonable dissolved tritium inventories, it is believed that the appropriate phases and a tritiated vapor pressure below 100 Pa should be maintained. However, the picture is complicated by purge stream chemistry and radiation. Radiation transmutes lithium into tritium, leaving excess oxygen or metal oxides. With sufficient burnup or high local tritium production rates, the local chemistry may be sharply changed or pushed from equilibrium. Physical trapping in radiation-induced bubbles, vacancies or dislocations is also possible, but not yet predictable. The diffusion of tritium may occur through several mechanisms, depending on local conditions such as temperature and vacancy concentration. Concerns over grain growth rates at high temperatures and diffusion rates at low temperatures have contributed to assumed operating limits for the solid breeder temperature (e.g. 500-930°C for the Orthosilicate).

Temperature is the most important parameter since the processes are thermally-activated. Indeed, the temperature is the single most important parameter since it will vary by up to 600 °C (i.e. ΔT) across the breeder. Strong variations in inventories, recovery rates, and mechanisms can be expected. Fluence, flux, and spectrum provide the source terms for tritium, chemistry changes, and micro- or macro-structure changes. Impurities in the solid phase may interfere with classic tritium diffusivity and solubility

Tritium diffuses to the surface of solid grains, where it can desorb and enter the gas phase to be carried away in the purge stream. However, there may be some movement along the surface, especially along grain boundaries with little to no open porosity. This surface movement is believed to be faster than diffusion time over comparable distances, although surface kinetics related to recombination, desorption, and absorption may also play a role. The overall solubility of tritium is ideally related to its vapor pressure over the surface, but surface impurities may either help or hinder the process.

Surface effects may impact the tritium solubility inventory or the rate of diffused tritium desorption, potentially increasing or decreasing the anticipated inventory and recovery time. Surface migration and desorption are common steps in all solid breeder designs, and data uncertainties exist for all candidate compounds.

An increased inventory of tritium is a major safety concern because of enhanced permeation during operation and hazard during accidents. If burnup is a limit, more frequent blanket replacement may be required. These concerns hold for all solid breeder compounds.

The present lack of data (particularly under irradiation) and the expected dominance of these processes in controlling tritium recovery from solid breeders make this a critical issue.

Neutrons primarily serve as a source of heating, determining temperature profiles and kinetics. Both solubility and diffusion are exponentially dependent on temperature. They produce also tritium from lithium, giving both the source term and the transmutation effect. Furthermore, they produce displacement damage that affects tritium diffusion and physical trapping. Surface chemistry may also be affected by neutron-induced transmutation, damage, or helium production, which can change surface structure or porosity with accumulating helium bubbles. Spectrum effects may be important in the dpa/T rate.

Moreover, at the beginning-of-life, it may be possible to analyse tritium transport, but when there are large temperature gradients, cracking, grain growth, creep, sintering, and tritium transport, the complexity is expected to prevent a realistic analytical treatment. These phenomena could also divert or interrupt the narrow purge channels and cause preferential purge flow, resulting in variations in purge effectiveness and tritiated vapor pressure both across the blanket and with time/fluence. Communication between breeder regions at different conditions (temperature, burnup) through the purge flow may also be important. The interaction of purge gas with structural components may be important in establishing the thermodynamic environment.

2.3.2 Liquid breeder tritium extraction

To minimize tritium inventory and permeation, it is necessary to recover tritium bred in the BB at acceptable levels of concentration and overpressure. Extracting tritium from liquid metals is influenced by the basic tritium diffusivity. Additionally, the extraction process may enhance loop corrosion. Poor tritium extraction will lead to high tritium partial pressure and inventory in the liquid breeder, and substantially enhance permeation. Tritium extraction is a concern for all liquid breeders.

Tritium extraction from lithium needs a large-scale engineering demonstration. The primary variables affecting tritium extraction are tritium concentration and impurity levels in the breeder. Temperature and pressure are also significant if the extractor has to operate at breeder conditions.

2.3.3 Temperature limits and variability in solid breeder material

2.3.3.1 Temperature limits

The upper and lower temperature limits are crucial for determining the operating range of a solid breeder blanket, which is designed to perform its primary functions such as tritium production and recovery, heat generation and removal, while ensuring adequate blanket lifetime. These limits reflect various temperature limiting factors, including Q_2 transport, tritium recovery, and mechanical interaction issues. Failure to meet the temperature limits can have significant consequences.

Due to the low thermal conductivity of solid breeder materials and high heat generation rates near the first wall, it is necessary to optimize blanket cooling components such as coolant (H_2O or He) and structure. However, increasing the fraction of coolant components within the blanket can reduce the fraction of solid breeder, potentially decreasing the overall tritium breeding ratio (TBR). Changes in heat transfer characteristics may result in increased temperature gradients within the blanket.

This issue is generic to solid breeder blankets, although different temperature limiting issues may apply to different solid breeder materials and the same solid breeder materials

with different micro-structures. Neutrons are the heating source that generates temperature gradients within the solid breeder material, and the temperature limits must be bounded by these gradients, which dictate either more closely spaced coolant channels or lower heat generation rates. Specific solid breeder materials are thought to have specific temperature limits, and neutron fluence effects influence temperature limits through the operating issues that halt the temperatures.

2.3.3.2 Thermal conductivity changes under irradiation

The thermal conductivity of solid breeder materials is a crucial factor that determines the operating temperature range of BBs. Changes in thermal conductivity can affect blanket performance and lead to reduced tritium recovery, increased Q₂ transport, and mechanical interaction, ultimately leading to decreased lifetime. This issue is generic to most solid breeder designs, and solid breeder thermal conductivities, including pebble bed effective thermal conductivities, need to be determined with and without irradiation effects. Most of the data currently available and used for the design of the solid BB rely on non irradiated pebble bed thermal conductivity.

The potential impacts of changes in thermal conductivity are high, and it is of significant concern due to its potential impact on temperature variability, physical integrity, tritium inventory and recovery, and lifetime. Neutron damage and defect production in the solid breeder materials can interrupt the conductance process within the lattice, leading to degradation of thermal conductivity.

Neutron wall loading and temperature are expected to be the dominant factors affecting thermal conductivity damages. Changes in thermal conductivity can begin at low fluence levels and may saturate up to high fluence (>10 dpa). In pebble beds, thermal conductivity can be significantly influenced by gas pressure.

2.3.3.3 Effect of cracking

The thermal and swelling gradients, stresses resulting from mechanical interactions, and grain boundary separation can cause macro and microcracking in solid breeder materials. This cracking can significantly impact the thermal and mechanical performance and lifetime of the blanket, especially for sintered solid breeder materials. The cracking affects the blanket's thermal performance by reducing heat transfer, particularly when normal to the heat flow direction. However, changes due to cracking are unpredictable because brittle fracture and cracked fragment relocation processes are stochastic in nature. This issue is generic to most solid breeder blanket concepts. The concern for this issue is high due to its potential impact on the blanket's performance and lifetime.

Neutron heating is the driving force for thermal stress cracking, and helium production generates swelling-induced cracking. The operating environment, including neutron wall load, geometry, temperature, stresses caused by temperature gradients, and fluence levels, also plays a crucial role in solid breeder cracking.

2.3.4 Breeder behaviour at high burn-up/high dpa

The use of blankets at high temperatures can potentially result in the permeation of tritium into the blanket coolant and subsequently through the primary system into the building area or secondary system. The extent of permeation loss is highly dependent on the chemical form of the tritium. If the tritium can be generated or converted into the tritiated water form, the permeation losses can likely be reduced to acceptable levels.

The permeation of tritium into the coolant is a significant safety concern. To reduce tritium transfer, a coolant processing system can be implemented, but this comes with an economic penalty.

Neutrons interact with solid breeders to produce tritium, and the temperature and chemical composition of purge gas, particularly hydrogen and oxygen content, can affect the tritium release form. Radiolytic decomposition of the tritiated water and the solid breeder's geometry may also play an important role.

2.4 Coolant/structure interactions

2.4.1 Mechanical and materials interactions

2.4.1.1 Corrosion

Mass transport is expected to occur in coolant and helium purge systems due to mechanisms such as corrosion and neutron sputtering. This corrosion products becomes activated and can redeposit in other areas, causing loss of integrity in structural materials due to wall thinning as well as system plugging because of localized deposition. In solid breeder blankets, corrosion particles may interact with the field and preferentially accumulate in particular regions of the blanket, while in liquid metal blankets, the magnetic field causes a reduction in the mass transfer boundary layer thickness, resulting in enhanced deposition or recession near flow perturbations.

The potential impact of mass transport includes availability implications, reduced performance and lifetime, and safety implications due to the transport of radioactive elements. Mass transport severity is very design-dependent and a primary factor in choosing desirable material combinations for blankets.

Due to the potential impact and extent to which mass transport determines blanket design and choice, it is a critical testing issue. The operating environment for mass transport depends on factors such as neutron fluence, geometry, temperature, velocity, solubilities, and diffusion coefficients. The magnetic field may be important for both types of blankets, but especially for liquid metal ones. Hydrogen isotopes may substantially change the corrosion mechanism, and testing may be needed to understand their effects. Neutrons are required for direct sputtering of materials and for the possibility of corrosion rate dependence on irradiation for materials damage. Bulk heating affects temperature profiles, which in turn affect corrosion rates.

2.4.1.2 Mechanical wear and fatigue from flow-induced vibrations

Fluid flow around or through a structure can cause vibrations in the structure, which are primarily influenced by fluid velocity, flow path, density, and the natural vibration frequencies of the structure. These vibrations can lead to wear, fretting, and fatigue failure of the structure.

Fatigue failure due to vibrations can occur in any structure with flowing fluids. Addressing this issue requires detailed dynamic structural analysis and potentially full-scale flow testing. The potential impact of mechanical wear and fatigue due to flow-induced vibrations on system performance and cost is significant. This issue is generic to all BB concepts and reactor types that have flowing fluids. Overall, the concern level for mechanical wear and fatigue due to flow-induced vibrations is medium, as this is a common problem that has been addressed in various engineering areas.

Neutrons have no effect on this issue. Testing parameters required to resolve this issue include the geometry of the first wall/blanket module, expected operating temperature, stress level, and coolant velocity.

2.4.1.3 Failure of coolant wall due to stress corrosion cracking

Stress corrosion cracking is a type of failure that occurs when a material is exposed to both stress and a corrosive substance. The material is typically resistant to the corrosive element in the absence of stress, and the response to stress alone would be benign without the corrosive environment. However, the combination of stress and corrosion significantly increases crack propagation, reduces ductility, and can lead to catastrophic failure.

The nuclear reactor industry, for instance, has observed stress corrosion cracking of austenitic stainless steel in pressurized hot water for many years. This phenomenon is important to consider in the analysis of fusion reactor designs, as it is difficult to design for this type of failure. Stress corrosion cracking is sensitive to even slight differences in microstructure and chemistry, which can result from variations in heats of material or differences in welds. Local compositional and microstructural changes caused by exposure to the fusion environment can cause unpredictability. The potential impact of unexpected stress corrosion cracking on the coolant wall in fusion reactor designs is system failure, with serious implications for safety, operation, and availability. This failure can introduce tritium into the coolant and the environment, which is undesirable. The loss of coolant and possible volatile interaction between the coolant and hot breeder make this a serious issue. While stress corrosion cracking is generic to water-cooled systems, its likelihood and severity are design-specific.

In testing, neutrons are necessary to produce displacement damage that enhances creep, solute redistribution, and irradiation hardening and softening. Neutrons are also required to study the effects of helium bubbles, dissolved hydrogen, and other species produced via high-energy neutron reactions. Therefore, the neutron spectrum and fluence are important parameters.

2.4.1.4 Failure of coolant wall due to liquid-metal embrittlement

When a material is vulnerable to embrittlement caused by liquid metals, it may experience rapid crack propagation, even at low stresses, and in severe cases, can spontaneously fracture along grain boundaries, disintegrating into fine particles without any applied stress. Liquid metal embrittlement is highly sensitive to temperature and strain rate, and therefore, it is essential to study it under appropriate conditions. Local chemistry variations such as those present in heat-to-heat variation, welds, and produced by neutron irradiation could unexpectedly induce this phenomenon.

Failure of channel/tube due to liquid metal enhanced cracking could result in liquid metal/coolant interaction (i.e. PbLi/water interaction) that would cause exothermal reactions and the immediate reactor shutdown with the substitution of the BB segment. Such occurrences would lead to system failure, with significant implications for operation, availability, or, at the very least, reduced component lifetime.

Although this issue is generic to all liquid metal designs, the probability and severity of consequences of failure due to liquid metal embrittlement are relatively low. The testing requires neutrons for specific reactions and displacement damage. Hence, the neutron spectrum and flux are critical experimental parameters.

2.4.2 Thermal interactions

2.4.2.1 MHD effects on first wall cooling and hot spots

The thermal efficiency of the power conversion system in the blanket is mainly influenced by the average temperature of the coolant at the blanket exit. However, failure modes of the blanket are determined by local temperatures within the structure or at the coolant/structure interface. The maximum temperature within the blanket is often the design limit due to corrosion, thermal stresses, or materials properties under irradiation. Liquid metal blankets have further limitations due to minimum fluid temperatures required to avoid freezing and maximum flow rates due to MHD pressure drop.

Magnetic field effects are the major source of uncertainty for liquid metal blankets, and MHD velocity profiles are highly sensitive to geometric and magnetic field perturbations. This can lead to local or widespread areas of altered heat transfer due to very thin boundary layers, shear layers, and flow stagnation points. The presence of a strong magnetic field is also known to suppress turbulence, which can hinder good heat transfer.

Issues related to hot spots and first wall cooling might be associated with the MHD pressure drop and have a direct impact on the design window. The thermal cycle efficiency requires high average temperatures, and performance is degraded with large peak-to-average temperatures. Severe miscalculation of temperature peaking could result in reduced lifetime or catastrophic failure.

The issue of hot spots is generic, but the severity of the problem and associated uncertainties are design-dependent. The highest level of concern exists for liquid metal blankets in which MHD effects are active.

Due to its critical impact on the design window and potential for system failures with serious safety implications, the level of concern is critical.

Neutron bulk heating or its equivalent is required since volumetric heating alters the temperature distribution within the coolant and structure. Neutron materials damage is also required since thermophysical properties change under irradiation. Geometry and magnetic field are critical parameters due to the importance of MHD effects. Surface heating, bulk heating, and temperatures are also necessary to study the thermal hydraulic behavior and its consequences.

2.4.2.2 Response to cooling system transients

This passage discusses the different types of cooling transients that a cooling system could experience, including loss of cooling, flow blockage, loss of coolant flow, and loss of site power. It highlights the importance of accurately predicting system response to such transients to avoid over-design or under-design with potential for serious fault conditions.

The potential impact of inaccurate prediction is stated to be either over-design with associated costs or under-design with potential for serious fault conditions. The design specificity is stated to be generic, as these types of cooling transients could apply to any cooling system.

For helium and water coolants, the level of concern is low, as these fluids are far better understood. The key unknowns for these fluids are more associated with the particular fusion blanket geometry than with uncertainties concerning the fluids themselves.

The operating environment for parameters includes steady and changing magnetic fields for liquid metal and salt cases, as well as transient tests with appropriate time duration, heat fluxes, geometry, temperature, flow velocities, pressures, and stresses for all fluids. Neutrons are not needed for testing.

2.4.2.3 Flow sensitivity to dimensional changes

In case of BB components with many small parallel coolant channels (e.g. FW), altered coolant flow distribution and potential blockage of passages, leading to local overheating and reduced component lifetime, can be envisaged. This issue can be initiated by common mechanisms such as thermal expansion, swelling, fracturing, and manufacturing tolerances, changes in passage dimensions.

The potential impact of this issue is an increased random failure rate of BB components, resulting in reduced component lifetime. This issue is generic to H₂O and He-cooled blanket concepts, and the level of concern is medium, as it is rather unlikely that widespread failure will occur.

Tests to address this issue will require simulation of local heating rates, surface heat loads, geometry, temperature, velocity, mechanical stress, and coolant pressure. Neutrons might be required for both heating and damage in order to develop realistic dimensional changes.

2.5 Solid breeder/multiplier/structure interactions

2.5.1 Solid breeder mechanical and materials interactions

The varying thermal expansion, creep, and swelling behaviors of the solid breeder material, neutron multiplier, and metal structure in a blanket module can cause mechanical interactions that may result in degraded performance, reduced lifetime, or unsafe operation. These interactions

are influenced by the differences in material properties and can also be affected by the expected restructuring of the breeder material.

2.5.1.1 Clad corrosion from breeder burn-up products

Due to the conversion of lithium into tritium, the chemical composition of the solid breeder material can change. This change in the chemical environment may affect the compatibility between the breeder and the structure.

This change can lead to the formation of highly corrosive compounds, which can negatively impact operating temperatures and ultimately limit the performance and lifetime of the blanket. Additionally, changes in the stoichiometry of ternary ceramics can lead to the formation of new phases, resulting in material property changes such as melting points and compatibility issues.

Neutrons play a significant role in determining the burnout of lithium and tritium production, as well as controlling heat generation and temperatures at the breeder/structure interface. Other factors such as geometry, spectrum, and any other contributors to local chemistry (e.g. H₂ added to purge) may also be significant.

2.5.1.2 Strain accommodation by creep and plastic flow

The mechanical strains resulting from mismatches in materials can be addressed through various means, such as accommodation in the solid breeder material itself, or by utilizing more compliant structural components. While strain accommodation can extend the lifetime limits associated with mechanical failure, it may also impair tritium recovery and fuel supply. Gaps and voids can decrease the overall breeding ratio of a blanket. Strain accommodation is a generic concern for all solid breeder blankets, but specific in character and extent to each design.

The neutrons in the operating environment provide the heating that generates the thermal environment in the blanket, while creep in solid breeders may be influenced by helium build-up and damage. The parameters of temperature, scaled geometric configurations, and fluences are important factors in addressing strain accommodation, with specific considerations for each type of strain. Thermal cycling at low fluences and temperature variability effects are initially important for thermal expansion mismatch strains, with swelling contributing at higher fluences.

2.5.1.3 Swelling driving force

The solid breeder BB concepts require direct contact between the solid breeder materials and structural materials to efficiently transfer the heat generated in the pebble bed. However, this can lead to structural component failures that compromise tritium purge gas boundaries, which can have a detrimental effect on plasma operation and fuel supply. Furthermore, deformation of structural components can negatively impact thermal hydraulic performance and contribute to a reduced blanket life. The swelling of the breeder material can modify this contact producing localised forces on the structure material or gaps with the consequent reduction of the heat transfer capabilities.

Swelling in solid breeder is caused by the helium produced by neutrons. Damage to the lattice is also thought to affect swelling.

Regarding operating environment parameters, neutron fluence and neutron capture cross-section are of interest in swelling. Low fluence testing is of limited value, and the geometric configuration directly impacts the magnitude of strains. Temperature also appears to have a direct influence on swelling.

2.5.1.4 Stress concentrations at cracks and discontinuities

Both thermal expansion and swelling mismatch strains can lead to the deformation of the structural components surrounding the solid breeder in the blanket, and this deformation need not be homogeneous. As a result, failure strains may occur earlier than expected from homogeneous

strains. Although configurational stress concentration factors can possibly be addressed through design changes, operational factors such as solid breeder cracking are not as easily controlled. Stress concentration factors can accentuate the potential impacts of thermal expansion and swelling-induced mechanical interaction, further reducing the lifetime of the blanket. Stress concentrations are not only dependent on the selection of solid breeder materials but also on the exact configuration of both the solid breeder and structural components. Therefore, a high level of concern has been selected, as strain concentration effects may play a critical role in the final assessment of design viability for a specific design.

Regarding the operating environment, neutrons have essentially no effect on stress concentration effects themselves, but without heating and swelling, it may be impossible to evaluate them. The geometry associated with a specific design is expected to control stress concentration, and cracking in the solid breeder material can cause stress concentration associated with thermal cycling, temperature gradients, and swelling.

2.5.1.5 Thermal expansion driving force

Thermal expansion of solid breeder materials is expected to exceed that of the surrounding structural materials, potentially causing mechanical interaction. Although the gross thermal expansion can be calculated, the effects of cracking, setting, and porosity on the actual expansion are not well understood.

The potential impact of thermal expansion includes structural component failures that compromise tritium purge gas boundaries. This, in turn, can affect reactor operation, while the deformation of structural components can degrade thermal hydraulic performance.

The thermal expansion mechanical interaction might be of concern for the packed pebble beds that are particularly sensitive.

Neutrons provide the internal heating that generates temperature gradients causing thermal expansion. Helium production and damage are important because they affect temperature variability. Two operating parameters determine the temperature distributions within the blanket: heat generation and geometry (size). Since thermal cycling can reconfigure strains, it is of importance. The neutron loading and spectrum determine, in part, the heat generation distribution throughout the solid breeder.

2.5.2 Neutron multiplier mechanical interactions

2.5.2.1 Beryllium swelling (swelling driving force in beryllium)

Many solid breeder blankets rely on beryllium or beryllide as a neutron multiplier to increase the tritium breeding ratio due to its high $(n,2n)$ cross section. However, the reaction $\text{Be}(n,2n)2\text{He}$ produces helium in beryllium, leading to swelling of over 10% in the bulk material at high temperatures and moderate fluences ($5 \text{ MW}\cdot\text{yr}/\text{m}^2$). When the volume of swelling reaches 30%, interconnected helium bubbles can form along grain boundaries, causing the metal to become brittle.

This swelling can induce mechanical interaction strains in neighbouring components, potentially causing structural failure and necessitating blanket replacement. Swelling in beryllium is a concern for all blankets with beryllium multipliers, as the viability of many solid breeder designs relies on the use of beryllium.

Neutrons produce the damage and helium responsible for swelling in beryllium. In addition, neutrons are the source of heat that establishes the temperature profiles within the neutron multiplier section. The two most important parameters that influence swelling in beryllium are neutron fluence ($> 5 \text{ MW}\cdot\text{yr}/\text{m}^2$) and temperature (400 to 600°C). Neutron energy spectrum is also important in establishing helium production and dpa rates.

2.5.2.2 Strain accommodation by creep in beryllium

As swelling continues over time, mechanical interaction strain and internal stresses from helium-induced swelling are expected to increase, but radiation-induced creep can relieve these stresses and strains through plastic deformation.

The operating environment parameters such as neutron wall loading, spectrum, temperature, and geometric configuration provide the environment for creep over the time the blanket is in operation. Prestress in the beryllium provides an initial driving force for creep.

2.5.3 Thermal interactions

2.5.3.1 Breeder- and multiplier-structure interface heat transfer

Determining the suitable operating temperature range for solid breeder materials in all solid breeder blanket concepts heavily relies on the solid breeder/structure interface. The acceptable temperature window restricts the design of these concepts, and hence, predictable thermal properties of the interface are crucial. Current understanding and analytical tools are sufficient to predict these properties if the gap geometry and conditions are known. However, uncertainties in manufacturing tolerances, purge gas pressure and composition, and gap geometry changes cause significant uncertainty in the gap thermal properties. Changes in the gap geometry due to differential thermal expansion, breeder rearrangement, and time-dependent material changes such as swelling, creep, and mass transport contribute most to this uncertainty. The unpredictability of the interface heat transfer coefficient over the long term is the primary issue, and it may jeopardise the BB design.

This issue represents a feasibility issue for a large class of blankets and will also be a serious operational concern, and the consequences of not addressing it can be severe.

In addressing this issue, neutrons will be required in some tests to develop the material damage that will produce changes in the interface geometry, and they may also be useful in developing desired temperature profiles in tests. The local power density, chemical environment, geometry, temperature profiles, purge flow velocity, mechanical stress/restraint, and purge pressure are necessary environmental aspects in tests addressing this issue. A low neutron fluence ($< 1 \text{ MW-yr/m}^2$) is adequate to evaluate the beginning-of-life gap conductance, but goal fluence levels ($>10 \text{ MW-yr/m}^2$) are required to verify lifetime capabilities.

2.6 General blanket issues

2.6.1 D-T fuel self-sufficiency

2.6.1.1 Uncertainties in achievable breeding ratio

To achieve fuel self-sufficiency in fusion devices that operate with a DT cycle, the achievable tritium breeding ratio (TBRa) must be equal to or greater than the required breeding ratio (TBRr), which depends on the desired doubling time and various plasma and reactor parameters, including the tritium fractional burnup, tritium inventories, and tritium processing systems. However, there are significant uncertainties associated with these parameters, making it difficult to estimate the achievable breeding ratio accurately. This uncertainty stems from system definition uncertainties related to technology choices and the degree of details available for blanket and reactor design, as well as prediction uncertainties associated with neutronics geometrical modelling, basic nuclear data, data processing, and calculational methods.

The accurate prediction of the required breeding ratio requires experimental data from the operation of a complete fuel cycle system, which includes nearly all components of the fusion device, particularly plasma, plasma exhaust system, blanket, and tritium processing systems.

Furthermore, firm confirmation of attaining fuel self-sufficiency conditions may not be possible prior to a full-scale demonstration plant, as the tritium production profiles in an individual blanket module can be vastly different from the corresponding values in a full-coverage blanket. Therefore, a fusion neutron spectrum is necessary for verifying the neutronics performance, and a 14 MeV neutron source with sufficient intensity is considered an indispensable means of verification of neutronics methods and data.

2.6.1.2 Uncertainties in required breeding ratio

During the operational lifespan of a solid breeder blanket, it is possible for localized regions, especially those near neutron multipliers, to experience a significant burnout of lithium isotopes. The extent of this burnout is dependent on the desired lifetime goals and the characteristics of the blanket. The loss of lithium in these regions causes a lower local neutron capture rate, which leads to lower tritium and heat generation rates. However, blanket calculations have shown that this burnout does not impact the overall tritium breeding ratio. Instead, tritium breeding shifts from high burnup regions to areas where lithium remains. This shift can be a design limitation since blanket configurations must accommodate large variations in heat generation rates to maintain solid breeder temperatures. Additionally, there may be reduced tritium breeding since neutrons will have to penetrate further into the blanket to find lithium.

In particular, due to the presence of neutron multipliers, the burnout effects might be worse because lower energy neutrons emitted from the neutron multiplier are more prone to capture because of higher cross-section for that energy, leading to high burnup near the multiplier.

Neutrons parameters, such as the spectrum, the geometry of the neutron multiplier and solid breeder are important in determining burnout effects.

2.6.2 Tritium permeation

2.6.2.1 Permeation from breeder to blanket coolant

The breeder material may release tritium into the coolant at heat transfer surfaces where thin walls separate the two. Tritium can diffuse through structural components at a rate determined by surface kinetics, tritium pressure, and permeability. Corrosion/chemistry at the interfaces may either inhibit or enhance permeability. Engineered barriers to reduce permeation may be degraded by local chemistry or cracking. Cracking of the barriers alone or through the entire clad strongly affects permeation. Uncertainties include surface kinetics, hydrogen diffusivities, and overall tritium vapor pressure and species.

If tritium permeates into the coolant, it may be difficult to prevent further tritium transfer outside of the primary coolant, which is a substantial safety penalty. Alternatively, a major tritium permeation problem would require replacing the faulty blanket. To prevent this, high coolant flow rates or high tritium extraction efficiency is required in the coolant.

Permeation is a major safety concern for all breeder designs due to the relative ease of hydrogen permeation, realistic tritium pressures, and the thin breeder/coolant interfaces needed for thermal efficiency.

Neutron damage in the clad material and barriers may change the diffusion characteristics. Neutrons are the source of tritium, and influence the local tritium concentration. The clad temperature and tritium pressure are the key variables. Different permeation processes may be important at the pressures expected under reactor conditions. Furthermore, neutron damage and realistic coolant, purge, and breeder impurities/corrosion products will affect the surfaces. Also the burn/dwell cycling may initiate or propagate cracks and, therefore, affect the tritium permeation.

2.6.3 Chemical reactions

The area of chemical reactions encompasses various issues, such as activation product, structural oxidation, and energy release. These issues could have severe impacts on the structural materials,

as well as chemically active liquid metals like PbLi. In the case of accidental oxidation, property degradation and radioactivity/chemical toxicity mobilization could occur, and high temperatures could lead to material volatility. The level of concern for these issues varies depending on the reactor's details, and scoping tests are essential to determine the possible level of concern for new materials. Operating environment parameters, such as time, impurities, temperature, flow velocity, pressure, and the chemical oxidizing environment, also need to be examined for all sub-cases. Neutrons are necessary only to induce relevant isotopes in certain materials, and exact duplication of all isotopes in relative amounts similar to that produced in a fusion spectrum is not needed.

PbLi has chemical reactivity with air (oxygen, nitrogen, and water vapor), water, and concrete, with the water reaction being particularly violent. The reaction releases hydrogen, which poses a hazard for combustion in air.

Neutrons are not necessary to study the severity of lithium chemical reactions. However, radiation damage will affect failure modes and rates, contributing to the overall level of concern for systems that use PbLi. However, temperature is a vital parameter for assessing this issue.

2.6.4 Tritium inventory

It is anticipated that fusion reactor blankets will experience off normal events, including thermal transients. This is particularly concerning for solid breeders, as they may contain large quantities of tritium, which could be released in case of a rupture. If a large amount of tritium is released, there could be serious safety implications.

The potential impact of tritium release is considered a generic issue that affects all fusion reactor blanket designs. However, the level of concern varies depending on the type of blanket material used. Solid breeders have the highest level of concern, while liquid metals have a medium level of concern due to their lower tritium inventory.

Neutron damage to structural materials and the distribution of tritium production rates in solid breeders can influence the tritium release. The operating parameters, such as temperature, solubility, and diffusion constants, strongly affect tritium release during thermal transients. Surface release mechanisms and stresses may also contribute to increased tritium release.

2.6.5 Failure modes and frequencies

The focus of the issues is mainly on the consequences of risks, without considering their frequency. New failure modes could result in severe problems for DEMO, and all relevant reactor testing should be screened for any signs of such issues. In some cases, specific tests may be required to obtain adequate operating time.

Abnormally new failure modes could lead to low machine availability, increased maintenance problems, and safety failures.

High-risk components that incorporate new technology must be thoroughly tested to determine the possibility of failure for use in DEMO; therefore, the level of concern is high. Neutrons are required for damage studies. Each high-risk component should undergo testing in prototypical conditions.

2.6.6 Nuclear heating rate predictions

During reactor operation, one of the main functions of the blanket is to convert the kinetic energy of incident neutrons into sensible heat through interactions with blanket materials. However, uncertainties in modelling, calculation methods, nuclear data, and geometrical definition can contribute to uncertainty in local and integrated heat generation. After reactor shutdown, heat is generated through the radioactive decay of radionuclides (usually estimate to be ~2% of the thermal power during normal operations).

The level of concern regarding a large uncertainty in heat generation prediction is high, especially since many blanket performance parameters are temperature dependent. In contrast, the level of concern with decay heat prediction is medium, as afterheat is only about 1-3% of the total heat generated during reactor operation.

Heat deposition during operation is a strong function of neutrons and gamma ray fluxes, spectra, and fluences. Decay heat after shutdown is a strong function of the previous history of operation. Neutrons are required for decay heat testing except for irradiation purposes. Gamma-ray heating is dominant in stainless steel type structures.

2.6.7 Blanket response to near blanket failures

The proximity of components near the blanket (e.g. limiters) may lead to abnormal conditions and potentially cause damage to the blanket, but both the conditions and the blanket response are uncertain, and interactions among components are poorly understood in general.

Any blanket could be affected by surrounding component interactions, but in tokamaks this issue is of particular concern due to the closer proximity of a limiter to the blanket, the higher heat load on a limiter, and the potential for a coolant leakage to trigger a disruption that could subject the blanket and limiter to a high thermal flux and transient magnetic influences.

There are no neutron-related considerations for this issue, and testing must include prototypical temperatures, geometries, stresses, coolant velocities, coolant pressures, transient pressures, and chemical environment.

2.6.8 Assembly and fabrication of blankets

Current blanket designs may be difficult to fabricate due to their geometric complexity and the large number of parts that need to be assembled. The tolerances are also small, adding to the difficulty. Fabrication of the solid breeder material is particularly uncertain, as it requires high purity and specific microstructure. These difficulties in fabrication and assembly may result in higher costs and reduced reliability of the blanket.

Neutrons are not required for the operating environment, and geometry is the only critical parameter.

2.6.9 Recycling of irradiated lithium and beryllium

There are enough beryllium resources available to consider its use as a neutron multiplier in first and second generation fusion reactors. However, for subsequent generations, careful attention to beryllium recycling losses will be required. Since beryllium will be activated in the fusion environment, a remote fabrication technology will be necessary. The potential impact is that without the development of recycling, beryllium neutron multiplier should only be used in the first generation of fusion reactors. This concern applies to all blankets that use beryllium neutron multipliers. The extended use of beryllium is dependent upon adequate recycling.

Neutrons provide the activation of the beryllium, and the heat and transmutations that generate the internal helium, which must be removed during recycling. The principal controlling parameters are the total neutron fluence, neutron energy spectrum, and operating temperatures (400°C to 600°C).

2.6.10 Prediction and control of normal effluents associated with fluid radioactivity

Several fluids used in nuclear reactors can become radioactive. The radioactivity can originate from the activation of the fluid itself (e.g. water), activation of impurities in the fluid, sputter products from the walls, or corrosion products from the walls. This radioactive material can be released into the environment through direct leakage to a steam generator, leakage or spillage into the reactor building, or waste streams from fluid processing systems. Leakage or spillage into the reactor building can also increase radiation fields, making maintenance more difficult and increasing occupational exposure.

Over- or under-estimating the amount of effluents released can have significant consequences. Overestimating could lead to siting restrictions or excessive control costs, while underestimating could require restricting operation or adding expensive remedial control systems. For highly active fluids such as PbLi, the impact could be severe enough to require substantial reduction or halting of reactor operation.

The level of concern is high for fluids with high radioactivity levels due to the potential for significant impact and uncertainty.

Neutrons are not needed for direct effluent tests, but sputtering and corrosion tests, some of which require neutrons, are generally necessary. Operating experience with prototypical fluid systems is needed to determine the potential for leaks and radioactivity levels in waste streams.

2.6.11 Tritium processing

2.6.11.1 Tritium Monitoring and Accountability

The current standards set high level of accuracies (>100 Ci/yr or 0.01 µg/yr [3]) in tritium processing systems, but this is technically unrealistic for a fusion reactor that circulates 1 kg/d of tritium with several more kilograms in storage, especially considering tritium's decay, burnup, creation, and permeation across large piping surfaces in different phases and chemical compounds. To address this issue, regulatory guidelines need to be developed to determine what tritium uncertainties are appropriate to meet real concerns, such as controlling the vulnerable tritium inventory from a safety perspective. However, meeting these accountability guidelines will require developing reliable real-time tritium monitors with good resolution, as well as a comprehensive computer model of the tritium inventory, including the tritium implanted (in the order of kilogram) into BB, limiters or divertors, which would need to be measured or modelled. At present, periodic shutdowns may be necessary to check specific inventories. This issue is generic to all DT fusion devices, and both monitoring and modelling techniques are being developed to meet the high level of concern due to the importance of the issue (both physical and public perceptions), the tight requirements that need to be met, and the current abilities to predict and measure tritium in an activated, on-line system.

High tritium accountability requires accurate assessment of regions exposed to neutrons due to neutron heating, specific reactions, and neutron damage. Flow rates, overall geometry, tritium concentrations, and impurities all directly affect the accountability, and secondary concerns include variation with time, operational transients, instrumentation response times, monitor lifetime, and neutron flux and fluence.

2.6.11.2 Tritium losses and extraction from coolant

Although strict controls will be placed on the release of tritium through gaseous and liquid effluents, larger amounts might be disposed with solid waste. Sources of such waste include the fuel clean up system and discarded components with high tritium levels trapped in the irradiated materials. There are several possible approaches to deal with this issue, such as additional impurity removal stages, better waste treatment technologies, baking of highly tritiated components, and modifications to the fuel clean up process. However, the source terms need to be quantified, and reprocessing and disposal issues need further attention. The cost of controlling tritium losses to acceptable levels is a major uncertainty that needs to be addressed. This issue is of high concern since it may significantly impact most designs as demonstrated in [4]. The tritium processing systems will operate outside of the neutron field, but neutron-induced trapping and neutron-enhanced permeation losses in the breeder region may affect overall losses. The efficiency of the processing system is related to tritium

concentrations, impurities, and time. Plasma and neutrons could influence the amount of tritium trapped in discarded components.

The possibility of tritium permeating into the water coolant within the hot blanket or plasma interactive region, and then transferring out of the primary system across a heat exchanger is a major safety concern, given that water is a desirable coolant. If significant tritium permeation into the water is inevitable, then it would be costly to remove, and there may be a general need for tritium removal from water in the secondary containment and waste treatment systems.

Present water-cooled designs assume that surface barriers will control tritium permeation to manageable levels, but this remains to be seen under fusion reactor conditions. If an acceptable tritium removal system could be demonstrated, then a significant drawback to water coolants would be eliminated.

The tritium extractor could be located outside the neutron field. The primary factors that affect the efficiency of the tritium removal system are water coolant flow rate, tritium concentration, and impurity level. The overall geometry and temperature might also constrain the size and process.

2.6.11.3 Tritium Processing System Integration

To prove system performance, an integrated system demonstration is necessary, encompassing various components such as plasma exhaust, vacuum system, breeder extraction system, isotope separation, tritiated waste treatment, secondary containment, and overall instrumentation and control. It is important to identify necessary redundancies for reliability and safety, as well as trade off the size and integrity of the secondary containment against cost and maintainability. Additionally, potential risks such as the possibility of mixing explosive amounts of hydrogen and oxygen must be assessed.

This system integration step will help identify any unknown or unexpected interactions among components, as well as operating procedures, that could reduce system performance. All DT reactors must process tritium, but the actual system design will vary according to expected throughputs, impurities, and tritium form. The need to verify overall performance and safety of this subsystem, including instrumentation and control, in near full-scale conditions gives this a high level of concern.

The tritium processing system is away from the neutron environment. The important variables are the flow rate, overall geometry, interconnectedness with other fusion systems, time effects (aging, wear, operational transients), and impurity effects, which might foul up the chemical processing system.

To reduce the hazard of tritium to personnel and the public in the event of tritium spills inside the containment building, emergency atmospheric clean up procedures must be implemented. These procedures generally involve using a large number of air detritiation. However, tritium can be expected to soak into exposed surfaces. The rate of soaking in and out again is not well known, leading to uncertainties in clean up time.

The number of detritiation systems installed in the containment building is based on a trade-off between economics and safety concerns for personnel. The effectiveness of the atmospheric clean up and the extent of soak-in depend on the spill size, geometry, and time scales.

2.6.11.4 Breeder Tritium Extraction Characteristics

The sustenance of the reactor relies on processing all the tritium required from the breeder, either in solid or liquid form. This input stream is distinct from the plasma exhaust. The solid breeder purge mainly consists of helium gas doped with hydrogen. There are uncertainties surrounding the Q2/Q2O ratio, isotopic abundances, impurity concentrations and type, and tritium phase and chemical compound flow rate. These uncertainties vary between different blanket designs and

within the same design. In solid breeder blankets, protium gas may be deliberately added to enhance the amount of tritium present as hydrogen gas.

The nature of the breeder tritium output stream primarily affects the fuel clean-up system, as the hydrogen is an additional load on the isotope separator. The breeder extraction stream requires special processing before being mixed with the rest of the fuel cycle. Uncertainties in the breeder output, especially the amount of protium and the Q2/Q2O ratio, are a performance and cost concern for the tritium processing system.

The level of concern regarding the uncertainties is low, as there is some understanding of the nature of the breeder output from present blanket designs, and impurity removal systems have enough flexibility to handle the uncertainties (with some economic penalty).

Neutron reactions can produce tritium, transmute other materials, and potentially cause decomposition of Q2O. Neutron sputtering and material damage contribute to the impurity level. Neutrons also influence tritium recovery and the overall purge flow behavior, particularly in solid breeders, which gives rise to uncertainties in the output rate and content. The breeder tritium output is a function of the purge/breeder flow rate, geometry, tritium concentration and impurities, and breeder temperature. Neutron flux and fluence are additional parameters that determine flow rate, impurity levels, and tritium concentrations to the extent that neutrons are important.

3 Requirements for breeding blanket testing-qualification w/ neutrons

The tests required for BB issues include single and multiple effect tests that require similar measurement capabilities and conditions. These tests should address several issues like the solubility, diffusivity, surface migration, desorption, flow effects, mass transfer, tritium recovery, and permeation losses from the blanket. Measurements will include tritium carrier chemistry, coolant or sweep gas tritium activity, post-test exam for mass transfer and tritium inventory, and neutron flux and spectrum dosimetry. The subsequent paragraphs propose several experiments that use neutrons aimed at addressing the aforementioned concerns.

3.1 Experiments on heat transfer

For addressing issues related to the heat transfer, experiments should be conducted using small blanket unit cell as test assembly. The tests should specifically address, at least empirically, heat transfer in realistic BB geometries. Multi-cell experiment can be also foreseen in case the tests are conducted together with tritium recovery experiments.

The initial performance of the unit cells is tested in Mid-of-Life (MOL) tests, while End-of-Life (EOL) tests include long-term changes. Blanket failure mechanisms are unlikely to appear in unit cell tests, and therefore MOL and EOL testing are nearly synonymous. Measurements include temperature (breeder, coolant, and tritium carrier such as purge gas or PbLi), purge pressure drop, and post-test examination of the breeder zone or of the breeder structure and the gap dimensions in case of solid BBs.

The importance of neutrons in this kind of tests is high, as they can be useful for bulk heating and radiation effects on heat transfer, such as thermal conductivity changes at high burnup or mass redistribution. Also, the formation of tritium may be important for mass transfer and any effect on gap conductance (in case of solid BB).

The importance of the fusion spectrum is high due to more typical damage rates in the structure and the greater likelihood of simulating life-limiting effects.

The exact geometry, including breeder microstructure and surface roughness (if possible), mechanical boundary stress, coolant and tritium carrier temperature, pressure, velocity, power density, and purge chemistry must be reproduced to replicate the required environmental conditions.

In these tests, the breeder temperature is not a test parameter but an output and according to the volume available for testing, several parallel tests can be foreseen.

3.2 Experiments on breeder thermo-mechanical interactive effects

The objective of these experiments is to study the thermomechanical interactive effects of solid BB behavior under realistic geometry, temperature, and stress states. Two rough classes of tests should be performed: (1) heating or beginning of life (BOL) and (2) radiation effects or MOL/EOL.

The heating tests would include thermal and pressure stresses, thermal creep and distortion, initial gap conductance, solid breeder cracking, sintering or settling, and hot spot effects. Radiation would add radiation-induced thermal conductivity changes affecting the temperature profile, swelling, radiation-induced creep and sintering, and many other effects.

These experiments would require measurements of temperature, stress, and post-test examination for gap size, cracking, sintering or settling, swelling, and any other observable changes. Neutrons would be certainly required for the second series of tests, but they can provide the heating during the first experiments.

The breeder thermomechanical behavior will depend on the temperature, coolant and purge pressure, bulk heating, geometry, and cycling. The tests should include a basic structural submodule of the blanket. For solid breeders, a few unit cells could be

accommodated, while a larger size might be needed for the larger-structured liquid breeder blankets in order to reproduce the MHD effect.

To bring out interactive effects, perhaps two BOL tests would be needed to understand the thermal interactions, and then somewhat more to allow studying radiation effects. It would be desirable to have high energy neutrons.

3.3 Permeation of tritium into breeder/multiplier coolant

These tests may be conducted in conjunction with other breeder or multiplier tests but are described separately due to their different focus. The objective of these tests is to determine tritium permeation rates from the breeder region into the coolant under actual operating geometry and conditions. Unlike simpler element tests that may have measured local permeation rates under ideal conditions and geometries, and determined the controlling processes, these tests primarily measure the net tritium permeation rate into the coolant. The measurements include tritium activity in the breeder tritium carrier and in the coolant, tritium carrier stream pressure and temperature, the form of tritium in the tritium carrier (oxide or elemental), clad temperature, and post-test examination of the clad surfaces to determine the surface conditions.

In these tests, neutrons are of high importance. Indeed, they provide the source distribution and concentrations of tritium, are the primary source of heat, and may affect the permeation process itself. Therefore, it is important to have neutrons. Since the exact contribution of neutrons to the permeation process is not known, the importance of the neutron spectrum is also uncertain. However, for beryllium multiplier, the (n, H) reaction threshold is 11.6 MeV, requiring high-energy neutrons if the tritium source term is to be correctly simulated.

The test environment should include tritium (diffusion rates are different from other hydrogen isotopes by more than just the mass ratio) and stable coolant, clad and tritium carrier pressures and temperatures, geometry (including joints and tritium carrier flow path), chemical environment, and temperature cycling. The test article should include a few breeder/multiplier unit cells.

3.4 Verification of thermomechanical behavior of submodules under complex loading

These tests involve subjecting a section of a full module (such as a first wall section or several solid breeder units) to stress conditions similar to those in an operating blanket to verify the thermomechanical design. Measurements include temperature, stress, and post-test examination for cracks, growth, deformation, or other visible changes.

Neutrons are needed as a source of heating, to produce specific reactions, and to cause material damage. Temperature gradients and neutron radiation can cause differential swelling and irradiation creep, leading to excessive stresses in the BB that can result in failure. Moreover, neutron damage can cause excessive distortion. The interaction of thermal creep, irradiation creep, and swelling leads to a complex time, temperature, and fluence-dependent stress history in the first wall/blanket module. The correct neutron spectrum is crucial because it affects the amount of creep and swelling that occurs. Neutrons can alter the stress distributions and deflections of a component. Thermal stresses and swelling relax during the plasma burn due to irradiation creep. Upon shutdown, these stresses reverse, causing residual tensile stresses to remain during the non-burn portion of the cycle. Bulk and surface heat flux and plasma effects are also important. Surface heat flux establishes the expected thermal gradients in the structure and the operating temperature. Irradiation creep and swelling depend heavily on the structure's temperature, and the correct thermal gradient is needed to determine the effects of differential swelling caused by the gradient.

An act-alike submodule is required to investigate the interaction of thermal and irradiation effects on stresses in the first wall and distortion of the breeder zone. This submodule will provide the primary stress distributions (coolant pressure and vacuum loading), secondary stress distributions (thermal gradients, swelling, and creep), and the distortions resulting from these loads.

3.5 Tritium behavior in thermal and flow transients

The objective of these tests is to investigate the behavior of tritium inventory in at least one breeder unit cell, under transient thermal or flow conditions. The measurements in these tests would include the temperature of the breeder and coolant, coolant and tritium carrier activity, and post-test examination for tritium inventory, cracking, or other solid breeder changes.

It is critical to have the correct distribution of tritium prior to the transients and, in case of solid BB, neutron damage effects. This can only be achieved through neutron-generated tritium. Adding tritium in the tritium carrier and letting it soak into the breeder will yield very different tritium concentration gradients. Some transients may also require heat and tritium generation during the tests.

The breeder temperature, coolant and tritium carrier conditions (flow, temperature, tritium partial pressure, impurities) should be reproduced in a similar geometry. The transient time scales should be adjusted to be consistent with the thermal and tritium recovery time scales of the test article, which may not be the same as in a reactor if the test articles are scaled.

There will be a range of transients to consider, but since safety considerations will suggest severe transients (blockage, leak of coolant into breeder), and since a detailed and destructive post-test analysis will be required to locate the tritium inventory, each test would require a separate test article.

3.6 Blanket response to coolant transients

To conduct a thorough assessment of coolant transients, it is necessary to expose a full or almost full module to scenarios involving loss of flow or loss of coolant. Subsequently, measurements of temperature, stress, coolant pressure, and flow rate should be taken, while examining the module for any signs of deformation or failure.

Neutrons are important in testing coolant system transients to simulate volumetric heat generation rates in a fusion reactor. The required environmental conditions include geometry, coolant velocity and heating, as well as the interaction of the escaping coolant in a loss of coolant accident with the materials in the breeding blanket and any purge gas. Additionally, the weakened and possibly embrittled condition of coolant tubes and blanket structure due to neutron irradiation damage and possibly sintered condition of breeding materials need to be reproduced. In case of liquid metal (e.g. PbLi), a magnetic field would be required to accurately simulate system transients. To accurately model the behavior of the component under a coolant transient, the test article should be of roughly the same size as the corresponding component section. A small range of transient conditions should be tested, including some mild ones where the test article can probably be reused, and some more violent ones where there may be destroyed. Simultaneous testing of multiple modules is not necessary, except where flow instabilities in the entire system are concerned. The component response to the transient should not be of a statistical nature.

3.7 Verification of neutronics prediction

Neutronics predictions for (i) tritium breeding, (ii) nuclear heating, and (iii) induced activation should be verified through tests on a complete full-scale module. Post-test examinations are carried out to measure activation, tritium inventory, and neutron fluence. The fusion spectra are crucial to consider in these tests because resolving errors and uncertainties is essential, with a reasonable allowable margin. The geometry is an essential factor to consider since the local neutron field is influenced by the nature of the module and

its surroundings. The size of the test article depends on the reactor design, but test modules should at least mock up the blanket module, and the neutronic environment in the test module should be equivalent to that of a full-size reactor.

The number of test articles depends on the design, but modules located near ports should be included. Multiple tests may be necessary to establish the required accuracy.

3.8 Verification of full-module thermal and corrosion performance

Full-module verification tests are necessary to ensure that the entire blanket module functions as expected. However, partially integrated tests can focus on simulating thermal and corrosion behavior in the full component, though this may come at the expense of other features such as thermos-mechanics. The measurements taken during testing include bulk fluid temperature, pressure, flow rate, coolant/purge chemistry, local internal temperatures, some stresses, possibly some local flow rates, and extensive post-test examination for any changes. There are three different test goals with specific issues and requirements.

For BOL performance testing, uncertainties arise from unexpected design-specific synergies and poor modelling of the precise geometry of the module. These uncertainties can lead to off-normal operation, and full-module verification testing is required to resolve them. All issues related to thermal-hydraulics must be addressed at this level, including verification of the module temperature field, coolant flow instabilities, MHD pressure drop (liquid metal blankets only), thermal/geometric instabilities, and interface heat transfer.

MOL performance testing involves extended operation of the blanket, which adds additional uncertainty to its projected performance due to nuclear and non-nuclear effects. Unanticipated interactions and imperfect modelling can also contribute to these uncertainties. Longer-term full-module testing is necessary to address these concerns. The issues addressed in MOL testing are similar to those in BOL testing, with an emphasis on performance changes that occur with extended operation.

EOL performance testing will likely suggest which effects will eventually prove life-limiting. Direct testing at the full-module level to observe EOL performance and failure mechanisms is highly desirable to develop confidence in blanket lifetime estimates.

Neutrons are critical for all full-module tests because they are needed to accurately simulate module- bulk heating, which is difficult or impossible to accomplish without neutrons. A fusion spectrum is also critical for BOL, MOL, and EOL tests because of the difficulty in otherwise simulating these conditions over an entire module. All environmental aspects should be present during testing.

3.9 Tritium recovery verification

Although it would be ideal for a full module test to address all performance issues of the blanket, scaling requirements may prioritize a module that focuses on "act-alike" tritium recovery instead of fully addressing thermomechanical or neutron-related conditions. The requirements for such a test module are discussed here, which would include in-situ tritium activity measurements in tritium carrier and coolant streams, neutron dosimetry, and post-test tritium assays to determine the location and magnitude of the tritium inventory.

Neutrons are critical in producing tritium, causing damage and swelling in the solid breeder, and generating heat within the blanket. The fusion spectrum is highly important in integrated module testing, with the spatial distribution of heat generation, tritium production, damage, and swelling being particularly sensitive to the spectrum in a large module. Other required environmental conditions include tritium carrier and coolant flow through the blanket module to establish tritium recovery and heat transfer processes. Moreover, the tritium movement in the blanket is essential for its functional operation. The size of the test element module is specific to each design.

3.10 Module thermomechanical lifetime verification

The verification of module thermomechanical lifetime performance involves conducting full module tests that focus on the structural failure modes and measure local temperatures and stresses. Post-test examination is carried out to determine the cause of failure. **Neutrons are critical as they provide a source of heating, produce specific reactions, and cause significant damage. Temperature gradients and neutron damage can lead to differential swelling and irradiation creep, resulting in excessive stresses that may cause failure. The correct neutron spectrum is also critical because it impacts the amount of creep and swelling that takes place. The required environments include surface heat flux and plasma effects, which are essential in establishing expected thermal gradients in the structure and operating temperature. The test article site must be an act-alike module that investigates the interaction of thermal and irradiation effects on stresses in the first wall and distortion of the component.**

4 References

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Report Annex 3.2

Quantitative estimates on requirements for instructive examples of Breeding Blanket testing

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Introduction: Requirements for Breeding Blanket testing

In this technical note, quantitative estimations on key testing parameters required for the qualification of breeding blanket technology are reported, mainly based on the study led by Prof. Abdou et al. in the 80s [1], **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..** These key parameters are mainly neutron wall load, which governs the neutron fluence on test specimens (modules, segments or sectors), the test size and/or volume depending on the type of test and exposure time and/or characteristic time constants of the phenomena to be evaluated.

Effective testing necessitates that a test facility's physical and operational characteristics align with specific conditions. Key test requirements are related to the major parameters of the test facility (Table 1) and are connected to the estimated reference conditions for a commercial reactor. Table 1 outlines minimum values primarily derived from an in-depth examination of significant blanket phenomena under associated test conditions. If these minimum values are not met, the utility of nuclear testing for at least one identifiable phenomenon will be significantly limited, and it is highly likely that results will not be applicable to reactor conditions. Conversely, the recommended values, based on both analysis and engineering judgement, provide sufficient confidence for extrapolating results to reactor conditions.

Table 1. Device parameters: reference conditions and recommended values (adapted from [3])

Parameter	Test facility		Reference reactor
	Minimum	Recommended	
Neutron Wall Load [MW/m ²]	1	2-3	5
Surface heat load on FW [MW/m ²]	0.2	0.2-0.5	1
Fluence at test module (a) [MW yr/m ²]	2	3-6	15-20 (b)
Plasma burn time [s]	500	>1000 (c)	Steady state
Plasma dwell time [s]	<100	<50	-
Continuous operating time	Days	Weeks	months

Availability [%]	20	30-50	70
Test port size [m ² x m]	0.5 x 0.3	1 x 0.5	-
Total test surface area [m ²]	5	10-20	-
Magnetic field strength	3	5	≈7

- (a) Fluence at test module. Required test device lifetime is greater (by factor ≈2)
- (b) Blanket lifetime
- (c) Steady state is preferred

Nuclear fluence requirements

Neutrons contribute to various changes in material properties and the behaviour of materials, which in turn define design constraints for blankets and their lifespan. These effects primarily rely on the total neutron dosage. Test requirements can be determined by achieving neutron fluences at which significant behaviour changes occur or become saturated. However, some behaviour changes are the result of interactions between different effects, and thus, a mere understanding of alterations in material properties is insufficient to determine test requirements.

Table 2 presents examples of critical phenomena that may potentially occur in the Breeding Blanket as a function of neutron fluence [3]. Both changes in material properties and engineering interactive effects can be observed. Nonetheless, the data in the table should be considered approximate estimates due to the substantial uncertainties arising from the lack of sufficient data for most of these phenomena.

The objective of the test facility should be to encompass at least the early-life effects, while the inclusion of mid-life effects would be considered advantageous. Based on the constraints of cost and technological capabilities, it would be preferable to test the breeding blanket throughout its entire lifespan and even beyond. This approach would allow for the prediction of both lifespan duration and failure modes resulting from extended exposure.

Table 2. Examples of important effects as function of exposure (adapted from [3])

Radiation effect classification	Exposure/Fluence [MW yr/m ²]	Phenomena/effects
Beginning-of-life effects	0-0.2	Thermo-physical property changes (e.g. thermal conductivity) First Wall erosion Tritium permeation
Early-life effects	0.2-1	Structural steel ductility changes Initiation of fatigue and creep-fatigue Thermal stress relaxation Reduction of fracture toughness in structural steel Early transmutation effects (e.g. drop in thermal conductivity due to element transmutation)

	1-3	Saturation of ductility changes in structural steel Burn-up effects on chemistry, compatibility, breeding Irradiation hardening / softening saturates
Middle-of-life effects	3-5	Possible fatigue crack propagation Possible fracture toughness degradation in structural steel
	5-10	Potential onset of irradiation creep / swelling interaction in structural steel Possible fatigue failure Change in fracture mode in structural steel
Lifetime effects	10-20	End-of-life phenomena: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • operational stress effects • Unstable deformation & cracking • Fatigue / creep-fatigue

Fluence is one of the most critical parameters of primary interest to testing. The magnitude of this fluence will have a substantial impact on the selection and design of any VNS. Any fluence requirement must be developed considering the following factors:

- time required to perform basis and multiple effects experiments to observe group of phenomena;
- time required to observe integrated behaviour past the beginning of life, during periods of significant radiation-induced changes in material properties;
- time required to obtain data on key issues related to long-term component and system behaviour such as corrosion, mass transfer, etc.;
- time required to obtain data on failure modes, effects and rates;
- time required to perform the needed stages: the reliability growth testing phase is the most demanding on fluence requirements [7].

Two important parameters to be taken into account when selecting fluence and test area are:

1. the machine lifetime fluence $I_d = P_{nw} \cdot A_d \cdot t_d$

where

P_{nw} is the average neutron wall load at the first wall of the fusion testing facility [MW/m²],
and

A_d the machine availability averaged over t_d , the machine lifetime [yr],

It is obvious that in a possible VNS the machine availability A and/or the average neutron wall load P_{nw} in the testing section (most likely the equatorial region if the VNS is a tokamak) should be as high as possible. This would allow, in fact, reaching testing objectives in a reasonable VNS exploitation period.

2. the test module fluence which is the time-integrated wall load as received at the front (first) wall of the test module: $I_m = P_{nw} \cdot A_m \cdot t_m \cdot T$

where

P_{nw} is the average neutron wall load at the first wall of the fusion testing facility [MW/m²],

A_m the machine availability averaged over t_m , the time during which a test module is placed in the machine [yr],

T is the transmission factor (equivalent fraction of neutron wall load that reaches the test module).

The testing facility lifetime fluence should be much greater than the test module fluence because normally no test module is inserted for the entire lifetime of the machine t_d and because the transmission factor T is always less than unity.

One of the most serious concerns in the engineering development of a new technological component is the demonstration of dependability and reliability, thus the assessment of possible failure mode and rates.

Causes of failures include errors in design, manufacturing, assembly and operation; lack of knowledge and experience; insufficient prior testing and random occurrence despite available knowledge and experience. Experience from other technologies shows that the failure rate during the lifetime of a component for a fully developed technology generally looks like a bathtub curve:

Figure 1: Failure rate characteristic for developed and underdeveloped technologies [7]

To derive the blanket system and other fusion nuclear technology component availability requirements for achieving a target DEMO availability it could be assumed that the reactor availability goal is determined by its main components, which at their fully developed stage for DEMO would carry the same amount of outage risk in reactor unavailability. Such a component apportionment has led to a required blanket/first wall system availability of 49 % for achieving a European DEMO reactor availability of 30%.

The blanket system availability goals can be used to establish blanket module availability requirements. A blanket system can be viewed as system consisting of several blanket modules in series for which the failure of any blanket module causes failure of the blanket system and the failure of any blanket module is entirely independent of the failure of any other blanket module.

The availability of any blanket module A_n - assuming that the MTTR for both the blanket system and blanket module are identical (blanket replacement operations in parallel), can be written as:

$$A_n = \frac{n}{(n-1) + \frac{1}{A_{BS}}} = \frac{1}{1 + \lambda_n \text{MTTR}_n}$$

For the 30% DEMO reactor availability, the MTBF_n ranges from 1.5 to 12.65 FPY for $\text{MTTR} = 1$ week to $\text{MTTR} = 2$ months. A 60% DEMO reactor availability scenario seems then an extremely ambitious goal compared with the state of the art.

MTTR	MTBF _n (FPY)	
	A (reactor) = 60%	A (reactor) = 30%
1 week	13.9	1.5
2 weeks	27.4	2.9
1 month	60	6.5
2 months	119	12.65

Figure 2: Required DEMO Blanket Module MTBF_n as a function of the mean time to repair for two values of DEMO reactor availability [7]

The main concern here is that failure rates may be much higher in fusion blankets with respect to steam generators and the core of fission reactors (from which the current data are so far extrapolated) since the former appear to be much more complex, indeed:

- larger numbers of subcomponents and interactions,
- more damaging, higher energy neutrons,
- other environmental conditions: magnetic field, vacuum, tritium, etc.,
- reactor components must penetrate each other,
- the ability to have redundancy inside the blanket/first wall is practically impossible.
- Some other important aspects to be highlighted are also:
- the capability to replace first wall and blanket in a reasonable time must be a design goal for fusion devices,
- design concepts must aim at improving reliability (minimize welds, brazes, tube length, etc.),
- a serious reliability and availability analysis must be an integral part of the design process,
- the R&D program must be based on quantitative goals for reliability (type of tests, prototypicality of test, number of tests and test duration),
- reliability growth testing in fusion devices will be the most demanding (particularly on the number of tests and time duration of tests). Reliability testing should include identification of failure modes and effects, aggressive iterative design/test/fix programs aimed at improving reliability and obtaining of failure rate data sufficient to predict MTBF.

To assess failure rates, the most used mathematical framework is the Poisson model also known as the constant failure rate model. The Poisson distribution can be used to relate the number of

testing failures, the confidence level, the testing time and the estimated MTBF. This model asserts that the component fails at random points in time but with a constant long-term average occurrence rate. Although the Poisson model might not really describe the failure behaviour of fusion components (material properties change with time because of irradiation effects), it is widely used and often is quite adequate.

The following picture shows the upper statistical confidence level as a function of the test time in multiples of MTBF and the number of failures that occurred during the test:

Figure 3: Upper statistical confidence level as a function of the test time in multiples of MTBF [7]

If larger number of failures occur, then very much longer test times are required to give high confidence that the actual MTBF is greater than or equal to the estimated one. Conversely, if few failures occur during the test period, high confidence levels can be provided with relatively short test periods. This implies that quick reliability confirmation might be obtained if the as-demonstrated MTBF of the component is higher than its required value.

Reliability growth testing in fusion devices will be the most demanding (particularly on the number of tests and time duration of tests). Reliability testing should include identification of failure modes and effects to obtain sufficient data to predict MTBF.

Reliability tests can be either sequential or fixed length. Because most test situations have schedule/time constraints, time-terminated tests are the preferred choice for fixed-length test strategies. A fixed-length test plan is particularly appropriate when the total test time must be known in advance. Such a test design assuming a constant failure rate can lead to the selection of the Poisson distribution for test analyses (Weibull intensity can be used in case failure rates are expected to change as a function of system usage). As mentioned, the Poisson distribution can be used to relate the upper statistical confidence level as a function of test time in multiples of MTBF and the number of failures experienced during the test. The primary objectives are to determine the blanket test time and the test area in fusion facilities which are required to meet certain goals for MTBF.

The total test time T in multiples of MTBF is calculated as:

$$T = \frac{Nt \cdot N^{1-\alpha}}{\Phi_{NW}}$$

N is the number of test modules, t test fluence per test module, α the experience factor and Φ_{NW} the DEMO neutron wall load. The experience factor is meant to reduce the total test time of Nt by a factor which considers that similar failure causes may be seen in different modules. Based on this test plan ($T \sim 3.5$ MTBF) [7], it is possible to calculate the confirmatory DEMO reactor availability at 80 % confidence as a function of fluence on test module and number of module tested, see following picture which shows the DEMO reactor availability achievable with 80% confidence and if one assumes one failure during the test as a function of fluence on the test modules:

Figure 4: DEMO reactor availability at 80 % confidence as a function of fluence on test module [7]

The fluence requirement on the test modules is critical. Figure 4 indicates that clearly the achievable DEMO blanket availability and hence the DEMO reactor availability, increases substantially with testing fluence. **For MTTR of one week, increasing the testing fluence from 1 to 6 MW-yr/m² increases the DEMO availability from 19 to 48% with 12 test modules and from 12 to 39% for 6 test modules. For MTTR of one month, a testing fluence of 1 MW-yr/m² leads to reactor availability of only 5.6% with 12 test modules, but increasing the testing fluence to 6 MW-yr/m² increases the DEMO reactor availability to 24%.** Notice also that the downtime to recover from random failures must be, by itself one of the critical objectives for testing in fusion facilities.

Device geometry and test volume requirements

If relevant conditions can be attained in a testing device, a wide range of test types and “test articles” (following the nomenclature of Abdou et al. in the FINESSE study) is desired to qualify the breeding blanket so as to obtain the maximum exploitation of the testing device in such unique environment. A “test article” is defined here as one physical entity (e.g., mock-up, segment, etc.) tested at one set of conditions.

These tests can be oriented to the verification of global component behaviour, or experimentation over specific (critical) elements of the breeding blanket design to provide key information to gain understanding on the (single or multiple) effects, obtain experience, gain confidence in their operation and grow on reliability. More specifically, six different test categories can be identified:

- **Basic Tests** measure basic or intrinsic property data such as thermal conductivity of a solid breeder material;

- **Single Effect Tests** are experiments with a single environmental condition aimed at developing an understanding and models of a single phenomenon or issue. At some point, however, additional phenomena and interactions must be added to demonstrate and explore any synergistic effects.
- **Multiple Effect /Multiple Interaction Tests** involve both interactions among the effects of multiple environmental conditions as well as direct interactions among different physical elements.
- **Partially Integrated Tests** attempt to obtain Integrated Test information but without some key environmental condition. This category emphasizes a particular range of tests in the continuum between Multiple Effect/Multiple Interaction and Integrated Tests. It is particularly relevant for fusion where costs may limit complete simulation of all important variables.
- **Integrated Tests** demonstrate that a concept is feasible; they are the “proof-of-principle” experiments. With all key environmental conditions and physical elements present, they specifically indicate any major unanticipated interactions. However, they are often performed under scaled size or environmental conditions. Depending on the degree of scaling, a given test may emphasize one aspect of component performance over another, such as a test that simulates thermomechanical behaviour but cannot also simulate full tritium breeding behaviour because of the changes in the module needed to accommodate the available test conditions.
- **Component tests** - in contrast to the above categories of tests where the focus is on basic data, understanding and concept feasibility, are performed at a more advanced stage of development to verify that full-sized components operate as expected under complete prototypical conditions. This brings out all interactions and any remaining unknowns and yields definitive reliability and performance data.

All these tests will be essential to gain experience towards the facilitation of the licensing of the breeding blanket in front of a nuclear regulator. As highlighted in [4] and [5], such tests could then be characterised by:

- importance of neutrons;
- importance of fusion neutron energy spectrum;
- other required environmental conditions;
- typical test article size;
- number of test articles (excluding duplicate tests for statistical purposes, off-normal conditions, data at several time intervals for high fluence tests, etc.);
- usefulness and limitations of non-nuclear test stands, point neutron sources and fission reactors as test facilities.

A particularly interesting class of tests are those which require high energy or fusion neutrons, since this is directly related to the question of the ability of non-fusion test facilities to fully develop reliable fusion nuclear components. In these tests, neutrons serve as a source of bulk heating, radiation damage and/or specific reactions.

These tests re summarised in Table 3, along with estimates of test article sizes and the required number of test articles based mainly on the effort Prof. M. Abdou and colleagues did within the framework of the FINESSE Project [3] and based on the BB design solution reported in [6]. Duplication of tests for statistical purposes, off-normal conditions, data at several time intervals, for high fluence tests, are not included in the number of tests articles reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Examples of number and size of test articles (mock-ups) required for breeding blanket testing (adapted from [3])

Tests	Typical test article size (Based on the features of the BB concepts described in [6]) [cm x cm x cm]	Number of test articles
Basic Tests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structural material irradiated properties • Solid breeder and multiplier irradiated properties • Radiation damage indicator cross-sections • Long-lived isotope activation cross-sections 	1 x 1 x 2 1 x 1 x 2 1 x 1 x 0.5 1 x 1 x 0.1	20000 1200 500 200
Single Effect Tests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structure thermomechanical response experiments • Welds behaviour experiments • Shield effectiveness in complex geometries • Optical component radiation effects 	10 x 10 x 10 10 x 10 x 5 50 x 50 x 100 2 x 2 x 2	50 50 50 20
Multiple Effect / Multiple interaction Tests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submodule thermal and corrosion verification 	Liquid Breeder: 100 x 100 x 30 Solid Breeder: 100 x 50 x 30	5 5
Partially Integrated and Integrated Tests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification of High Heat Flux Component Thermomechanical Behaviour under Complex Loadings • Verification of neutronic predictions: T-breeding, nuclear heating, induced activation • Full module/segment verification: thermal and corrosion, thermomechanical lifetime, T recovery 	100 x 100 x 30 50 x 50 x 100 100 x 100 x 50	8 4 5
Component Tests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Blanket performance and lifetime verification 	Liquid Breeder: 900 x 300 x 80 Solid Breeder: 30 x 100 x 80	3 3

For the sake of an example consider the “Verification of High Heat Flux Component Thermomechanical Behaviour under Complex Loadings” (Partially Integrated and Integrated Tests). In high heat flux component design, particular for limiters and divertors, safety margins with respect to thermal-hydraulic performance (critical heat flux, flow distribution, temperature rise) and mechanical behaviour (primary and secondary stresses, cycling, deflections, erosion) are small and the need for testing is large. Module tests need to be performed in several stages with increasing complexity and size. Initially, they should verify the thermal-hydraulic behaviour, possibly with a non-nuclear heat source, as well as materials and fabrication aspects. Mechanical tests concentrating on aging and fatigue phenomena in other modules can be conducted in parallel. Finally, the synergistic thermomechanical effects have to be tested in integrated module tests. More details about the testing needs for such an issue are reported below:

- **Importance of Neutrons:** neutron damage is important with respect to the mechanical behaviour and will be needed in the integrated module tests. The thermal hydraulic tests, however, and many of the mechanical module tests can reveal valuable information about the design, fabrication techniques and overall performance without neutrons.
- **Importance of Fusion Spectrum:** the effect of fusion spectrum on neutron damage is not well understood for most of the Heat Flux Component materials. The materials test program will provide a better understanding. According to present knowledge the effect of fusion spectrum cannot be ignored.
- **Other Required Environmental Conditions:** the test environment must include high surface heating, plasma materials interactions, internal pressure stresses, and magnetic field transient forces. Extensive heating of a large surface can possibly only be achieved by an energetic particle streaming a high heat flux test stand. The mechanical loading conditions at critical joints should be simulated by either thermal cycling or by mechanical load mechanisms. The study of the mechanical response on plasma disruptions requires transient magnetic fields.
- **Test Article Size:** the test module should comprise a significant portion (possibly bordered by lines of symmetry) of a full size limiter or divertor section. Such dimension were identified in 100 x 100 x 30 cm³ according to the component features described in [6]. The module tests will be preceded by appropriate tests of smaller size.
- **Number of Test Articles:** the number of test modules with significantly different design features (e.g., coolant channel pattern, manifold arrangements, support structure, heat sink/plasma side material combination) might be in the order of eight to ten according to an educated engineering judgment. This number does not include ad hoc modifications during the test. Neither does it account for the numerous accompanying or preceding element tests.
- **Test Facilities:** high heat flux test stands are the appropriate tools for elements and module tests. However, the lack of neutrons limits their usefulness to non-irradiation tests. Point neutron sources are not applicable due to their narrow size limitations. Fission reactors cannot provide the size and surface heat load required for module tests. The thermomechanical Heat Flux Component development requires a flexible and broad stepwise non-fusion test program up to the level of these module tests, but definitely needs performance tests in fusion facilities such as TFCX for short term effects and lifetime performances, including radiation damage effects.

Moreover, for this class of interactive, partially integrated, and integrated tests, it is nearly certain that the parameters of the test device will not all match those of a full-scale fusion reactor because of cost constraints. This will result in changes to the operating conditions in the test module. If

nothing is done to correct this situation, the value of the test to resolve the key nuclear testing issues may be severely restricted. It is possible in many cases for which the phenomena are sufficiently well understood to modify the design or operating parameters of the test module in order to recover the important aspects of the testing issues. This process of developing meaningful tests at reduced device parameters is known as engineering scaling. In some cases, even if the phenomena are well-understood, a reduction of the device parameters beyond certain limits will result in the inability to maintain act-alike blanket behaviour. One of the goals of Engineering Scaling is to identify and determine these limits, or test requirements, see Table 4 for few guidelines extracted from [3]. This procedure is often difficult because blanket behaviour usually varies slowly as a function of the device parameters, without an abrupt change of operational performance. Many trade-offs between cost and benefit must be considered with respect to the large number of testing issues and their priorities. In order to understand and quantify the scaling laws and test requirements, analyses of many technical aspects of blanket operation were performed, including fluid flow, MHD, thermal-hydraulics, tritium recovery, structural mechanics, neutronics, corrosion and materials compatibility. The analyses done within the FINESSE framework were based on issues that were believed important but were limited in scope. Consequently, the conclusions regarding the requirements for useful scaled tests are not complete and have to be revised as well as updated considering the current BB design concepts instead of the ones highlighted in [6].

It is worth noting how geometric considerations play a pivotal role in defining possible testing requirements (please refer to [4] and [5]), indeed:

- the position of the test articles in the reactor (inboard or outboard, upper port or lower port or equatorial region, etc.) may affect neutron wall load (i.e., fluence), magnetic field and plasma heat flux, please refer to the previous section “*Nuclear fluence requirements*”.
- the overall geometry of the test device (tokamak) will specially influence the geometry of the large test articles (segments, sectors)

The most outstanding impact of limitations in the surface area available for testing comes from velocity, temperature, and corrosion product transport. All these parameters are in development/changing throughout the entire blanket segment. In this regime, the magnitude of heat, mass, and momentum transport are changing rapidly. Therefore, reducing the channel length for any of the channels could eliminate important regions of the blanket from the modelling. In cases where the most serious consequences occur at channel outlets, for example temperature and corrosion, important failure modes may not be properly modelled.

Another effect of reducing the channel lengths is that the temperature rise in the channels will be reduced: this is one phenomenon which can probably be accommodated by maintaining the fluid residence time. However, when the energy input to the blanket is reduced, there is no obvious way of maintaining temperature rises without affecting other phenomena. Another effect of reduced length is the decrease of MHD pressure drop. The contribution due to straight channel flow is usually the dominant one, so reducing the length substantially will increase the apparent effect of flow non uniformities, bends, etc. The contribution of this latter type of pressure drop is extremely design dependent. Finally, limits on the available surface area place minimum requirements the surface heat flux for thermos-mechanics testing.

Table 4. Engineering Scaling Guidelines (adapted from [3])

	Scaled-down Device Parameter		What is potentially lost	Scaling Techniques	Comment
1	Surface Heat Flux	a	First wall thermal stresses	Thicken first wall	Since aspect ratios must be preserved, a thicker wall results in altered radial damage gradient
		b	Spatial Distribution of Temperature dependent Radiation Damage (Radial Temperatures and Damage Profiles)	Radiation damage doesn't scale	Most important if the amount of swelling is high. Only model verification is possible
		c	Failure Modes and Stress Concentrations	Unknow	Crack growth rate increase with wall thickness; amount is unknow
		d	Pressure Stress and stress ratios	Increase magnetic field or velocity	Static pressure can be increased to model localized stresses only
2	Bulk Heating	a	Heat Transfer Coefficient and axial temperature profiles	Maintain thermal capacity, diffusivity, and velocity profiles	Secondary concern since effect is not dominant
		b	Radial Temperatures Profiles (see also 1b)	Maintain thermal capacity, diffusivity, and velocity profiles	Second wall temperature may not be easily modelled without good control of coolant temperature
		c	First wall thermal stresses	Maintain $T - \frac{\int T da}{A}$	If second wall temperature is not maintained, thermal stresses will be lost
3	Total Energy Input ($q + Q\sigma$)L	a	Corrosion Dependence on temperature Rise	Lower velocity or increase length (preserve ΔT)	Can't be scaled if residence time is fixed
		b	Radiation Effects due to Axial Temperature Gradient	Lower velocity or increase length	BB design dependent
4	Magnetic Field Strength	a	Corrosion Boundary Layer Thickness	Constant $\frac{a/H}{\sqrt{DL/u}}$	Lower field results in lower corrosion rates. Changes of a factor of two may alter regimes from diffusion controlled to velocity profile controlled
		b	MHD Pressure drop and stresses	Increase wall conductivity $\nabla p \sim v B^2 (\sigma_w/a)$ or velocity	Axial pressure gradient effects are likely not to be modelled at reduced field strength
5	Magnetic Field Geometry (B_t/B_p)	a	Fluid Flow Developing Profiles	$B_t/B_p \sqrt{\Phi} \sim L/d$	Reorient angle of flow

		b	Velocity profile effect on heat transfer		Serious concern: local velocity, B-field regime and geometry must be preserved
6	Structure geometry		Eddy currents (consequently velocity profiles, pressure drop, temperatures) and structural behaviour	Constant aspect ratios	Interactive testing requires close attention to geometry
7	Burn/dwell time	a	Temperature profile development	Keep burn time much longer than residence time	Temperature profiles develop quickly in most LM blankets (BB design dependent)
		b	Creep/swelling/Fatigue/crack growth	Uncertain	
8	Length, width	a	Thermal – velocity concentration profile development	$\alpha L/vd^2$ and $\sqrt{C_y/C_y}$ scaling, lowered velocity	
		b	Temperature rises for corrosion profile development	Scale residence time L/v	
		c	MHD Pressure Drop	Increase v or B	Model verification can probably be done in short modules

In the following, the effects of the test article geometry in the neutronics, thermal-structural behaviour and liquid metal MHD issues are briefly detailed.

Geometry effects on neutronic behaviour

In an ideal testing apparatus, there should be an aim to maintain analogous profiles of nuclear heating, tritium production, and radiation damage parameters. This would facilitate the evaluation of thermal and mechanical performance. The quality of the simulation is gauged by the degree to which these profiles mimic those of the reference reactor. Tests explicitly designed to confirm the behaviour of neutronics are considered unique due to the high level of precision required in measurements. Tritium production, in particular, demands stringent requirements as the accuracy needed to predict tritium self-sufficiency has proven to be extremely high.

The modification of the absolute value of the tritium production rate contributes significant uncertainty to the demonstration of tritium self-sufficiency. Alterations to spatial gradients compound this uncertainty and also limit the potential for accurate neutronic measurements. Calculations exploring the effect of varying the device size and test module dimensions suggest that neutronic parameters in the test module can typically be kept within 20-30% of reactor values, given appropriate maintenance of boundary conditions. The implications of scaling can be roughly assessed through an understanding of the neutron mean free paths in the blanket materials. If the first wall thickness is expanded beyond 2-3 cm or the blanket radial depth is reduced to less than approx. 20 cm, then the neutronic profiles will experience a significant impact [3].

In summary, sufficient simulation of neutronics parameters in the test module appears attainable for evaluating most non-neutronics issues such as thermomechanics and tritium recovery, provided the dimensions do not deviate by more than a factor of 2-3 from the reference reactor values. Nonetheless, the measurements of the tritium breeding ratio and some other neutronics parameters necessitate a higher degree of accuracy, which may not be feasible without full-size "look-alike" test modules or full sectors. If modules are utilized, the surface area at the first wall should be no less than 1 m x 1 m.

Geometry effects on thermal-structural behaviour

While elastic stress/ strain can typically be preserved in the context of constrained test volume, as long as aspect ratios are retained, the same cannot be said for inelastic strain. For instance, structural impacts stemming from radiation damage present scaling challenges as damage profiles rely primarily on neutron reaction cross sections and kinematics, factors relatively unconnected with geometry.

The structural response is so intrinsically tied to loading conditions that the ways in which geometry influences thermal stresses and pressure stresses become more significant issues. While aspect ratio scaling is a crucial consideration in the design of the test module, it necessitates meticulous caution to prevent the alteration of other phenomena during the test.

Geometry effects on liquid metal MHD behaviour

The geometry plays a key role in the uncertainties in phenomena related to MHD in liquid metal blankets. Velocity profiles are contingent not only on the dimensions and shape of the channel but also on the wall thickness and the configuration of the blanket outside the channel. Furthermore, these profiles are considerably influenced by the specifics of the magnetic geometry. Given these interdependencies and the resulting substantial uncertainties in blanket behaviour, testing liquid metal blankets necessitates meticulous consideration of geometric similarity.

Due to the potential requirement of long entry lengths for the development of velocity, temperature, and mass concentration profiles, as well as the possible emergence of global (interchannel) eddy currents, the space requirements for testing liquid breeding blankets can be very demanding. A potential method of scaling for testing in smaller modules involves the concept of residence time. For diffusive processes, which include heat and mass transfer in laminar flow, profile development mainly depends on the time the fluid spends in the channel. Reducing flow velocity proportional to the reduction in channel length could result in approximately equivalent profile development.

The emergence of global eddy currents in liquid metal blankets is another phenomenon that could necessitate of large test modules. These currents can manifest when geometric perturbations lead to voltage differences between channels. If the structure is electrically continuous (meaning the channel walls are not insulated), inter-channel currents can significantly influence both velocity profiles and pressure drop. This occurs as MHD-induced currents are not constrained to return through thin channel walls.

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2023 EUROfusion Breeding Blanket Working Group

Report Annex 4.1

Characterization of Materials Test Reactors

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Executive Summary

This report provides a summary of the most critical information on the EU-located Material Test Reactors (MTRs) which are (can be) used for the material irradiation relevant for the needs of qualification/development of TBM programme. Table below provides the executive summary of the MTR's features.

Reactor	reactor power ¹ , MW	max neutron flux range ² , and flux trap, n/cm2/s	fast neutron flux ³ (E > 1 MeV), n/cm2/s	volume/channel (for fast neutron flux)	number of channels ⁴	achievable dpa/year	status of the facility (operation /in construction)	time to deploy the irradiation experiment ⁵	Available irradiation environment
BR2	125 (pressurized water), typical operational power 55-65	7×10^{13} - 10^{15}	3×10^{14}	Ø32×700 mm Ø 80×700 mm	32 channels	up to 8 dpa/year	operational, license till 2035	1. T-by design ⁶ : 0.5-1 Year 2. Device with active control: 1-2 years	PWR water; Inner gas; Liquid metal; Vacuum;
HFR	45 (tank in pool)	comparable to BR2	1.8×10^{14}	Ø 31×600 mm Ø 70×600 mm	17 channels	up to 5 dpa/year	operational, license till ???	comparable to BR2	comparable to BR2
LVR-15	10 (tank in pool)	up to 2×10^{14}	6×10^{13}	to be clarified with Ladislav Vala	several irradiation positions, but parallel operation is limited (safety)	up to 1.5 dpa/year	operational, license till ???	comparable to BR2	comparable to BR2
Maria	30 (open reactor pool), typical operational power 18-24	up to 2.5×10^{14}	$1 \cdot 10^{14}$ (E > 0.5 MeV)	Ø 23, 28, 38, 46, 85 mm x 900mm	several irradiation positions, but parallel operation is limited (safety)	up to 2 dpa/year	operational license till ???	to be checked, lack of info on recent instrumented experiments	to be checked, lack of info on recent instrumented experiments
BRR	10 (open reactor pool)	up to $2.2 \cdot 10^{14}$	$7.5 \cdot 10^{13}$	6* 20*20*55 mm ³	several possible irradiation positions, but 1 irradiation rig	up to 1 dpa/year	operational license till 2023, extension for 10 more years ongoing	Comparable to BR2	N-He gas, controlled temperature 60-350 C
MYRRHA	70 (LBE pool)	up to $3 \cdot 10^{15}$	$5 \cdot 10^{14}$	Ø 80×600 mm	7 channels	up to 15 dpa/year	in construction, deployment after 2035	Comparable to BR2	Comparable to BR2, except irradiation in PWR environment
JHR	100 water cooled, pool type	up to $7.4 \cdot 10^{14}$	$6.4 \cdot 10^{14}$	Ø86×700 mm Ø 33×700 mm	26 channels	up to 18/year	in construction, deployment after 2033	Comparable to BR2	Comparable to BR2

¹ This value often defines the maximum flux, maximum fast flux and volume/number of channels available

² This range indicates the variability of the irradiation channels and maximum neutron flux summing up thermal and fast fluxes

³ This flux drives the accumulation of DPA

⁴ number of channels typically available for material irradiation experiment without affecting standard operation of the reactor (i.e. production of radio-isotopes, Si-doping and other services)

⁵ time to deploy the irradiation experiment counting from the moment of the resource allocation (= signature of the contract)

⁶ Irradiation temperature will be achieved by design and not by active control, see recent example of EUROfusion irradiation at HFIR: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0920379621007110>

Two additional comments must be given with respect to irradiation temperature range and capabilities to handle tritium-breeding experiments.

Temperature range: the irradiation temperature in general is defined by two technical aspects of the reactor: (i) possibility to perform instrumented irradiation such that electrical heaters, variable gas pressure or movable parts are introduced inside of the irradiation device; and (ii) the range of the neutron flux, at this the higher the neutron flux the higher irradiation temperature can be reached (because of the gamma heat generation inside of the irradiated materials). In general, reaching even rather irradiation temperatures (e.g. 1500-1700 °C for tungsten) is achievable thanks to gamma heating given that the neutron flux is of the order of 3×10^{14} n/cm²/s or higher.

Tritium handling capabilities: for some of the fusion materials, the generation of tritium is unavoidable or even being its function, hence handling of tritium-breeding experiments is of special importance. There can be two types of experiments involving tritium: (i) fully instrumented irradiation device which is flushed with gas thereby extracting all gaseous tritium during the irradiation; and (ii) "blind" irradiation device, where the actual production (and retention) of tritium could only be checked by post-mortem tests. The former type of the irradiation is very costly (due to the need to equip special cabinet inside the reactor hall which must be hermitical = extra danger to the operation of other reactor experiments). Usually, such devices can be installed in low-power reactors so that one single experiment could justify most/all of the operational costs and in case of the de-hermetization (=evacuation of personnel) no serious damage is made for the continuation of the reactor operation. The second type of the experiment is much cheaper and faster to organize, however, the caveat is the uncertainty in the amount of tritium that is stored inside the irradiation device and limit on the tritium that could be lost in the reactor pool/cooling circuit. This implies that there will be a strict technical limit on the amount of tritium that could be produced in a single irradiation experiment. Also, the limit for tritium will be defined by the reactor license, national regulations and organization of the safety surveillance during the reactor operation (= condition triggering the evacuation of the personnel).

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List of abbreviations

ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BR2	Belgian Reactor 2
BRR	Budapest Research Reactor
CEA	Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CVR	Centrum výzkumu Řež
EC	European Commission
EFPD	Effective Full Power Day
EJP	European Joint Programme
ESN	European Stakeholder Network
EU	European Union
HFR	High Flux Reactor
LVDT	Linear Variable Differential Transformer
LWR	Light Water Reactor
MOX	Mixed oxide fuel
MPa	MegaPascal
MTR	Materials Test Reactor
MW	MegaWatt
NRG	Nuclear Research & consultancy Group
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PWR	Pressurized Water Reactor
PSF	Pool Side Facility
R&D	Research & Development
SRA	Strategic Research Agenda
VVER	Vodo-Vodyanoi Enyergeticheskiy Reaktor (Water-Water Power Reactor)
WP	Work-package

Introduction

This report provides the current status of Material Test Reactors (MTR) in Europe which can be used for the irradiation programmes relevant for the qualification/development/down-streaming of TBM materials, sub-components and components.

It must be stated that MTRs have a critical role in Europe for the fuel and material testing to support existing nuclear fleet and R&D for the future nuclear developments, particularly SMRs, which could offer some synergistic action for the TBM programme. Material and fuel testing has been recognized as one of the potential bottlenecks to bring the new reactor designs to the market in the near future because the cost of the exploitation of the MTRs (especially for material irradiation) is compromised with the revenue generated by the production of medical isotopes.

Availability and future plans of MTRs

Current European MTRs, their capabilities and plans for the future, are listed below in the alphabetical order. Given the short time available to produce the report, the level of detailization is different for different reactors. However, all EU reactors capable to deliver neutron flux and volume relevant for the TBM qualification/development are listed in this document.

BR2, Mol, Belgium

The BR2 material test reactor is located at SCK CEN operational site in Mol, Belgium. With its nominal power of 125MW and unique adaptable core configuration, the BR2 is one of the most powerful and flexible material test reactors in the world. Since its start-up in 1962 the reactor has operated on highly enriched metallic uranium fuel with pressurised water as coolant. The core moderation is done by a combination of light water and metallic Beryllium. This combination of materials and the unique geometrical design provides a compact core with high neutronic performance.

The neutronic performance of the light water cooled, beryllium moderated core offers a wide range of neutron fluxes for experiments:

- At regular operating power (55 to 65 MW_{thermal}), the total flux in the central core region reaches 10^{15} n/cm²s. This flux can be highly thermalized in the central flux trap, yielding thermal flux levels of 10^{15} n/cm²s, while at the peripheral reflector channels, flux levels go down to 7×10^{13} n/cm²s.
- Fast neutron flux irradiation positions are available in the central cavity of fuel elements or irradiation channels surrounded by fuel elements. The fast flux

($E > 1$ MeV) with standard fuel elements ranges from 3×10^{14} down to 5×10^{12} n/cm²s.

As the reactor is cooled by pressurized (1.2 MPa) water, the allowable heat flux on the fuel surface, exposed to the nominal primary flow, is 470 W/cm² for the driver fuel, up to 600 W/cm² in experimental-set ups cooled by the primary water. The fuel elements are tubular, with 6 concentric tubes, each made of 3 circular formed fuel plates. In the centre of the fuel elements, there is sufficient space for an irradiation device. The fuelled zone is 762 mm long, the reactivity control of the load occurs through the addition of burnable poisons in the fuel meat and the vertical motion of the shim/control rods. The driver fuel elements are reloaded typically for 5 or 6 cycles, accumulating up to 60% of average burn-up.

The position and number of control rods and fuel elements are not fixed by design and therefore adaptable to the requirements of all experiments in a reactor cycle. For a typical configuration, as shown in Figure 1, between 30 and 35 driver fuel elements are loaded, together with 6 control/shim rods. A regulating rod and eventually a safety rod are added. Such configuration can typically be operated 21 to 28 days at a reactor power between 55 and 70 MW. The standard type of fuel element used in the six plate element (with F1 type of irradiation position in its centre). Upon request of experimenters, 5 plate elements can be regularly made available (F2). Historically, also other types of elements have been used and can be refabricated for dedicated experiments.

Figure 1 Cross section of BR2 reactor at mid plane with indication of irradiation channel types.

Material irradiation

Capsule-based irradiation

Un-instrumented capsules can be loaded in irradiation positions inside fuel elements (F1) or in standard channels (S). Up to 8 capsules of diameter 15mm (F1) or 25mm (S) are loaded in one irradiation position. The capsules can be loaded in the primary water flow (entire cycle irradiation) or in a thimble tube device (flexible irradiation time). The capsules can be open to the water (irradiation temperature <100°C) or can be gas filled, in which case the irradiation temperature is determined by the irradiation position (up to 1500 °C irradiation temperature), the mass of the samples, the composition of the gas (typically He/Ne/Ar) and the spacing between the samples and the cold wall of the capsule. The BAM1 capsules offer the lowest cost and lead time for irradiating structural material samples. Typical lead time to launch the irradiation is 6 months to 1 year, depending on the complexity of the design. 6 months lead time is required to organize the repetition of the experiment. The fast neutron flux (> 1 MeV) is up to 3×10^{14} n/cm²/sec, and thermal neutron flux is 1×10^{15} n/cm²/sec.

ROBIN

The ROBIN device is loaded in a thimble tube, inserted in a standard channel (S) (flexible irradiation time). The specimens are encapsulated in closed needles (9 needles of diameter 11mm); the irradiation temperature is determined by the design of the needles and is controlled by adjusting the water flow in the thimble. In order to avoid boiling, the positioning of the experiment is limited to relatively low flux positions (thermal and fast flux 0.7 and 0.3×10^{14} n/cm²s, respectively). The temperature in the samples is monitored by adding an instrumented dummy capsule with identical design as the specimen needles.

LIBERTY

The LIBERTY device is also loaded inside a thimble tube in a standard channel (S). The main difference with the ROBIN device is that there can only be 5 sample containing needles, but the needles are larger in diameter (16mm inside) and can be equipped with active temperature control by integrated electrical heating and temperature measurement. In this way, specimens can be preheated before the start of irradiation. The fluxes in LIBERTY are similar to the ones in ROBIN.

RECALL

The RECALL device is a pressurized water capsule device, loaded in a standard reflector channel (S), with small flow rate. The device allows accurate active temperature control in the range from 250 to 320°C, before as well as during irradiation. The device is loaded for the entire reactor cycle and allows to irradiate 24 standard Charpy V specimens within a homogeneous flux zone (+/-15% axial deviation). The positioning of the device is flexible in order to achieve between 0.05 and 0.15 dpa in steel in one reactor cycle. The device is reusable, offering very short lead times for experiments

MISTRAL

The MISTRAL device is inserted in a 5 plate fuel element (F2) and offers active temperature control in a boiling water environment. The MISTRAL device is designed to irradiate a large number (87) of miniature specimens (5mm diameter or 3x4mm² cross section and length of 27mm) in stable temperature conditions (160°C-350°C) with medium to high fast flux level (up to 2.5×10^{14} n/cm²s, E>1MeV). The rig can be reloaded, so lead times for experiments are limited as well as the rig costs. Of the 87 specimens, 26 are located in the zone having over 90% of the maximum flux in the rig. The irradiation temperature is monitored by measurement inside dummy specimens and the irradiation temperature is fixed by setting the saturation pressure in the rig and sustaining boiling by electrical heating if the nuclear heating is insufficient to maintain boiling (during start up and shut down of the reactor).

HTHF

For irradiating materials at maximum fast flux (2.8×10^{14} n/cm²s, E>1 MeV) in a standard fuel element (F1) and controlled temperature up to 1200°C, a gas filled capsule (diameter 21 mm) with active temperature control is designed. This capsule is constructed of graphite, allowing high temperature stability and heat evacuation under the highest fluxes available in the BR2 reactor. The design is adjusted according to the experimental needs (specimen number and geometry, temperature range) and the capsules are single use. However, capsule cost and experiment lead time are controlled by the generic design and the reuse of the out of pile control equipment. The availability of several driver fuel elements with comparable neutronic conditions allows for the simultaneous irradiation of HTHF devices, for example to compare different materials or generate data at different irradiation temperatures.

The High Flux Reactor, Petten, The Netherlands

The High Flux Reactor (HFR), located in Petten in The Netherlands, is one of the most powerful multi-purpose research and test reactors in the world and the world's largest producer of medical isotopes. The HFR is owned by the European Commission (EC). Its operation has been entrusted since 1962 to the Netherlands Energy Research Foundation and later the Nuclear Research and consultancy Group (NRG). Since February 2005, NRG became also the licence holder of the HFR.

Together with the hot cells of NRG at the Petten site, the HFR has provided for over five decades, an integral and full complement of irradiation and post-irradiation examination services as required by current and future R&D within the field of nuclear energy and healthcare for industry and research organisations. The HFR has a longstanding tradition of multilateral collaboration in combination with 'frontier breaking' irradiation programmes HFR within the domains of transmutation, HTR, graphite research and Molten Salt Reactors.

The HFR has 17 in-core and 12 poolside irradiation positions (Figure 2). The HFR uses low-enriched uranium U₃Si₂ fuel and operates at a constant power of 45 MW and uses light water both for cooling and moderation. The current cycle length is 31 operations

days with nine cycles per year, for a total of ~279 full power days/year. The reactor is of the tank in pool type with a rectangular aluminium vessel. The core is surrounded by beryllium reflector elements at three sides. At the fourth side the Pool Side Facility (PSF) is located (outside the reactor vessel).

With a variety of dedicated irradiation devices and with its long-standing experience in executing small and large irradiation projects, the HFR is particularly suited for fuel, materials and components testing for all current and advanced reactor technologies. Inside the aluminium reactor vessel, the irradiation devices may be installed in a lattice position inside the fuel region. In total 17 irradiation positions with a 60 cm effective height are available (typical diameter 70 mm). These positions can be subdivided in smaller diameter (typical diameter 31 mm) irradiation positions. Maximum flux values are in the range $2.6 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ n.cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (thermal flux) and $1.8 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ n.cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (fast flux, $E > 1 \text{ MeV}$); typical damage and fuel power values are 6 dpa/year and 200-400 W/cm (Figure 2). The flux profile of the HFR is predictable and stable, showing a small upward shift each cycle that can be compensated by vertically translating irradiation devices. Together with gas gap conductivity control, this feature provides strong control over sample temperatures.

Based irradiation tests are performed either in irradiation facilities with semi-stagnant gas or in closed capsules/ampules. Advanced irradiations are operated with advanced gas systems that enable accurate control and analysis of the sweep gases. In the past rodlets have been irradiated in stagnant sodium. Maximum irradiation temperatures in the 1000-1200°C range can be achieved. All irradiation facilities are instrumented with up to 24 thermocouples (48 for larger capsules). Irradiation facilities with bellows that apply a fixed load on the samples under irradiation, are used to determine creep under irradiation conditions. LVDT-based sensors are used to measure dimension changes and pressure in-pile.

In addition to the in-core positions the HFR has a pool-side facility. PSF experiments can be moved to and from the reactor core using a trolley system. This allows for reliable power control and power cycling, without significantly affecting other operations in the HFR core.

Figure 2 Schematic view of the HFR core, with indications of damage build-up for materials and linear heat rate for fresh LWR fuel. The pool-side facility (to the left) allows for power control and power cycling operations.

LVR-15, Rez, Czech Republic

Irradiation facility

The LVR-15 reactor is a multi-purpose research reactor. It provides a high-density neutron flux, allowing for a long-term representative material research of the Gen II, III and IV reactor materials as well as the potential material for fusion reactors. Thanks to variable configuration it is possible to simultaneously conduct several experiments at different positions within the reactor core and beyond it including horizontal neutron beam. Horizontal channels and pneumatic rabbit system are used for neutron scattering experiments and activation analysis for nuclear analytical investigations and for fundamental nuclear physics studies. The common experimental in-reactor equipment (e.g. vertical irradiation channels, "Chouca" irradiation rig or others) is used for series of long term irradiation experiments with the possibility to change the irradiation temperature, but in many cases the irradiation rigs are developed and manufactured based on specific requirements for specific experiment and user needs. Loop technology is used in CVR to investigate the behaviour in the environment corresponding to the reactor environment for the investigations of the material – coolant interaction, coolant thermohydraulic studies, impact of impurities on coolant chemistry and other purposes, covering wide range of reactor systems.

LVR-15 is a light water tank-type research reactor placed in a stainless-steel vessel under a shielding cover. It has forced cooling, IRT-4M fuel and an operational power level up to 10 MWt. Reactor operations run in cycles, typically 6-7 per year. Usually the

cycle lasts for 30 days, followed by an outage lasting for approximately 20 days for maintenance and fuel reloading. Demineralised water is used as a moderator and coolant. A reflector is composed of a water, or beryllium block, depending on the operation configuration.

A cross section of LVR—15 reactor is shown in Figure 3 and its typical core in Figure 4.

Figure 3 LVR-15 reactor vessel cross-section.

Figure 4 Typical core layouts with in-fuel irradiation rig in position D7 (left) and CHOUCA rig in position D2 (right).

The general operation parameters are:

- Maximal thermal power: 10 MWth;
- Maximal available thermal neutron flux: $2 \times 10^{14} \text{ n} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$;
- Maximal available fast neutron (> MeV) flux: $6 \times 10^{13} \text{ n} \times \text{cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$;
- Pressure: atmospheric;
- Coolant Temperature: max. 56°C.

During 2020, CVR extended LVR-15 operating licenses which is now without time limit. Reactor operation until at least 2030 is expected and CVR has a plan to operate even beyond.

Irradiation rigs and loop systems

For material radiation degradation studies the reactor operates standard and non-standard irradiation rigs. Single purpose irradiation rigs are designed, produced and tested in-house according to the needs of the irradiation experiment. Irradiation rigs provide irradiation in an inert gas atmosphere He, He/N₂, He/Ar, online temperature monitoring and temperature control. Fluence evaluation is realized during irradiation through computational simulations and after the irradiation by the evaluation of passive neutron fluence monitors. Rigs can be designed to fit into reactor positions with the highest available fast neutron fluxes to provide as highest radiation damage as possible in the shortest time.

For investigation of degradation and corrosion behaviour of structural materials' mechanical properties under irradiation and PWR/VVER water chemistry and thermal-hydraulic conditions, RVS-3 in-pile loop is used. CVR has also long-term experiences with in-pile loop systems under Boiling Water Reactor water chemistry and thermo-hydraulic conditions. Currently there are two out-of-pile loops dedicated for material studies under Gen IV. Reactor conditions – Super Critical Water Loop and High Temperature Helium Loop, with a plan for their future introduction into the LVR-15 core.

MARIA Research Reactor, Poland

MARIA Research Reactor is located 30 km from Warsaw city centre at National Centre for Nuclear Research. It is a multi-purpose pool-type reactor with pressurized fuel channels immersed in the reactor pool. It is a high flux reactor of 30MW nominal power moderated with water and beryllium. Pressurized fuel channels are situated in the open reactor pool in the beryllium matrix enclosed by a lateral reflector made of aluminium canned graphite blocks. Fuel channels are pressurised up to 1.7 MPa at the fuel channel inlet. Three types of fuel are currently used:

- MC-5/485, French production (by Cerca-Areva), with 19.75% enrichment, a dispersion of a uranium silicide alloy powder (U₃Si₂) in Al, and
- MR-6/485, Russian production (by Novosibirsk Chemical Concentrates Plant, TVEL), with 19.70% enrichment, a dispersion of UO₂ in Al,
- MR-2/225.7, Russian production (by Novosibirsk Chemical Concentrates Plant, TVEL), with 19.70% enrichment, a dispersion of UO₂ in Al,

The last one is licensed and tested for the irradiation of material samples in the holder in the fuel central area. In both types the fuel core is clad with aluminium. Each fuel element has a form of six (MR) or five (MC) concentric tubes. The thermal and fast neutron flux density may reach $2.5 \cdot 10^{14}$ n/cm²s and $1 \cdot 10^{14}$ n/cm²s respectively. The

reactor has been designed with a high degree of application flexibility. The reactor core has a modular design and its core configuration is fitted to either production or research purposes.

It is anticipated that MARIA will be able to operate until 2050 after several modernizations take place. One of the current challenges is all the preparatory work to license renewal.

The MARIA Reactor core consists of 28 fuel channels and 13 control rods situated in a beryllium matrix. Number of fuel channels may vary from cycle to cycle, while the number of control rods remain constant. The beryllium matrix is enclosed by graphite blocks forming the reflector. It is also equipped with approx. 26 vertical channels used for irradiation and 8 horizontal channels (7 operational and one still only in conceptual design). The whole core is placed in an aluminum housing, called 'basket', located on a table at the bottom of the reactor pool. Top view of the core is shown in Figure 5. The most common operational power of the reactor varies from 18 to 24 MW depending on the cycle needs.

Figure 5 MARIA Research Reactor top view

Fuel channels are marked in yellow, Rabbit systems in blue, static vertical irradiation channels in green, control rods in orange and red.

The MARIA reactor was designed to operate with several experimental devices in parallel. The most important of them are:

- vertical irradiation channels for radionuclide production;

- reactor test rigs for structural materials, biological samples and reactor fuel studies under stationary conditions ;
- large sample channels for electronic, concrete and another materials irradiation;
- horizontal experimental channels for neutron beam studies.

The reactor construction allows installing various kinds of irradiation facilities and neutron sources.

The following channels are available:

- channels of 23 mm diameter in beryllium blocks;
- channels of 28 mm diameter in the graphite reflector;
- channels of 38 mm diameter in the graphite reflector;
- channels of 46 mm diameter inside the modified fuel element MR-2;
- bulk material irradiation facility for large-size (up to 85 mm in diameter and 900 mm height) target materials
- channels equipped with a hydraulic transport ('rabbit') system located in the beryllium and graphite area of the reactor core.

The customized fuel channel can be used to irradiate the fission materials, like targets or fuels, under strictly controlled conditions. Such technology has been applied for irradiation of uranium targets for ^{99}Mo production. This activity plays a special role in the utilization of the MARIA reactor.

For the very long time MARIA reactor was known for its isotope production activity with some capabilities to irradiate material samples in standard irradiation vehicles. In recent years several thermostatic irradiation rigs were designed and implemented. So far a single use devices were irradiated. The irradiation of functional materials was also performed for EUROfusion.

Budapest Research Reactor (BRR), Hungary

The Budapest Research Reactor is operated by the Centre for Energy Research in Budapest, Hungary. It is a 10 MW nominal power plant operating since 1959 and used both as a cold neutron source (using a liquid Hydrogen cell, for materials studies) and for material irradiation purposes. Its operational license will expire in 2023, but the process of extension for 10 more years is ongoing. Fresh fuel is secured at present for further 6 years to 2029.

Figure 6 Layout and view of Budapest Research Reactor

The reactor has been used for material irradiation studies within the EU fusion program for more than 20 years. 39 different irradiation campaigns were run for structural and functional materials (Eurofer97, W, Ti alloys, CuCrZr, Alumina, Sapphire, Silica, Spinel, YAG, Diamond, BaF, CaF, ZnS and C12A7) and for fusion devices (bolometers, electron source for pressure gauge). Irradiations were done up to about 2 dpa (Fe).

Irradiations were performed in the BAGIRA irradiation rig or in the fast channel of the reactor. The Bagira irradiation rig is inserted in the core of the pool type reactor as the figure shows. BAGIRA can host samples at multiple levels as the figure shows.

Recently, the current assembly of the Bagira rig provides the following possibilities:

- Volume, average and peak neutron fluent :
 - average neutron flux is $7.5 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ n/cm}^2 \text{ sec}$, $E > 1 \text{ MeV}$ ($9 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ dpa/m}^2 \text{ sec}$), slightly affected by the yearly partial refuelling and the level of the outburning of the nearby fuel elements
 - minimum neutron flux is $2 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ n/cm}^2 \text{ sec}$, $E > 1 \text{ MeV}$ at the bottom and top of the axial height of the zone
 - maximum neutron flux is $1.3 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ n/cm}^2 \text{ sec}$, $E > 1 \text{ MeV}$ at the middle of the axial height of the zone
 - Maximum irradiation volume is altogether $6 \cdot 20 \cdot 20 \cdot 55 \text{ mm}^3$, in 6 package
 - The recent rig is in the core of the reactor 624-632-633 position (see Figure 7)
 - PC based temperature control and data acquisition system
 - Electric heating
 - Separated thermocouples on the levels
 - N-He gas mixture for temperature control
 - Irradiation temperature range: 60 – 350°C up to 350 C, temp. accuracy over time $\pm 10^\circ \text{C}$, spatial temperature accuracy $\pm 10^\circ \text{C}$, maximum two relatively near temperature irradiations can be done in one irradiation.
 - Tritium capabilities is not licensed, for demand can be calculated
- The dose is monitored and irradiation environment is calculated by reactor modelling.

Figure 7 Top view of the zone of Budapest Research Reactor

Figure 8 Position of BAGIRA irradiation rig in the zone of Budapest Research Reactor

Additionally to the BAGIRA rig irradiations can be done in the vertical fast channel of the reactor. Here ITER components (bolometers, electron sources) were irradiated to about 0.2 dpa (Fe).

Post Irradiation Investigations are performed in the hot cells and the connected qualified laboratory area: mechanical characterization by tensile, hardness, Charpy fracture toughness tests , microstructure investigation by optical microscopy and SEM.

MYRRHA Reactor, Belgium

MYRRHA research reactor will be built in 80 km from Brussels in the Belgium Nuclear Research Centre.

This section provides a review of the envisaged fusion irradiation facility on the MYRRHA reactor, whose construction is planned at at 2035. The MYRRHA reactor facility is foreseen as a flexible fast-spectrum irradiation facility, to meet the demands of various application requirements pertaining to material irradiation. MYRRHA is an accelerator driven system (ADS), which couples the proton accelerator to a heavy liquid metal spallation source that feeds the subcritical core with fast neutrons. This core is immersed in a pool of liquid lead-bismuth eutectic (LBE), along with the primary pumps and heat exchangers which make up the reactor primary system. MYRRHA is also able to operate in critical mode (without assistance of the proton beam) producing a total power of 70 MW_{th}. The scope of applications within the MYRRHA reactor include the transmutation of high-level nuclear waste, irradiation for nuclear materials and fuel research, and radioisotope production for medical and industrial applications.

In the core of the MYRRHA reactor (Figure 6), provisions are made to include so-called In-Pile Sections (IPS) positioned around the central core or at the central core position below the spallation target when operating in subcritical mode. A top view, cross-section of the sub-critical core layout at Beginning of Cycle (BoC) is shown in Figure 6. This sub-critical BoC configuration includes a total of 163 core positions and consists of:

- a central assembly housing the proton beam tube and the spallation target, with a rig for fusion material irradiation located in the center under the spallation target;
- 78 Fuel Assemblies (FAs) with different levels of burnups;
- 6 IPSs for irradiation rigs requiring fast neutron fluxes;
- 3 Control Rods (CRs);
- 3 IPS for the production of radioisotopes;
- 30 dummy assemblies filled with LBE;
- 42 reflector assemblies with magnesium oxide;
- a stainless steel jacket.

Figure 6. Top view cross-section of the MYRRHA core layout.

Of relevance for this paper, concerning fusion-relevant irradiation conditions, is the central core position housing the spallation target assembly with an irradiation rig for fusion material research. When operating in sub-critical mode, the vertical beam tube

with a hemispherical beam window at the bottom (see Figure 7), brings the source of 600 MeV protons into the centre of the core. The center of the beam window is located 12 cm above the core mid-plane, and due to the spallation process between the protons and the LBE fluid target, a high energy neutron spectrum is generated, providing suitable irradiation conditions for fusion material research.

An irradiation rig, schematics is shown in Figure 8, is placed below the core mid-plane where the high constant flux levels and appm He/dpa ratios are representative for fusion reactor irradiation conditions. The performance target for this rig is a high constant fast flux level resulting in 10 - 15 dpa/EFY (equivalent full power year), and a representative appm He/dpa ratio in the range of 5 - 25. The irradiation rig shown in Figure 8 contains 18 compartments for cylindrical samples with $\text{Ø}=8$ mm, $L=40$ mm (3 samples per compartment), for a total of 54 samples. Application of SSTT allows one to increase the number of samples by a factor of four, up to 200 samples per rig. A calculation of the appm He/dpa ratio for the volume below the beam window, shows that an irradiation volume of approximately 1000 cm^3 is available.

Each core channel, including the central spallation target channel, is cooled by a flow of LBE which enters the core from the bottom of each core channel at a temperature $220 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This LBE at 220°C flows around the sample holder, so irradiation temperatures of at least 220°C can be provided. For higher irradiation temperatures, local heaters as well as nuclear heating with gas gap (capsule-based irradiation) is foreseen. No closed-loop circulation of cooling or heating media is currently foreseen for the samples, but the samples could be immersed in stagnant liquid metal or helium gas, in suitably designed capsules/rigs. The maximum temperature limits will be dependent on the specific design of the irradiation rig, the irradiation at least up to $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is envisaged.

Figure 7. Side view of the spallation target assembly, showing the beam tube and fusion irradiation sample rig

Figure 8. appm He/dpa ratio below the beam window (above) and a horizontal cross-section of the irradiation device sample holder (below)

The MYRRHA reactor will operate during three cycles of 90 days with two short maintenance periods of 30 days in between the cycles. During the 30 days maintenance period, the beam tube is replaced due to irradiation damage to the beam tube window, the experiments are unloaded and loaded back if required, the fuel is reshuffled and minor maintenance activities are performed. No in-cycle loading or unloading of the irradiation rig is foreseen, meaning that the samples can only be removed during the 30 day maintenance cycles. Following the third 90 day cycle, a so-called “long maintenance” period of 90 days is foreseen, dedicated to major maintenance activities including fuel unloading/loading and installation of irradiation experiments. For the irradiation samples mounted in the sample holder shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8, irradiation levels in terms of dpa and helium production (in appm) in iron were calculated for stacks of tensile

samples. For the 120 mm long sample stack compartment – made up by a stack of three 40 mm long samples – the peak and average irradiation damage is reported in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Peak and average radiation damage characteristics in the fusion material rig installed in MYRRHA.

parameter	average	peak	requirement
dpa/year	28	36	10 - 15
appm He/dpa	21	24	5 – 25

Jules Horowitz Reactor

This is test reactor under construction in France whose primary application is qualification of fuel assemblies. The reactor is under construction and planned deployment time is beyond 2034 (likely beyond FP10 timeframe). The design of the reactor provides irradiation locations situated inside the reactor core with the highest ageing rate and irradiation locations situated in the Beryllium reflector zone surrounding the reactor, with the highest thermal flux.

Numerous locations are implemented (up to 20 simultaneous experiments) with a large range of irradiation conditions (Figure 9):

- 7 in-core locations of small diameter for experimental devices up to 33.1 mm diameter (101, 105, 203, 207, 211, 303, 307, 313)
- 3 in-core locations of large diameter (80 mm) for experimental devices up to 86 mm diameter (103, 211, 301)
- 16 fixed reflector locations for experimental devices up to 97 mm diameter (two of them, C311 and C413, will be used for surveillance specimens monitoring irradiation ageing of the JHR vessel material)
- 1 fixed reflector location for an experimental device up to 200 mm diameter (P322)
- 4 displacement devices located in water channels through the Beryllium reflector for experimental devices up to 100 mm diameter (T5, T8, T10, T12)
- 4 additional displacement devices for Moly production (T0 to T3)

During the first years of operation, CEA targets to operate the reactor 180 days per year, 15% at 100 MW and 85% at 70 MW. A mean reactor cycle is expected to last about 34 operating days corresponding to 25 EFPD.

Figure 9 Left: Experimental locations in the JHR core and reflector. Right: Locations of the experimental devices available for the JHR start-up.

The start of operation of the JHR (scheduled to the end of this decade) will happen in two fleets for the experimental capacity. The first fleet will contain five different testing devices: MADISON for normal operation, ADELINE for off-normal operation, OCCITANE for pressure vessel steel experiments and 3 MICA material test capsules for more conventional material testing. In addition, there will be Non-Destructive evaluation techniques available for different purposes.

MADISON (Fuel device)

- Designed to carry out irradiations of LWR fuel samples during which no clad failures are expected. Consequently, the experimental conditions correspond to normal operation of power reactors (steady states or slow transients that can take place in nuclear power plants).

As an example fuel sample instrumentation for a 4 rods irradiation rig:

- For each fuel rod:
 - 1 temperature measurement: fuel temperature or clad temperature
 - + 1 LVDT measurement: fuel clad elongation or fuel plenum pressure

Example of fuel sample instrumentation for a 2 rods irradiation rig

- First fuel rod
 - Fuel stack elongation
 - + 1 LVDT measurement: fuel clad elongation
- Second fuel rod
 - 1 temperature measurement: fuel temperature or clad temperature
 - + 1 fission product measurement (acoustic sensor)
 - + 1 LVDT measurement: fuel plenum pressure
- The first operational irradiation rig will be designed to host 9.5 mm UO₂ fuel rods with 5% ²³⁵U and 60 cm length. Smaller or higher rod diameters (from 7 to 12.5 mm) and higher ²³⁵U content (or MOX fuel) would be manageable but require additional studies.
- PWR conditions (155 bar and 320°C for the inlet temperature).

ADELIN (Fuel device)

- Able to hold a single experimental fuel rod from all LWR technologies to reproduce various experimental irradiation scenarios in which clad failure is either a risk or an experimental objective.
- First version of the ADELIN device is mainly dedicated to power ramp testing. In particular, the design is optimized to provide a qualified thermal balance (with a targeted 5-6% precision) and good accuracy on the clad failure instant and, consequently, a good knowledge of the linear power inducing the failure.
- A typical PWR power ramp sequence is made of the following phases:
 - A low power plateau (from 12 hours up to 7 days) with control of clad surface temperature while the sample linear heat rate is controlled between 100 and 200 W/cm, depending on end-user request;
 - A linear power ramp at a continuous rate ranging between 100 and 700 W.cm⁻¹.min⁻¹;
 - A high power plateau that may last 24 h (performed if the cladding has not failed during the power transient).
- The first irradiation rig is designed to host 9.5 mm UO₂ fuel rods with 5% ²³⁵U and 50 cm length. Smaller or higher rod diameters (from 7 to 12.5 mm), higher length (up to 60 cm) and higher ²³⁵U content (or MOX fuel) would be manageable but require additional studies.
- For a reactor power of 100 MW, the limit for the power at maximum flux plane is the thermal-hydraulic limit of 620 W/cm whatever the burn-up (0 to 120 GWd/t).

MICA (Material device)

- Designed to irradiate structural materials in the core of the JHR, within a fuel element. Its typical temperature range is between 280 and of 450°C for the samples. Seven different locations are available for MICA devices: two in the first ring, two in the second ring and three in the third ring of the JHR core.
- The experimental samples are loaded in a sample holder at the centre of the MICA test device. The available space in the MICA is limited by the internal stainless steel tube of diameter 24 mm. The sample holder is immersed in liquid metal (Na-K eutectic) which ensures optimal thermal homogeneity with its high thermal conductivity.
- Nuclear heating in the JHR core transfers energy to the MICA and thus to the experimental load, which is foreseen to be between 15 and 35 kW depending on the reactor power, the location of the MICA in the JHR core and the experimental load in the MICA. Additional energy is provided by heating elements embedded in a sprayed aluminium coating around the internal stainless steel tube.
- Several thermocouples and dosimeters can be integrated to the sample holder to monitor temperature and neutron fluence at different locations.

OCCITANE (Material device)

- In the field of pressure vessel steels of NPPs, irradiations are carried out to justify the safety of this second containment barrier and to improve its lifetime and consequently the lifetime of the reactor itself.
- CEA is designing a hosting system named OCCITANE (Out-of-Core Capsule for Irradiation Testing of Ageing by Neutrons), which allows irradiations in an inert gas at least from 230 to 300°C.
- OCCITANE will be located in P611 in the first ring of JHR reflector. The neutron characteristics will be as follows (best-estimate values at maximum flux plane, 100 MW, 27% ²³⁵U, core at equilibrium in mid cycle):
 - Fast flux (E > 1 MeV): about $8 \cdot 10^{12}$ n/cm².s
 - Fast flux (E > 0.1 MeV): about $2 \cdot 10^{13}$ n/cm².s
 - mdpa/EFPD: 1.0
- Neutron fluxes and dpa should be multiplied by 0.7 for a reactor power of 70 MW.
- The neutron spectrum ratio $R_s = \Phi(E > 0.1 \text{ MeV}) / \Phi(E > 1 \text{ MeV})$ and the nuclear heating in the samples can be adapted with neutron and gamma shields.
- Various kind of samples (creep, tensile, Charpy and microstructure) can be irradiated if their size does not exceed 30 x 62.5 mm². Samples can be stacked on top of each other on to 60 cm height with a damage axial gradient due to the variations of the fast neutron flux. Between each cycle, the sample holder is rotated 180° in the device in order to homogenise damage in the experimental samples.
- The multi-zone furnace controls the required irradiation temperature between 230 and 300°C and compensates the axial thermal gradient due to the above-mentioned axial nuclear gradients.
- The associated instrumentation includes at least thermocouples and dosimeters as close as possible to the samples.

Institute Laue-Langevin reactor

The Institut Laue–Langevin (ILL) is an internationally financed scientific facility, situated on the Polygone Scientifique in Grenoble, France. It is one of the world centres for research using neutrons. Founded in 1967 and honouring the physicists Max von Laue and Paul Langevin, the ILL provides one of the most intense neutron sources in the world and the most intense continuous neutron flux in the world in the moderator region: 1.5×10^{15} n/cm²/sec, with a thermal power of typically 58.3 MW.

The ILL reactor has not been actively used in the conventional material/fuel irradiation programmes for fusion or fission, instead it is applied as source of neutrons for analysis. The ILL neutron scattering facilities allow the analysis of the structure of conducting and magnetic materials for future electronic devices, the measurement of stresses in mechanical materials. It also allows

investigations into macromolecular assemblies, particularly protein dynamics and biomolecular structure. It is a world-renowned centre for nanoscale science. Hence, its inclusion in the summary table is currently irrelevant.

Hoger Onderwijs Reactor University of Delft

In the Netherlands, the Reactor Institute Delft (RID) is the academic center for radiation-related research and education. The institute's research reactor, the Hoger Onderwijs Reactor (HOR) is a light water reactor of the pool type with a thermal power of 2 MW. Construction of the HOR successfully completed in 1963. The reactor is currently operated around the clock, 5 days/week, 45 weeks per year at a thermal power level of 2 MW, with an average thermal flux of about 2×10^{13} n/cm²/s. For the HOR reactor core nuclear fuel elements of the MTR type are used. The reactor is used as a source of neutrons, positrons, gamma rays and radioisotopes. The reactor is mostly used as source of neutrons and large scale material test programmes (for high fluence irradiation) have never been executed due to the relatively low flux. Given that this reactor was not used in the past (and not planned for) for the dedicated fusion irradiation campaigns it is not included in the table.

Report Annex 4.2

Characterization of Spallation Sources

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Date: 2026-06-26

Executive Summary

Spallation sources are generally conceived for producing beams of thermal or cold neutrons for neutron scattering studies. These beams are produced by slowing down the high-energy neutrons from the spallation source, therefore some facilities might be used for material irradiation studies using the high-energy neutrons which are present close to the source. Most of the spallation sources operate in pulsed mode, which means that even if the peak neutron flux is high compared to a research reactor, the average might be lower. For irradiation studies the cumulative neutron fluent is the most important, therefore the average should be considered.

SINQ

The SINQ neutron source, located in Switzerland at the Paul Scherrer Institute, is based on a proton beam and solid target. It is designed for neutron scattering experiments but offers some facilities for neutron irradiation as well [1]. Thermal neutron fluence around 10^{12} - 10^{13} $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ is available in limited volumes. SINQ operates quasi-continuous, therefore it is somewhat special among the spallation sources. For the irradiation locations the samples are moved into the device with a rabbit system. The highest flux location is PNA, mostly used for medical isotope production. Availability for fusion material studies has to be checked.

SINQ also conducted extensive experiments on a large selection of materials, including ferritic steels by directly hitting the specimens with the proton beam [2]. The damage reached was up to 27 dpa, but the irradiation was done with a mixture of 500 MeV protons and neutrons.

European Spallation Source (ESS)

The ESS is under construction in Lund, Sweden. It will use a 2 GeV linear proton accelerator, operating in pulses at 14 Hz with about 4% fill factor. In the first year the beam energy will be only 0.57 MeV. The main use of neutrons from the W target is for neutron scattering after slowing them down in moderators.

ESS is planned to be equipped with a neutron irradiation module [3] in which material samples can be irradiated in the pre-moderator. The present setup is considered as a proof of principle device with no temperature control and passive cooling with the aim of providing materials damage data for ESS itself. The samples will be embedded in water. The volume is 20 cm x 4 cm x 0.5 cm. A neutronic study [4] indicated that at 5MW beam power the neutron energy is up to 2 GeV with an integrated fast neutron flux (in the 0.1 MeV and 2 GeV energy range) of 10^{15} $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. (See comparison of various neutron spectra in Figure 1.) The energy spectrum has a tail well above the one in a fusion environment, therefore applicability would need some consideration. However, it is interesting to note that the dpa damage is expected to be up to 12 dpa per year and the He production similar to fusion conditions [3]. This might make the test more relevant than fission reactor studies. These calculations assume ESS design parameters, 5MW 2 GeV proton beam energy. For the first operation year only 0.5 GeV proton energy will be used, resulting in about 1 dpa/year.

The ESS irradiation module has already been assembled and waiting for first operation of the accelerator in 2027. Irradiation on fusion materials is also foreseen.

ISIS

ISIS is a spallation source based on a 800 MeV proton beam hitting W targets. It is located in the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory, Oxfordshire, UK. The operation frequency is 50 Hz with 200 microsecond pulse length. Two W target stations generate neutrons and muons for the experiments. Due to the short pulse length the device is not suitable for irradiation damage studies and no such application is mentioned.

MYRRHA using 100 MeV proton beam on spallation target

In such a setup the 100 MeV proton beam is directed on a high Z material such as tungsten or tantalum without moderation. Figure 1 shows a comparison between various neutron sources, namely: material test reactor BR2 (fuel channel with a total flux 10^{15} n/cm²/s, which is similar to any other high flux fission material test reactor facility such as HFR, HFIR or SM2) [5], DEMO first wall and IFMIF High-Flux Test Module (HFTM). The DEMO fusion reactor spectrum has a clear peak at 14 MeV [6]. This illustrates that the fission mixed spectrum reactor experiment allows one to assess damage mechanisms occurring mainly in the middle-low energy ranges, with a very low fraction of neutrons with energy exceeding 10 MeV. The future IFMIF irradiation source specially designed for fusion irradiation shows spectra with a broad peak at 15-20 MeV with an energy tail till 50 MeV [6]. At this, it is important to note that the 100 MeV spallation source has an energy tail only up to 100 MeV which is a clear benefit compared to other neutron spallation sources which have energy tail up to few GeV.

Figure 1. Comparison of neutron spectra of the 100 MeV tungsten spallation source and other relevant neutron sources (for the spallation source 100mA/m² is assumed to be a safe starting point to operate. Nevertheless it is believed that this current density can be increased significant (4x)).

Static neutron converter cooled with water can reach a current density of about 100 mA/m² which yields in about 0.4 dpa / 200 days in Steel at fusion relevant transmutation rates (detailed analysis is provided further). Under the spallation irradiation conditions, the available irradiation area would be 400 cm² at 4 mA operational current. The steel samples would have a reduction of 50 % in dpa at 15 mm thickness and this gradient can be alleviated by sequential radiation at both sides, which then makes possible the application of standardized samples or usage of a stack of miniaturized samples (to achieve several irradiation doses in a single run). In total, it would offer a volume of ~2 Liters.

Possible types of experiments: non-instrumented capsule-based irradiation; instrumented experiments in gas/vacuum/liquid metal environment; instrumented experiments enabling

thermal or mechanical fatigue (such as proposed by FUSERO design); experiments involving irradiation of tritium breeding materials (40 TBq of tritium limit).

The expected deployment time is 2027.

The reference for the provided information is: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fusengdes.2023.113764>.

Compact neutron sources

Smaller accelerator-driven neutron sources are also planned or being built, an exhaustive summary of the technology can be found in [7]. The achievable neutron rate and energy depends on the technology, but the highest neutron production rate is considered to be about 10^{14} - 10^{15} n/s. From this the flux would be presumably not more than 10^{11} - 10^{12} $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at most, therefore does not seem to be directly relevant for TBM development.

Summary

From the European spallation sources ESS and SINQ seems to be relevant for TBM studies. Their key parameters are listed in the table below and compared to DONES. ESS appears to be the most relevant, but it is not designed for irradiations studies and the neutron energy is well above the one encountered in fusion.

Device	Neutron flux [$\text{cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$]	Neutron spectrum	Expected availability	Comment
SINQ	CW, 10^{12} - 10^{13}	Thermal	Today	Small volume, rabbit system. Higher dose rate with mixed p and n dose can be available
ESS	Pulsed, 4% fill factor, 10^{15}	< 2 GeV	2027 (low flux), 2029	Water cooling
MYRRHA	CW, 10^{14}	< 20 MeV	2027	Gas/water/liquid metal environment
DONES (for comparison)	CW 10^{14}	< 50 MeV	?	

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Report Annex 4.3

Characterization of p/d Accelerator-based Neutron Sources

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Executive Summary

The document provides an assessment regarding light-particle accelerator-based neutron source facilities in view of a testing & qualification strategy for the Breeding Blanket of DEMO. Key technical data are summarized: neutron spectrum and flux values, irradiation damage parameters, irradiation sample volume, and time to availability.

The concept of compact accelerator-driven neutron sources (CANS) features a convenient and scalable combination of established medium-energy LINAC and efficient neutron production from metallic targets at moderate power handling demands. A dedicated CANS for nuclear qualification tests for fusion breeder blanket technologies, featuring suitably high neutron fluxes for relevant damage, gas and tritium accumulation, is currently missing. A provisional study indicates that with ca. 300 kW beam power irradiation volumes of 0.5 liter could be utilized at neutron fluxes of few 10^{13} n/cm²/s offering 0.4 dpa/fpy in the sample volume. Scalability of the beam line and optimization of target materials and reflector assembly provides prospects of roughly one order of magnitude higher neutron exposure at moderate extrapolation. The concept of low-energy deuteron beams on tritiated metallic targets for D-T fusion neutron sources (14-MeV neutron generators) can be extended to high power concepts based on dual beam implantation on rotating wheel targets. At 4 MW incident power similar neutron irradiation performances as with the medium-sized CANS can be achieved with a genuine 14 MeV neutron source.

Motivation

Concerning the prospects of dedicated neutron irradiation facilities, the key requirements to be addressed in view of nuclear qualification of breeding blankets are:

- Representativeness of the neutron spectrum at target vs DT 14-MeV neutron spectra of in-vessel conditions of a DEMO/FPP.
- Achievable neutron fluences and typical neutron irradiation accumulated responses.
- Potentially the capability of accelerated irradiation (e.g. life-time DT damage fluence during less time).
- Target volume of suitable fluence accumulation with sufficiently low gradient flux (and damage response) distributions.
- Operational control of neutron source emission and target conditions (in particular, temperature control).

Benefits of Compact Accelerator-Based Neutron Sources

Whereas IFMIF-DONES is aiming at qualification and irradiation data for structural materials under high-dpa (typically FW) and suitable helium to dpa production rate conditions, alternative concepts gained renewed interest concentrating on the feasibility of fusion neutron sources for component testing in contrast to material sample testing in IFMIF and spallation sources. The concept of compact accelerator-driven neutron sources (CANS) utilizes low to medium energy light particle (p,d up to 50...100 MeV) and high current (up to potentially several tens of mA CW) beams on suitable targets for efficient neutron production.

Typically, neutron yields per incident ion are a few percent strongly increasing with energy and slightly increasing with target nuclei mass. This is significantly different to spallation neutron sources with typically tens of neutrons per incident ion. As a typical example serve the case of a 30 MeV, 10 mA proton beam on a beryllium target. The neutron yield is roughly $1.7 \times 10^{15}/s$ delivering a broad spectrum up to ca. 30 MeV. The neutron flux at target is up to $10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ with typical surface area of 100 cm^2 .

Advantageous characteristics of light ion linear accelerators in favour of competitive concepts are:

- Compact accelerator line with reduced costs and moderate shielding demands.
- High beam current with low beam loss.
- Efficient and simple neutron production pathways using metallic targets.
- Flexibility on ion source utilization, variable pulse structure and CW operation and energy tuning. Scalable concept.

Figure 1 Neutron yield for Li, Be, and Ta as a function of the primary ion energy, [3].

DT-neutron generators

Utilizing the proven technology of existing DT-neutron generators to obtain genuine 14-MeV neutrons is the driver for upgrades in terms of achievable neutron source strengths and irradiation parameters. Based on ion source and accelerator technology used in NBI systems. The low relative neutron yield from deuterium beams at few hundreds of keV can then be compensated by high current ion implantation on a suitably designed and cooled metallic target.

Attractive features of such low-energy DT-neutron sources are:

- Proven ion source/accelerator technology with moderate shielding demands.
- Genuine 14-MeV neutron source.
- Option of single ion source for mixed d/t-implantation. Neutron yield independent of secondary species.

Design considerations for nuclear qualification testing

Neutron production from p/d-LINACs in the relevant ion energy range provide a white neutron spectrum with average energy in the few MeV range. The fast neutron spectra can simulate the integral responses in terms of damage and charged particle production rates of a DT fusion neutron environment. Tailoring can be achieved by modification of the beam energy (at the same time tuning the neutron yield) and suitable design of the target assembly with moderator (if required) and reflector.

To optimize the neutron yield and eventually the irradiating neutron flux at sample position, the choice of beam ions and energy and the target material is essential. Generally, the neutron yield scales approximately linearly above some energy far from the threshold value. Using deuterium accelerators offers roughly a factor 2-4 in terms of neutron yield in the envisaged energy range. Below ca. 30 MeV beam energy the neutron production from light targets e.g. Be, Li) is favorable which reverses at higher energies (e.g. V, Ta).

Figure 2 Neutron flux spectra in a 30 MeV p-Be accelerator vs. IFMIF-DONES High Flux Test Module

The CW beam power is deposited on the target assembly; at 30 MeV and 10 mA this amounts to 300 kW. Moreover, the charged particle deposition has to be considered for mechanical stability (avoiding blistering). Accordingly, the thermomechanical design of the target assembly is challenging considering other requirements such as machining, corrosion resistance, activation characteristics and costs.

Existing and projected compact accelerator-based and DT neutron sources

The development of CANS facilities and projected designs has been driven by the perceived needs on availability of neutron scattering facilities for a variety of applications in nuclear and material science, engineering and medical therapy and radioisotope production. Irradiation testing is part of the portfolio accessible by such CANS devices, however, most of the facilities are aiming at high brilliance neutron sources with variable pulse structures and rather limited duty cycles. Applications in radioisotope production, neutron capture therapy and others are focusing, on the contrary, to CW and high current operations.

Some selected CANS are listed in the following table with key parameters (to be amended in future updates). It also includes few selected projects of DT-neutron generators.

CANS	Status	Beam performance	Neutron performance	Applications
CPHS, Beijing	In operation	13 MeV p, 50 mA (peak), 1.25 mA (av.), 2.5 % duty cycle	5×10^{13} n/s	Imaging, SANS, detector R&D
HUNS, Hokkaido	In operation	35 MeV e, 30 μ A	1.6×10^{12} n/s	Radiation effects, imaging, SANS, ...
KUANA, Kyoto	In operation	3.5 MeV p, 10 mA (peak)	1×10^{11} n/s	
RANS, Riken	In operation	7 MeV p, 10 mA (peak), 100 μ A (av.)	1×10^{12} n/s	Imaging, industrial applications
ESS-Bilbao	Projected	50 MeV p, 2.25 mA (av), 115 kW, 3 % duty cycle	1×10^{15} n/s	SANS, moderator testing
LENOS, Legnaro	Projected	5 MeV, 50 mA CW	Up to 1×10^{15} n/s	Nuclear astrophysics, nuclear data etc.
NOVA-ERA, Jülich	Design Study	10 MeV p, 1 mA (peak), 4 % duty cycle, 400 W	3×10^{13} n/s Up to 1×10 n/cm ² /s	Multipurpose
HBS, Jülich	Projected	50 MeV p, 100 mA (peak), 100 kW, 4.3 % duty cycle	1×10^{17} n/s (burst), 4.3×10^{15} n/s (av.)	Multipurpose
SONATE, Saclay	Projected	20 MeV, 100 mA (peak), 2-4 % duty cycle	Up to 5×10^8 n/cm ² /s (thermal)	Material science studies
SORGENTINA-RF	In construction	250 keV d/t, 466 mA (per beam)	Up to 7×10^{13} n/s	Medical isotope production
SORGENTINA-BMT	Projected	300 keV d/t, 7 A (per beam)	Ca. 4×10^{15} n/s, ca. 3×10^{13} n/cm ² /s	Fusion material research

It can be observed from this limited survey, that current and projected CANS are providing broad neutron scattering options at competitive neutron brilliance conditions. Only few CANS provide CW accelerators, albeit at limited power. A dedicated CANS for nuclear qualification tests for fusion breeder blanket technologies, featuring suitably high neutron fluxes for relevant damage, gas and tritium accumulation, is missing. The effective neutron energy spectra from carefully designed target-moderator-reflector assemblies are expected to be representative for DT fusion neutron spectra in terms of relevant damage parameters. Such a CANS may be designed to operate with separate targets for long-term irradiations as well as short-term studies including neutron imaging instruments.

Provisional key parameters for a dedicated high-power DT-neutron generator

A schematic layout of a DT-neutron generator based on a rotating target (SORGENTINA-BMT, Blanket Module Test; see also Ref. [7]) is shown in below picture. It features 300 keV beams of d/t with ca 7 A per beam hitting a rotating target wheel covered by a thin titanium deposition layer. The concept is based on the original SORGENTINA design developed in ENEA since the 1990's (R. Martone et al.). The D-T reactions on the implanted Ti surface generate 14 MeV

neutrons at a rate of 10^{15} n/s in order to utilize irradiation volumes with a flux of more than 10^{13} n/cm²/s.

Figure 3 Schematic layout of NSFS target station.

Neutron spectra and flux

Neutron flux values on the high flux irradiation region above the beams' deposition area have been estimated as ca. 3×10^{13} cm⁻²s⁻¹ (within 500 cm³). Other variants of the target design, featuring two rotating targets, indicate that flux gradients should be restricted to enable even larger sample volumes.

Irradiation sample volume

As shown above, an effective irradiation volume of 500 cm³ at roughly 1 dpa/fpy (estimated from the quoted neutron flux) can be envisaged. Even larger volumes seem to be feasibly at somewhat reduced performance.

Time to availability

A low-power (250 kW) version of this concept, SORAGENTINA-RF, is under design and testing at ENEA Brasimone. A tritium supply of up to 5.6 g/day is considered with a recirculation system in the facility. It is expected from experience gained in this project, that a high-power facility could be operational within 5 years after project approval.

Provisional key parameters for a dedicated CANS

A schematic layout of a pre-conceptual CANS with a simplified target/reflector assembly is shown in the below picture. For initial scoping and to derive the key technical parameters relevant for the assessment of such a facility the following assumptions are considered (see also in the section above):

- 30 MeV proton (or deuteron) beam, 10 mA CW, 5 cm diameter circular profile
- Water-cooled Be target, 0.6 cm thickness.
- Roughly 10 cm thick reflector assembly
- Dedicated sample volume of 125 cm³

The irradiation volume is not limited to this initial study. It is assumed that a HCPB-like material mixture is located in that volume.

Figure 4 Schematic layout of p/d-LINAC based CANS with fast neutron target/reflector assembly.

Neutron spectra and flux

The Be target provides a neutron yield of 2.25 % per incident proton or 5.5 % per incident deuteron at 30 MeV. Accordingly, a 10 mA beam would yield ca. 3.6×10^{15} n/s or 7.2×10^{15} n/s for proton or deuteron beam, resp. In the case of proton beam with a beam footprint area of roughly 20 cm^2 the resulting neutron flux averaged across the Be target is ca. $7.7 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, and within the sample volume it amounts to ca. $1.3 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. For a deuteron beamline the average sample neutron flux would reach $4.4 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$.

The neutron flux spectra at target, behind target and at sample are shown in *Figure 2*.

Irradiation damage parameters

In this simplified configuration various nuclear response have been calculated to obtain irradiation damage related parameters. They are listed in the following table; all refer to response in EUROFER except tritium production which has been calculated for the assumed HCPB material mixture.

Sample integral/average	p-Be, 30 MeV	d-Be, 30 MeV
DPA [dpa/fpy]	0.38	1.70
He [appm]	6.48	28.89
H [appm]	19.0	100.0
He appm to DPA	16.9	17.0
H appm to DPA	49.7	59.0
T [at/s]	2.87E13	6.95E13
T ₂ [mg/fpy]	4.4	10.6

The spatial distribution of neutron flux and damage dose rate shown in the following figures provides some rough illustration of the variability of potential irradiation volumes.

Figure 5 Neutron flux map (left), $n/cm^2/s$, and dpa in EUROFER map (right), dpa/fpy (p-Be, 30 MeV, 10 mA).

Irradiation sample volume

Effective sample volumes may extend to lower neutron flux (damage) areas and could be optimized with suitable reflector configurations. The current study (p-Be, 30 MeV, 10 mA) suggests that typical volumes affected by significant neutron flux above $1 \times 10^{13} n/cm^2/s$ could be in the range of several hundreds of cm^3 .

Scoping calculations for sample volumes of $600 cm^3$ with p/d-beams at 30/50 MeV indicate a feasible range of 0.3 to 3.4 dpa/fpy and average neutron fluxes between 1×10^{13} and $9 \times 10^{13} n/cm^2/s$.

Time to availability

The expected construction and instrumentation costs of such a pre-conceptual (proton-based) CANS are envisaged between 50 to 100 M€. Similarly, a design/construction phase up to initial operation should encompass 4-5 years.

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Report Annex 4.4

Characterization of IFMIF-DONES

Author: David Rapisarda

Date: 21/May/2023

Executive Summary

The reactions in the DONES lithium target will produce an intense high-energy fusion-like neutron flux, which will allow the development of different fusion-related experiments including the irradiation of specimens installed immediately behind the target. These specimens will be arranged in steel structures named Test Modules that will allow precise control of different temperatures in the samples. Both the target and the modules will be located inside a concrete shielded cell named the Test Cell, which will be a highly activated area, with a controlled atmosphere. The high-flux test module (HFTM) will be devoted to structural materials irradiation [1]. Samples installed in HFTM can receive up to 50 dpa/fpy without removal. In addition to the HFTM, IFMIF already considered experiments related to the qualification of the breeding blankets. Those experiments were included in the medium flux area of the Test Cell: the Liquid Breeder Validation Module [2] and the Tritium Release Test Module [3].

Characterization of IFMIF-DONES

CHANGES FROM PREVIOUS EDITION

First version

AUTHOR:	REVISED:	APPROVED:
D. Rapisarda	F. Martin-Fuertes J. Molla F. Mota	David Rapisarda

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1 INTRODUCTION

The reactions in the DONES lithium target will produce an intense high-energy fusion-like neutron flux, which will allow the development of different fusion-related experiments including the irradiation of specimens installed immediately behind the target. These specimens will be arranged in steel structures named Test Modules that will allow precise control of different temperatures in the samples. Both the target and the modules will be located inside a concrete shielded cell named the Test Cell, which will be a highly activated area, with a controlled atmosphere. The high-flux test module (HFTM) will be devoted to structural materials irradiation [1]. Samples installed in HFTM can receive up to 50 dpa/fpy without removal.

Starting from March 2023, the facility takes 10-11 years to build. This means that experiments will approximately start in 2033. However, dedicated experiments could be foreseen during the commissioning phase of DONES. That is 2030-2031, approx.

2 GENERAL COMMENTS

It is important to note that the IFMIF-DONES engineering design has been developed to maximize flexibility: beam shape from 200 x 50 to 100 x 50 mm -with impact on the spatial distribution of neutron flux-, beam energy from 30 MeV to 40 MeV, irradiation modules capabilities, additional irradiation areas... In addition, it easily allows the implementation of possible upgrades (i.e. samples reloading capabilities -to release the 50 dpa limit-, upgrade to a second accelerator -implying a factor two higher neutron flux-, ...)

- An important advantage of DONES is that, at this stage, there is room for designing new experiments.
- The estimated tritium production in breeding experiments is around one order of magnitude lower than that produced in the target itself (dominated by lithium activation by deuterons). Therefore, from the safety point of view of the installation, it is not a killing factor and can be easily managed.
- There is an adjacent room to the Test Cell called the 'Tritium Room'. In this space, tritium-related experiments (such as tritium extraction from purge gas) can be implemented. Specific interfaces have to be identified, but it is something that depends on the definition of the experiment.
- The functionality of the experiments to be carried out should be added to the list of parameters of each neutron source.
- IFMIF already considered experiments related to the qualification of the breeding blankets. Those experiments were included in the medium flux area of the Test Cell: the Liquid Breeder Validation Module [2] and the Tritium Release Test Module [3]. Later on, an additional "catalog" of up to 20 different possible irradiation modules has also been developed, including integral validation of Breeding Blankets unit cells. These experiments are just in a conceptual phase and the design is not available yet.

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3 RELEVANT PARAMETERS IN DONES FOR BB QUALIFICATION

3.1 Availability

The availability of DONES is determined by the periodic maintenance of the target assembly, which is currently set at approximately 1 year (345 days of irradiation, 20 of maintenance). During the irradiation period there is no access to the Test Cell, therefore any experiment has to be designed according to that time window. This should not be a limit taking into account that the validation experiments should be able to reach EOL (End Of Life) targets.

3.2 Available volume

The available volume in DONES is huge and represents an important benefit since, as mentioned before, there is a large margin to propose new experiments. Approximate measures: 1.37 m in the direction of the beam (x-axis), excluding the High Flux Test Module; 1.5 m in the horizontal direction (z-axis); 4 m in the vertical direction (y-axis).

Figure 1.- Test Cell main dimensions in the x-z plane

3.3 Effective volume

The effective irradiation volume can be defined as the volume where the experiments will be relevant (in some way) for the qualification of the BB. This means that the effective volume could be most of the available volume, what is important is to define specific experiments. Otherwise, it is quite difficult to specify an effective irradiation volume: as in any other neutron source, depending on the used materials and components, the irradiation field could be modified.

First of all, it is worth noting that the priority of DONES is the HFTM, which should be “in place” independently of any additional experiment. However and if needed, BB experiments could be developed by removing the HFTM. But it is also important to mention that the values in the HFTM (neutron flux, dpa, spectrum...)

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correspond to those expected at the FW of DEMO. This means that experiments behind the HFTM can be, without any doubt, representative of the breeder zone (BZ) in DEMO. In that sense, in the direction of the beam, the effective length can be practically considered as 1 m.

For the vertical and horizontal directions, the gradients have to be carefully considered. The footprint in DONES is an area of 20 x 5 cm² with a low gradient and where most of the flux is concentrated. It opens along the x-axis so, at the backwall of the HFTM, it covers a larger area of about 40 x 30 cm² with a mean flux higher than 2x10¹³ n/cm²/s (Figure 4, right).

One could define a figure of merit related to a reduction in an important value, i.e. the dpa. According to Figure 6, if we assume a decrease of one order of magnitude in dpa, the effective volume would be 1 m in the vertical direction; 1 m in the horizontal direction; almost 1.3 m in the x-axis. Approximately 1 m³.

Again, this volume is tentative and will depend on the final experiment to be performed (e.g. the use of reflectors in the upper/lower regions of the gradients could help to increase and homogenize the values).

3.4 Neutron Spectrum and fluence rate

In the case of the neutrons, DONES offers a spectrum dominated by high-energy neutrons, with 80% higher than 1 MeV. Behind the HFTM the neutron spectrum is thermalized, as in the case of the breeder zone in DEMO. In this case, approximately 70% of neutrons have an energy higher than 1 MeV, Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the neutron spectrum just behind the HFTM (solid black line) compared with the spectra for different concepts of BB at the breeding zone [4]. Note that the DONES spectrum can be modified with the addition of reflectors or diffusers. In the case of adding a second accelerator to the facility, the spectrum will be multiplied by two.

Concerning the fluence rate, behind the HFTM it varies from 10¹³ to 10¹² n/cm²/s (Figure 4). This last value is very homogeneous in all directions, but it will depend on the experiment (materials) that will be included.

Figure 2.- Neutron spectrum behind the HFTM [Courtesy F. Mota, CIEMAT, May 2023].

Figure 3.- Neutron spectra in the breeder zone [4] compared to the neutron spectrum in DONES (black line) behind the HFTM [Courtesy Y. Qiu, KIT, May 2023].

Figure 4.- Neutron Fluence Rate [n/cm²s] in the Test Cell [5] and footprint just after the HFTM [Courtesy Y. Qiu, KIT, May 2023]

3.5 Gamma field

An intense gamma flux will be present at the Test Cell, which is mainly induced by neutron activation in the HFTM (secondary gammas). 10-15% of the gamma rays are directly generated in the lithium target (primary gammas). Figure 5 shows the photons flux in the Test Cell (left) and the spatial distribution along the beam direction (right), indicated by a white line that crosses the Test Cell in the central part.

Figure 5.- Photon flux ($p/cm^2/s$) in the Test Cell calculated with MCUNED [6]

3.6 Displacement per atom

According to Figure 6, the dpa mean value in the effective volume in the back of the HFTM is around 0.3 dpa/fpy. Maximum 0.5 and minimum 0.05 dpa/fpy. These values have been calculated in iron, again it is necessary to define specific experiments.

Figure 6.- Equivalent dpa/fpy in IRON [5] in the back of the HFTM

3.7 Helium production

Figure 7 shows the production of gases in the HFTM for different beam sizes. As can be seen, the neutrons' energy and flux are reduced when passing through one test module, in this case, the HFTM. According to Figure 8, the helium production in the effective volume in the back of the HFTM is between 0.5 and 5 appm/fpy.

Figure 7.- Gas-DPA ratios in the horizontal cut-plane (left) and the vertical cut-plane (right) [7] in the HFTM region

Figure 8.- Helium production from SS316L (appm/fpy) [5] in the back of the HFTM

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3.8 Tritium production

This value has to be carefully calculated, but previous results for the LBVM considered a production of about 10^{17} atoms/cm²/s [8]. This value depends on the experimental configuration and can be optimized.

3.9 Temperature gradients

The temperature is another parameter that highly depends on the definition of the experiments and the engineering design of the irradiation module. Taking as a reference past IFMIF-DONES activities, the temperature in the modules varied in the range between 250°C - 650°C in the high-flux area [1], and available conceptual designs allow temperature control from 300°C - 900°C in the medium-flux area [2].

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Report Annex 4.5

Preliminary Considerations on a European Volumetric Neutron Source (VNS)

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Date: 27/06/2023

Executive Summary

Recently, the EUROfusion Design Central Team (DCT) has informally commenced an exercise to explore the feasibility of a Volumetric Neutron Source (VNS) for the development and testing of Breeding Blanket (BB) systems to be considered for DEMO.

The primary objective of the initial stage of this exercise is to focus on (1) the exploration of the technical characteristics (physics and engineering), (2) the identification any potential showstopper and (3) the definition of a sound testing strategy.

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
BB	<i>Breeding Blanket</i>
DCT	<i>Design Central Team</i>
FW	<i>First-Wall</i>
NBI	<i>Neutral Beam Injector</i>
NWL	<i>Neutron Wall Load</i>
VNS	<i>Volumetric Neutron Source</i>

1 Introduction

Recently, the EUROfusion Design Central Team (DCT) has informally commenced an exercise to explore the feasibility of a Volumetric Neutron Source (VNS) for the development and testing of Breeding Blanket (BB) systems to be considered for DEMO. This was recognised already 30 years ago [1] to be an attractive option that could reduce the remaining technical gaps and regulatory risks associated with the performance and reliability of one of the most critical components of DEMO and future power plant. The rationale for this facility is described in Ref. [2]. The primary objective of the initial stage of this exercise is to focus on (1) the exploration of the technical characteristics (physics and engineering), (2) the identification any potential showstopper and (3) the definition of a sound testing strategy.

The subsequent paragraphs offer preliminary insights into a possible European VNS.

2 Project Goal Statement

Herewith, project goal statements are reported:

- Motivation**
- Reduce the technical and regulatory risks and uncertainties associated with the demonstration of power extraction and tritium breeding technologies essential for DEMO and future fusion power plant.
 - Contribute to increase the TRL of the breeding blanket systems for DEMO that even with a full ITER TBM testing program would remain low.
- Purpose**
- Conduct irradiation tests aiming at (1) establishing acceptable blanket performance in particular with regard to effectiveness of the tritium breeding and extraction function; (2) exploring coupled phenomena and unexpected synergistic effects in a fusion environment; (3) correcting potential design/ material choice faults; and (4) identifying early life failure mode and rates. Collect additional useful and guiding information on safety, licensing and waste legacy of the plant and its components whose design and technology shall be relevant for DEMO with moderate extrapolations only.

- In particular, for the qualification of components, some m² of plasma-facing wall surface shall be exposed to a typical fusion neutron wall load of order ~0.5 MW/m² in combination with plasma radiation fluxes and a lifetime neutron fluence of ~30 dpa (tbc).

- Concept**
- Small (2-3 m in case of a tokamak) low power (< 50 MW) DT fusion device generating a high 14 MeV neutron flux by beam-target interactions; not relying on high plasma confinement ($Q \leq 1$).
 - Low tritium consumption and no requirement for tritium breeding self-sufficiency or electricity production.
 - Effective in-vessel remote replacement schemes shall allow for staged component testing and simultaneous testing of different breeding blanket concepts.
 - Built and operated in parallel to ITER and the DEMO design process.

- Operation concept**
- Commissioning phase (non-nuclear).
 - Pre-qualification phase: Plasma operation up to a moderate neutron fluence level interrupted by maintenance periods.
 - High fluence qualification phase: Plasma operation up to a high neutron fluence level interrupted by maintenance periods.

- Cost**
- Construction: to be developed together with conceptual design studies
 - Operation: to be developed together with conceptual design studies

- Time to completion**
- to be developed together with conceptual design studies

- Site**
- nuclear licensing depending on site selection

- Supply**
- Tritium supply: in the order of 2 kg / full power year (tbc)
 - Power supply: $\leq \sim 200$ MW (tbc)
 - Tritium start-up inventory (in the order of 500 g)

3 Preliminary Technical Data Estimate

The preliminary configuration of the European VNS for a tokamak is reported in Figure 1 below. In the outboard equatorial region, the Neutron Wall Load (NWL) reaches its highest point, allowing for an approximate achievement of ~6 dpa/fpy. The preliminary evaluation suggests an average NWL of about 0.39 MW/m² on the First Wall (FW), leading to an accumulation of ~3.9 dpa/fpy on average. To facilitate maintenance and provide better accessibility to testing, the initial proposal is to focus on conducting BB concept tests in the equatorial ports and/or the outboard area. Information about the area and volumes available for testing are reported in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** and Table 1.

Figure 1. Potential geometrical arrangement of the in-vessel components in a VNS based on first assessments.

Table 1. Estimated irradiation area and potential volumes.

	Area [m ²]	Volume [m ³]	Notes
Equatorial ports (per port)	$\sim 0.4\text{-}0.7$	$\sim 0.4\text{-}0.7$	(i) The dimension of the port is currently under discussion and matter of optimisation. (ii) The number of the port available for testing is under discussion.
Central Outboard Segment	~ 1.2	~ 1.2	Single segment
Lateral Outboard Segment	~ 1	~ 1	Single segment
Total Outboard (with cut-outs & zone close to NBI removed)	~ 21	~ 21	The total outboard area is reduced assuming: (iii) about 15% is lost because of cut-outs (iv) one third (i.e. 120) of the outboard segments nearby the Neutral Beam Injector (NBI) is not used for breeding.

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Report Annex 5

Volumetric Neutron Source as test bed to qualify Breeding blankets for future fusion reactors based on magnetic confinement

Authors: Robert Stieglitz, Mark Gilbert, Mattia Siccinio, Alice Ying

Date: June 22, 2023.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The analysis of the proposed sketch of a volumetric neutron source (VNS) by the working group has shown that on the way to a closed sketch, essential elements are at a rudimentary stage of development which require further analysis and development. This concerns in particular the plasma scenario, the fuel cycle, the heating systems, the divertor and accompanying neutronic analyses. The time required to meet these challenges alone is estimated at approx. 15 full-time equivalents (FTEs). To integrate all individual technical concept solutions into a closed preliminary concept, a human resource effort of a similar amount is assessed, i.e., approximately 15 FTEs best concentrated within an engineering design team on a single site.

The development effort to design a volumetric neutron source based on the Tokamak principle poses the least technical risk, and enables experience in licensing, the operation of a fuel cycle, as well as the logistics of the installation/expansion of neutron-irradiated in-vessel components to be made possible and thus represents a real added value on the way to the development of a future fusion reactor.

Due to the low degree of maturity of the VNS sketch, a two-step approach is proposed. First of all, a pre-concept study should be carried out over a period of one to two years to develop a coherent pre-concept of a VNS, the results of which can be clearly defined and should include the following points.

1. A closed physical concept (feasibility, meeting the testing requirements, identification design margins,...).
2. A risk registering of the most critical components.
3. A time schedule and a resource table to execute a closed conceptual engineering design (allowing for a cost assessment and a time frame for deployment).

The endorsement of a pre-conceptual VNS study necessitates a fundamental decision. If a volumetric neutron source (VNS) is considered an indispensable element for the scalable qualification of a breeding blanket, the provision of the corresponding manpower from both the existing EUROfusion DEMO design team and the large research laboratories is essential. The pre-concept phase proposed by the working group can be done in a time of **one to two years** and does not significantly delay the development of a DEMO power plant, given the long development time horizon. Conversely, it would be fatal if along the DEMO reactor development it is recognized that a VNS device is mandatory for breeding blanket qualification. The design phase following the pre-concept phase will need at least a period of approx. another 3 years, to be followed by a site selection procedure and a subsequent multi-

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annual nuclear licensing procedure, as well as a construction phase which will be in the order of that of IFMIF DONES.

In the light of these long-time scales necessary to implement a volumetric neutron source, postponement of a decision on a pre-conceptual study for a VNS should be considered more likely to be counterproductive.

Design requirements for nuclear blanket qualification

The VNS design anticipated matches several fusion DEMO blanket relevant target parameters. The most prominent are.

- neutron wall loading at first wall.
- fusion plasma relevant radiation conditions (line, brems and thermal radiation).
- Similar operational time scales allowing to mimic dynamical loads of in-vessel components
- Operational demonstration of a functional inner/outer fuel cycle (with verification of all chains)
- Management of transfer/replacement logistics of in-vessel components to establish guidelines required for nuclear safety demonstration.

- Tritium distribution/gradients within a reactor (released and trapped quantities)

Several more are listed in the report “Qualitative compilation of testing-qualification requirements for Breeding Blanket” provided as another output by the EUROfusion Breeding Blanket Working Group (see Annex 3.1 “Qualitative compilation of Breeding Blanket testing / qualification requirements requiring neutrons”), such as verification of fabrication technologies.

The VNS design for testing and qualification of the blanket poses important design requirements in at least two areas:

- (1) major parameters and
- (2) engineering design.

The major parameters of concern are those that have a major impact on both the usefulness of the tests and the cost of the device. The requirements of the engineering design include providing capabilities for fast insertion and removal of blanket test articles; access to the many coolants, inner and outer fuel cycle tritium-processing, and instrumentation lines; and suitably located space and facilities for ancillary equipment to support the test program. The engineering design should be pursued during VNS design phase.

The VNS major parameters for testing are derived by the goal of providing the database necessary to qualify/construct the blanket for DEMO. The most important parameters are neutron wall load, plasma mode of operation, continuous operating time (COT), fluence and test area.

The minimum acceptable neutron wall load is derived from two factors:

- (1) engineering scaling considerations and
- (2) trade-offs between device availability and wall load for a given testing fluence and testing time.

Volumetric heating in the blanket is directly proportional to the wall load. Most thermomechanical and tritium-related phenomena in the blanket strongly depend on the temperature and stress profiles, which in turn are directly dependent on the heating rates. If the wall load in VNS is lower than that in DEMO ($\sim 1MW/m^2$), engineering scaling considerations become crucial. Useful testing at a reduced wall load, relative to DEMO, is possible by altering the design and operating parameters of the test modules. However, if the wall load in the VNS is reduced by a factor of > 2 to 3 relative to that in

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DEMO, it becomes difficult to design act-alike test modules using engineering scaling rules to maintain important performance parameters such as stresses and temperatures; hence, many phenomena cannot be preserved. However, since the fusion device size, such as VNS, and cost increase with wall load, a neutron wall load of 0.5 MW/m^2 can provide meaningful testing and qualification for current EUROfusion DEMO breeding blankets." A higher wall load has a benefit of achieving a desired fluence at a shorter time for the same machine availability. The surface heat flux has a major influence on first wall thermo-mechanics. Prototypical ratios of the surface to bulk heating should be preserved.

The plasma mode of operation and the minimum continuous operating time (*COT*) have the effects on blanket testing in obtaining and sustaining equilibrium conditions of representative DEMO blanket behaviours. If pulsed operation is unavoidable in VNS, the goal is to keep the burn time longer than $3\tau_c$, where τ_c denotes the time constant of the most important process involved in the testing and qualification. The *COT* allows continuous operation of test blanket module to reach equilibrium and to observe cumulative effects, e.g., some radiation-induced changes, failures, and other nuclear phenomena. A *COT* of $\sim 1 - 2$ weeks was recommended from examining various characteristic time constants linked to solid breeder and liquid-metal blanket processes.

Fluence requirements for VNS can be derived by considering the following factors:

1. time required to perform basic and multiple-effect experiments to observe groups of phenomena and to resolve technical issues associated with particular aspects of the blanket design, e.g., solid breeder thermomechanical interactions;
2. time required to observe integrated behaviour past the beginning of life and during periods of significant radiation-induced changes in material properties and component behaviour;
3. time required to obtain data on key issues related to long-term component and system behaviour such as corrosion and mass transfer, chemical interactions, stress relaxation, breeder burnup and tritium build-up, and containment;
4. time required to obtain data on failure modes, effects, and rates, and component reliability data.

It should be noted that the test module fluence is different from the machine lifetime fluence. The test module fluence is the time-integrated wall load as received at the front wall of the test module, while the machine lifetime fluence refers on the time-integrated neutron wall load at the first wall during the machine lifetime. A test module fluence of $0.3 \text{ MW} \cdot \text{yr}/\text{m}^2$ is considered for individual and multiple-effect tests at beginning of life (BOL). A test module fluence of $2 \text{ MW} \cdot \text{yr}/\text{m}^2$ would be needed to verify blanket performance beyond BOL and in the regime where changes in properties nearly saturate. A longer fluence would be needed to assess blanket lifetime issue.

A desirable total testing area at the first wall of VNS was estimated to be $> 10 \text{ m}^2$. This amount of test area accommodates testing of different blanket design concepts, the need of engineering scaling, the need of grouping different phenomena, and multiple test modules per concept to achieve statistical significance.

Moreover, it is intended that by matching the overall conditions to be achieved, that aside from (validation and verification (V&V) for the blanket design process also procedures for manufacturing, safety demonstration (at normal operation, transients as well commissioning/decommissioning) and other can be derived paving the way towards a power plant licensing process (as mentioned in [1]).

Benefits and drawbacks of Volumetric Neutron Sources (VNS)

First, a fusion reaction based on magnetic confinement plasma provides the neutron spectrum expected in a future fusion power reactor. The VNS design sketch suggested now corresponds in principle to that of the proposals of [2] and [3] although the geometry dimensions differ, higher

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magnetic field is applied and substantial progress in material technology have been made since that time, allowing for a more robust and credible device realization. In [4] it is stated that a “Volumetric Neutron Sources (VNS) can be based on different designs based on mirrors, reversed pinches and tokamaks”. Then later “Preliminary feasibility assessments of different plasma confinement concepts, including tokamaks, stellarators and mirrors are underway in EUROfusion”, benefitting from work done in the past. Based on the results of this preliminary study, expected by the end of 2024, an ambitious plan for the realisation of a Tokamak based device, to be constructed as early as possible and run in parallel to both ITER operation and the DEMO design process, should be prepared and implemented.

Nonetheless, given the numerous sets of possibilities towards a volumetric neutron source, non-tokamak options may solve some of the volume constraints that would prevent the VNS from being useful for testing of breeding blanket solutions. There are numerous options to achieve a volumetric neutron source which are all associated with limitations either in terms of magnitude of the irradiation volume, the dose rate achievable and, most stringent to the neutron spectrum, causing not only material damage (dpa) but also transmutation (He/dpa). Here, VNS concepts based directly on a fusion reaction could mitigate all drawbacks associated with accelerator or fission reactor-based neutron sources, however, the plasma physics limits the solution space for magnetic confinement or inertial confinement solutions. The downsizing of the magnetic confinement reactor to a VNS scale as presented in [4] leaves a rather small solution space for the plasma domain allowing for a continuous reaction, which is essentially driven by a neutral beam heating system. Thereby, the plasma radiation is rather small compared to a thermal confinement. Furthermore, when relying on a tokamak based solution, the flexibility of the device is limited because procedures for the exchange of blanket modules are complex and space-intensive. Nevertheless, focusing on a tokamak based VNS provides as an additional benefit to provide experiences and improved means for DEMO maintainability. Alternatively, inertial electrostatic confinement (IEC) facilities are potentially conceivable as neutron sources allowing for a continuous burn. However, their degree of maturity as neutron source for qualifying reactor typical dimensions is rather low.

Irrespective of the type of fusion reaction-based neutron source a large source requires a tritium processing plant similar to a future fusion reactor. Furthermore, long irradiation times demand an access to maintenance facility (for cooling down and post treatment of the sample for PIE and reprocessing) so that blanket options to be tested have to be matured in the sense of irradiation behaviour and performance. On the other hand, there is no maturity possible without testing of a substantial volume of a DEMO blanket including all elements and loadings. Only an experimental device such as a VNS is able to achieve this maturity for DEMO blankets.

Still, any VNS testing device requires complementary irradiation facilities providing fusion reactor experimental verification/validation conditions for functional materials (breeder / multiplier), armor and diagnostic materials. These complementary facilities do not necessarily require large testing volumes, but must provide prototypical damage and transmutation to damage ratios – ideally already in advance of the VNS becoming operational.

Considering a fusion reaction based VNS to test blanket modules a minimum size/volume is required to achieve fusion reaction conditions which immediately translate into fusion power provision of the order of tens of megawatts. Such a power production by fusion consumes tritium in the kilogram range. Such a quantity of tritium required to operate a tokamak/stellarator VNS necessitates a nuclear licensing even if the device is licensed as an irradiation facility. This licensing procedure is associated with a safety demonstration at all operational stages from commissioning via operation to decommissioning. If a Tokamak based VNS is considered, the licensing procedure to be executed can

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act as an exercise/blueprint for a future fusion power reactor. To summarize, only the realization of a VNS provides major learning step towards a DEMO fusion reactor.

Still some questions need to be evaluated and answered during the pre-conceptual study including the following overarching questions:

- Will a tokamak-based VNS be more expensive to be built than other types of machines?
- Are there more physics and plasma technology R&D left for a tokamak-based VNS, which are not part of DEMO R&D?
- Is there a machine feasible to be built while providing substantial volumes for DEMO blanket testing?

Analysis of the considered VNS

Plasma scenario

The current VNS design point studied does not constitute a consolidated design point, but rather a first guess in an iterative exploration phase. For this reason, it is unsuitable for any conclusion on the feasibility of the VNS in a general sense. Here, the focus is to analyse some aspects which appear to be general for all tokamak VNS solutions. Consequently, the analysis remains on a qualitative, rather than quantitative level. A design review *stricto sensu* is only conceivable after deeper understanding, assessment and consolidation of the point.

To limit the machine size and the tritium consumption, the VNS considered in [4] is based on beam target-fusion reaction, and not originating from thermal reactions of the bulk plasma, as ITER or DEMO. Thus, the device is characterised by

- Small size (to minimise the surface and thus maximise P_{fus} for a target NWL).
- High heating power installed.
- Required magnetic-field. Generally speaking, the VNS benefits from a high magnetic field on axis. This because the large auxiliary power (NB) which has to be injected into a relatively small volume would otherwise lead to high β -values, in turn driving instabilities. A high aspect ratio (A) machine has the advantage of allowing for a large toroidal (TF) coil while keeping the overall machine size small. Plus, their small surface helps in increasing the NWL, since the beam-target fusion power is roughly independent on the plasma volume. On the other hand, large A-values tend to exhibit a larger β -normalised for a given β , with possible complications on the resistive wall mode (RWM) stability. Plus, they are generally less easy to vertical control at given elongation - where elongation might be useful to increase the plasma current at given field and
- Achievable pulse length. The VNS is a beam-target driven neutron source. The relatively large amount of beam power which is required for this purpose (tens of MW) can easily be employed for current drive, and this simultaneously to fusion power generation. For this reason, even at low current efficiency, the plasma can be expected to be fully non-inductive, which corresponds to (potentially) stationary plasmas (where “stationary” means that the pulse length is not constrained by the available central solenoid (CS) flux swing, or by any plasma physics requirement, so it can be adjusted to the needs of the experiment). A small CS might be necessary for the plasma start-up, possibly together with wave auxiliary current drive (electron cyclotron -EC- or ion cyclotron -IC- heating) for the early plasma stages, where the plasma density is too low to employ beams. Incidentally, EC is very likely necessary also to control tungsten influx during the plasma start-up.
- Heat radiation on in-vessel components. In the intended VNS operational parameter regime, the electromagnetic radiation from the core is foreseen to remain relatively low. In fact, while

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the temperature will be too low for significant synchrotron radiation emissions, both Bremsstrahlung and, especially, line radiation, are limited by the necessity of keeping the effective charge Z_{eff} low. A too high Z_{eff} reduces the beam slowing-down time to very short value, decreasing correspondingly the fusion power production. For this reason, it will probably be quite difficult in this VNS to reach DEMO-like level of heat radiation on the plasma-facing components while maintaining a sufficient neutral wall load.

- Heat load on divertor. The heat load on the divertor poses a challenge to the VNS device design due to the high thermal power and the low volume. Different solutions to dissipate the heat entering the divertor volume have to be considered and compared, also and especially in an integrated approach with the machine performance as a whole (see the previous considerations on Z_{eff}). Moreover, fast particle losses from the core may lead to the presence of hot spots of the first wall, by virtue of the large number of fast particles present (both α and beam particles) and the reduced machine size. This indicates that the plasma current should not become too low (say < 1 MA), to ensure a reasonable fast particle confinement. Also, the size of the machine must not shrink below a certain minimum size, where the lower end can at present not be identified.
- Burn efficiency. The burn efficiency performance corresponds to the one observed in JET during the last D-T campaign, i.e. $Q \approx 1$ for the beam-target fusion only. This corresponds to a beam burn-up fraction of about 0.7%.

From the plasma physics point of view the most essential questions are:

- Is the considered plasma scenario capable to achieve the duty cycle envisaged?
Limiting the device to an essentially beam-target fusion reaction-based design, the VNS can achieve in terms of plasma availability and pulse length the requirements considered.
- Can the VNS achieve blanket requirements in terms of neutron wall loading and heat radiation on the first wall?
In terms of achievable NWL, the projected VNS can likely attain the intended neutron wall loading similar to a DEMO reactor. However, it will be challenging the to achieve simultaneously NWL and first wall radiation heat loads.
- What needs to be done to achieve a credible plasma scenario matching the requirements?
Modelling activity and data mining in the experiments (e.g., JET or TFTR for the beam-target physics driven scenarios.
- What resources are required to get towards a closed plasma scenario?

Recommendation

Dedicated modelling activities on MHD stability, power exhaust, fast particle losses and vertical stability control. Here, an effort of about 5 FTEs are considered to sufficient for this purpose (plus the necessary computational resources).

Tritium fuel cycle

The tritium fuel cycle of a D-T fusion device generally includes two sub-cycles: (1) the inner fuel cycle (IFC) which primarily includes fuelling systems such as gas injection as well as pellet injectors, plasma exhaust (vacuum pump) to pump out unburned fuel, helium and any other impurities/gas, fuel clean-up, isotope separation, water detritiation, storage and management, and (2) the outer fuel cycle (OFC) which primarily recovers tritium lost in first wall/divertor and coolant and extracts tritium bred in breeding zone or tritium extraction system. In view of reducing the overall processing time and tritium inventories, KIT has proposed a direct internal recycling architecture that carries fuel directly from the plasma exhaust gas to the fuelling systems without going through the isotope separation system [1].

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Many technologies to satisfy the process, reprocess, separation, resupply, and injection functions of a fuel cycle tritium plant have been proposed, developed, and progressed [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17]. To maintain the VNS experimental program to the desired fluence levels will require a tritium processing plant encompassing a complete tritium fuel cycle. The tritium plant fuel cycle will need to be designed for VNS involving the best technologies available at the time, knowing that its control and management can still be challenging because of the very large scale-up from the state of the art, nevertheless its operation will further establish the technical basis for tritium processing in DEMO fusion power plant.

A 50 MW fusion power VNS will consume 2.8 kg tritium (T) per full power year. If the cost desire is to limit external tritium supply T to 2 kg or less per year, it would be economically incentive to operate the outer fuel cycle to recover the bred tritium from the blanket test modules. The state-of-the-art tritium extraction technologies including coolant purification systems for solid breeder and liquid metal PbLi blankets [8], [18], [19] should be utilized in the VNS tritium processing plant outer fuel cycle, while their operations can help further develop and optimize tritium extraction and recovery techniques for DEMO.

Tritium Throughput

Tritium (or D and T) throughput is a physics parameter and must be analyzed depending on the machine considering plasma edge recycling, radiative power to divertor, etc. The fuelling rate, S_{fr} necessary to replenish the burnt fuel in the $Q_{DT} = 10$ ITER Baseline H-mode scenario can be estimated from the fusion power ($\sim 500 MW$) and is about $\sim 0.7 Pa m^3/s$ [14]. An evaluation of the required fuelling rate of ITER Q=10 plasmas was determined to fulfil five major functions:

- (a) replenishing the fuel burn-up,
- (b) sustaining the core density,
- (c) ELM pace-making,
- (d) replenishing the fuel removed collaterally with He, and
- (e) controlling the divertor target peak power loads.

The required throughput while satisfying the design limitations of the external fuelling and pumping systems leads to a combined present technical ITER design limit of $200 Pa m^3/s$ for the total throughput of the D and T fuel components during a 400s pulse [14]. If this fuelling is performed with a 50–50 DT mix, the TBF in ITER would be $\sim 0.36\%$ at this maximum fuelling rate level [1]. (TBF: The fraction of tritium that reaches the plasma and undergoes fusion reaction before it escapes the confinement is called tritium burn fraction (TBF). In other words, TBF is the probability that a tritium atom injected into the plasma will be consumed in a fusion reaction before it diffuses out of the plasma [1].) The key physics differences between present experiments and ITER or DEMO that impact significantly the TBF are the inefficient penetration of edge recycled neutrals into the confined plasma and the need to sustain a relatively high separatrix density in burning plasma conditions to ensure acceptable power fluxes at the divertor through radiative divertor operation [1]. Noted that the VNS machine as proposed in [2] attempts to design and operate with a degraded pedestal because there is no need of good confinement while avoiding ELMs. There is no need to employ ITER-like ELM pace-making, instead the VNS will use RMP coils if any ELM mitigation turns out to be necessary. In addition, gas puff may be enough for fuelling. Nevertheless, only a small fraction of the fuel injected will undergo fusion, and one would need to analyze this quantity of burn fraction as well as the throughput for the proposed VNS machine during the pre-conceptual design study.

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Recommendation

Physics requirements studies on fuel throughput will have to be performed for VNS for the estimation of TBF.

Extrapolated from ITER TBF of 0.36%, the total throughput of the D and T fuel from gas puffing would be 12.2Pam³/s for a 30.5MW fusion power of VNS. If an estimated tritium burn fraction for JET D-T campaign of $\approx 0.2\%$ is applied, it will require a total D and T fuel throughput of 22.2Pam³/s. For a 50 MW VNS, the corresponding throughputs are 20 and 36 Pam³/s for a TBF of 0.36% and 0.2%, respectively.

Startup Inventory

The tritium startup inventory strongly depends on fusion power, tritium burnup fraction, tritium processing time, and a reserve inventory in the storage system to maintain the plasma and the power plant operational in case of any malfunction in a part of any tritium processing system. Numerical estimation of tritium startup was presented in [1] using a residence time approach for the entire fuel cycle. Extrapolated from the estimations provided in [1], Table 1 shows the approximated tritium startup inventory for different tritium burn fractions, IFC tritium processing times, and reserve scenarios. This simple analysis is meant to explore at what parameter ranges a startup inventory could be manageable. The startup inventory could be kept at less than 1 kg T for all cases analyzed, and for a fusion power of 50MW VNS, it could be less than 500 g T for an ITER like tritium burn fraction of 0.36% together with a tritium processing time of 4 hours or a lower tritium burn fraction of 0.2% but with a fast tritium processing time of 2 hours. Nevertheless, a detailed analysis of tritium startup inventory will need to be performed during the pre-conceptual study phase considering plasma physicists' estimated tritium burn fraction/tritium throughput together with the tritium fuel cycle operating parameters for the proposed VNS device and its associated tritium fuel cycle plant.

Table 1: Start-up inventory for various fusion power, tritium burn fraction, IFC tritium processing time

Fusion power, MW	Tritium burn fraction**	IFC tritium processing time, hr	Reserve time, hr	% IFC element failure	IFC Inventory, g	Reserved inventory, g	Start-up inventory, g
100	0.01	4	24	0.25	255.7	383.6	639.3*
30.5	0.01	4	24	0.25	78	117	195
30.5	0.0036	4	12	0.25	216.6	162.5	379.1
30.5	0.0036	4	6	0.25	216.6	81.2	297.9
30.5	0.002	4	12	0.25	390	292.5	682.5
30.5	0.002	4	6	0.25	390	146.2	536.2
50	0.0036	4	6	0.25	355.1	133.2	488.3
50	0.002	4	6	0.25	639.3	239.7	879.0
50	0.0036	2	6	0.25	177.6	133.2	310.8
50	0.002	2	6	0.25	319.6	239.7	559.4

*Dynamic simulation including OFC (outer fuel cycle) tritium processing time for tritium extraction system etc. gives a value of 710 g [1].

** Tritium burn fraction in [1] accounts fuelling efficiency

This startup inventory may be reduced (TBD) with a direct internal recycling architecture. Tritium bred in VNS test articles can be extracted to accommodate the need of external tritium supply.

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External Tritium Supply

Right now, the tritium used in fusion experiments like ITER, and the smaller JET tokamak in the UK, comes from nuclear fission reactors.

Tritium production rate in light water reactors (LWR) is limited to $\sim 0.5\text{--}1\text{ kg/y}$ whilst CANDU reactors produce $\sim 130\text{ g/GW}_{el}$ per full power-year from nD reaction. Future supply from CANDU depends on whether current reactors can be licensed to extend life by 20 years after refurbishment, which depends on political, national policy, and practical issues. Other non-fission sources, e.g., proton accelerator (APT), were proved to be uneconomical. Because of the relatively short life of tritium, which decays at a rate of $\sim 5.5\%$ per year (12.32 years half-life), and the issues and limitations of tritium production in fission systems, tritium resources available now from non-fusion sources are irrelevant to evaluating availability of tritium for start-up of DEMO or other fusion devices which will be constructed 20 years from now or beyond [1].

The time evolution of tritium inventory available from CANDU to provide start-up for fusion reactors is presented in Figure 1 [1]. With production and decay over 40 years of operation of CANDU reactors, tritium supply peaks at 27kg in 2027. Other recent studies regarding commercially available tritium can be found in references [15], [16]. Noted that for a 30.5MW fusion power of VNS, it will consume 1.71kg tritium (T) per full power year and will be 2.8 kg tritium (T) per full power year for a 50 MW fusion power. A 2 kg per year tritium T limitation will afford the 50 MW VNS to operate for 8.5 months per year. This shows that the tritium bred from the blanket test modules should be recovered to supply DT fusion reactions.

Fig. 1. Tritium inventory available to provide start-up inventory in the temporal window 2000–2060 taken from [1].

Tritium Safety Licensing

The safety standard requirements for protection of the public and release guidelines in ITER may be applied to VNS. General safety approaches include minimizing tritium inventories, reducing tritium permeation through materials, and decontaminating material for waste disposal.

ITER complies with International Commission on Radiation Protection (ICRP), International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), and French regulations. The Institute for Radiological Protection and Nuclear Safety (IRSN) published a reference document that outlines the safety and radiation protection

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considerations for fusion reactors [17]. Tritium release from ITER is conservatively assumed to be solely tritiated water and is not to exceed $2.5g/y$ in years of heavy maintenance and $0.6g/y$ under normal operation. The tritium site limit in the whole facility is $4kg$ and limit in the vacuum vessel is $1kg$ [1].

Findings:

VNS should encompass a complete tritium processing plant including both inner and outer fuel cycles. The state-of-the-art sub-element fuel cycle technologies should be employed including to consider Direct internal cycling cycle to reduce tritium processing time and inventory. If VNS starts DT operation in parallel to ITER operation, there might be enough civilian tritium inventory available to supply both machines DT burns for a few years. However, economically, the tritium bred in VNS test blanket modules should be recovered to make-up the tritium consumed. A 50 MW fusion power VNS will consume 2.8 kg tritium (T) per full power year. Tritium (D and T) throughput is a physics parameter and must be analyzed from VNS physics, which then governs inner fuel cycle design including sizing and capacity for various fuel cycle sub-elements. In addition, tritium throughput has a tremendous impact on the tritium start-up inventory.

Recommendations:

1. VNS physics modelling to be performed to quantify T and D throughput (included in the recommended modelling activities in Plasma scenarios)
2. A concept development study with a combined expertise 2-3 FTEs in tritium processing for both inner and outer fuel cycles is recommended to develop VNS tritium processing plant.

In-vessel components

Several aspects of the technology of breeding blankets could be tested by an early VNS; more than just pure TBR demonstration, but also tritium recovery factors from operating breeding modules, tritium migration into structural materials (and the barriers that need to be developed and tested to prevent this). Depending on whether some or all of these “test requirements” are to be achieved in a VNS, there will be a different set of requirements for the VNS itself. Regarding the presented VNS concept the major technological challenges to meet the formulated requirements are:

- Are the machine dimensions sufficient to achieve breeding blankets testing requirements?

In the case of a simple TBR demonstration for a particular combination of lithium compound, coolant and structural material, then it may not be necessary to have a full-scale mock-up tested by a VNS – by full-scale here we would mean the full breeding zone (radial) thickness. If only for TBR demo, then shielding can be maximised to protect the vacuum vessel. However, there would need to be careful assessment of the geometry to confirm that a much reduced radial extent can achieve the necessary shielding. If the requirement is to test a larger proportion of the in-vessel tritium fuel cycle – e.g., to include the validation of extraction of sufficient tritium from a breeding zone to confirm self-sufficiency – then the size of the testing zone – by radial thickness and cross-sectional area – must be more faithfully represent the dimensions of a breeding module in a power plant. In this case, the thickness of the breeding module to be tested would be of the order of $70 - 100\text{ cm}$ – equivalent to the designs proposed for EU-DEMO [20]. In this case, of a realistic scale breeding zone, it was shown [20] that there is no need for additional shielding – the breeding zone and vacuum vessel are sufficient and the Vacuum vessel (VV), in particular, should be protected by the breeding zone without any further need for separate shielding. While this would not lead to a tokamak-VNS having any special designs, such as additional shielding, it would nonetheless require the VNS to have a radial dimension equivalent to a full-scale reactor.

Recommendation:

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Perform the appropriate neutron-transport assessments of a proposed VNS geometry to identify if there would be issues with shielding due to the limited space available in a compact VNS.

- What flexibility of the VNS is required?
Even if only a single operating temperature regime and coolant choice was part of a proposed VNS, there would still be some scope for testing different options concerning moderation/reflection and structural materials. On the other hand, to be fully flexible, and able to test the full range of breeding concepts being considered, including using helium, water, or liquid lithium coolants, then the engineering of a VNS will be much more challenging. For example, the bulk of the VNS may use one coolant system (e.g. water) and a main operating temperature range, but there may be selected breeding zones with completely separate systems that would all have to be integrated together [note that mixing the testing of liquid lithium coolant in a system using water for coolant elsewhere, would raise serious safety concerns and require additional protections to be built into the reactor.
- Are the required shielding dimensions sufficient to vacuum vessel the super-conducting coils?
Looking to the CAD provided in [21], the distance of fusion plasma edge to the coils is of the order of 0.8m, requiring a highly efficient neutron shielding. Especially. One has to take care of that the maximum allowable fast neutron flux at the TF coil winding pack is not exceeded to assure a long life-time of the VNS. Considering Nb₃Sn superconductor the maximum fast neutron flux (>1MeV) shall not exceed 10⁹n/(cm²s) and the total neutron heating in the winding pack shall be smaller than 50K/m², as described in [22], [23]. Here, the VNS concept sketch needs to be refined further with respect to operational scenario, test beds available.

Recommendation

Given the rather compact design of the VNS and the technology being used close to that being applied in a future DEMO fusion power plant, high quality expert knowledge based neutronics analysis is required in conjunction with the design of high heat flux components as well as remote maintenance know-how. This means not access to High Performance Computing (HPC) capacities during the pre-conceptual phase but qualified and continuous analysis of the order of 2-3 FTEs.

Divertor

The fraction of the divertor area to the entire plasma domain is considerably larger than that of a fusion reactor and thus the heat removal from the divertor plays an essential role. Moreover, the distance of the divertor to the neutron source is in terms of view angle and distance so short, that it will experience a significant neutron damage aside from a high heat loading, which is different to the concepts considered in the past based on a very high aspect ratio [3] [2]. Nonetheless a closed divertor design exhibiting a similar life time as the test modules is mandatory to assure a credible and sufficiently long availability of the device to meet blanket relevant damage rates.

This in turn requires significant expert know-how of radiation resistant high heat flux component design and fabrication technologies but also profound expertise in remote handling logistics and material. Despite the challenging divertor development all concept solutions found must be strongly synchronized with the overall design at least of the in-vessel components of the VNS.

Recommendation:

Given the compact dimensions of the divertor and the small distance of the divertor to the core plasma a dedicated VNS divertor design measure needs to be started in tight collaboration with a pre-conceptual design team to establish a closed pre-conceptual VNS model. Solely the activity of the development of a VNS compatible divertor is assessed to be of the order of 2 FTEs.

Heating systems, Diagnostics, Heat Transfer systems (Robert)

The heating concept of both types envisaged including Neutral beam injection (NBI) and Electron cyclotron (EC) heating of the presented VNS is well matured and almost corresponding to that developed for ITER and experimentally proven in JET.

Although the dimensions are not given in detail, the assessments show that none of the systems are exceeding space charge limits. Nonetheless, still considerable efforts have to be allocated into the design of cw-stability of the NBI system to ensure long term endurance at high power levels. Another aspect is the NBI efficiency at low plasma densities and low temperatures requiring further studies. Here, at least 2 FTY are required to ensure that a reliable source with an adequate integration into the VNS can be provided.

The VNS is a rather compact machine associated with high spatial gradients of particles and temperature. Thus, there is limited space for machine control and the required diagnostics. There are numerous aspects which need clarification during a further maturation of the VNS concept such as:

- What types of diagnostics are foreseen (limited space- but radiation hard -ITER LIKE)?
- Even for the VNS considered as nuclear installation redundancy is required. How is it intended to accomplish? ITER like approach- if so how does this interfere with the temporal availability (how many hours of yearly operation are foreseen?)

Due to the previously unspecified usage profile of a volumetric neutron source (VNS), the current concept sketch contains a number of essential features that significantly influence the engineering design of the overall system and thus its performance. In this way, different cooling media, breeder/multiplier materials can be considered demanding substantially different infrastructures, space requirements and also available test volumes.

Recommendation

In this sense, it would surely be useful to specify in more detail in the requirements profile of the VNS source in the view of the blanket testing, which mainly has to address the possible spectrum of blanket concepts, since this then also does not insignificantly influence the costs of a plant and the required infrastructure to operate the test blankets, e.g., coolant purification, activation, By now, the paper

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[4] suggest that VNS will likely address the first two DEMO reference concepts WCLL and HCPB, and may address WCCB later, however, this needs to be confirmed.

Although the VNS concept sketch has been elaborated from the plasma side, the blanket requirements parameter set is mainly limited by physical parameters and lacking of the impact of engineering aspects. The integration of the engineering aspects may require not only additional space for the integration of coolant tubes, shielding, but also auxiliary systems. Here, it is recommended to specify at an early stage what spectrum of blanket concepts shall be studied in the context of a VNS.

Overall VNS device Design

The volumetric neutron source, in its current state, is more in the state of a concept sketch than a closed concept.

For the core aspects such as the plasma, the magnetic configuration and the components within the vacuum container, a closed overall concept should first be developed, which then forms the basis for an engineering design to be developed subsequently. For this, however, it is also necessary to specify the range of requirements even more concretely; here, some points of view are still open.

During the pre-conceptual phase a set of engineering solutions need to be developed to assure a closed dimensioning of such a facility. Here, essential problems must be prepared in such a way that a solution approach can be found that enables an engineering design and thus dimensioning. Excellent questions in this context represent the following aspects:

- What extraction concept is foreseen to allow for rapid extraction of in-vessel components (IVC)?
- What range for testing of blanket concepts is foreseen due to the large variety of blankets concepts existing, which are all associated with different temperature ranges, coolant duct requirements?

By now the concept of the VNS has not been fully developed. According to the UK material qualification strategy page 19 [24] there is a quite wide temperature differences to be covered by different blanket concept types. Limiting the types of blanket concepts intended to be studied in the frame of a VNS immediately has an impact of the design of a VNS.

Here, in the context of the concept sketch a set- of aspects have to be developed on the frame of a structured pre-conceptual design activity.

Recommendation

- *The specification of the requirements and the consolidation of the VNS concept should be addressed in a timely manner.*
- *After this first phase, lasting at maximum 1 to 2 years, it should be decided whether and to what extent the engineering design of a VNS can be completed.*
- *This decision is ultimately based on the extent to which the projected VNS plant will be able to meet the requirements and where the greatest development risks lie.*
- *After the development of a closed concept, it also becomes clear which investment costs and operating costs are to be expected at least in large scale.*
- *Another mission of this exploratory team should be to quantify the personnel effort required for the engineering design and to develop a time horizon up to which a “conceptual design report” shall be produced.*
- *After this pre-conceptual design phase a review of the concept should be executed, since the engineering design requires substantial human resources to dimension*

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- *Magnet systems and winding pack together with the cryo-system*
- *Vacuum systems (-> fuel cycle)*
- *Building set-up including rad-waste management*
- *Power management,*
- *.....*

For the maturation of the currently discussed VNS concept sketch towards a closed pre-conceptual design gaps have been identified in several expertise domains requiring human resource efforts. The assessed human expert resources to cover the most striking fields and the required efforts are in the following domains:

- Plasma physics: 5 FTEs
- Tritium Fuel cycle: 3 FTEs
- Neutronics analysis supporting: 3 FTEs
- Divertor: 2 FTEs
- Heating Systems: 2 FTEs

The solution of the individual challenges mentioned above still does not assure a holistic pre-conceptual design. This is because all the individual solution concepts have to be integrated into an overall concept of a VNS in such a way that different blanket concepts can be operated under conditions typical of fusion power plants. This requires the establishment of a central design group, which develops a holistic preliminary concept and integrates the work for the development of solutions in the previously mentioned areas. This design group is responsible for all tasks such as magnet systems, building concept, power supply, logistics, diagnostics, component arrangement, and much more. The effort of the design team to integrate all individual solutions into a holistic pre-concept, which contains the following points-

- a pre-concept report
- provision of a risk register for required work on the way to a VNS design report
- quantification of the development effort for a VNS design,
- providing a schedule for the development of a VNS design,

estimates the group of similar magnitude as that of the expert teams, i.e. 15 FTEs.

The design team should be located in one location so that all -coordinative tasks can be carried out on short communication routes. The availability of human resources, together with the relevant specialist expertise to implement the project, is certainly a major challenge, which, given the short time scales, can hardly be met by the current EUROfusion home team or the research laboratories.

A fundamental decision must therefore be taken here. If there is a conviction that a volumetric neutron source (VNS) is an indispensable element for the scalable qualification of a core component of a future fusion power plant such as the blanket, the provision of the corresponding manpower from both the existing EUROfusion DEMO design team and the large research laboratories is essential. The pre-concept phase, limited in time to **one to two years**, does not significantly delay the development of a DEMO power plant, given the long development time horizon.

Conversely, it would be fatal if later during the DEMO development it is recognized that a VNS device is mandatory for breeding blanket qualification. Starting too late the pre-conceptual phase, an engineering conceptual design phase will require at least a period of approx. 3 years, to be followed by a site selection and subsequent multi-annual nuclear licensing procedure, as well as a construction phase which will be in the order of IFMIF DONES.

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The aspects of licensing and the construction of a VNS addressed in the working order for this working group cannot be answered, as they will be one of the key findings of a pre-concept study that has not yet begun.

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Report Annex 6

Overview on the requirements for irradiated materials test data input to performance assurance modelling of blanket components

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Date: 02/June/2023

Executive Summary

Given the current situation with ITER and timing of DONES-IFMIF, the soonest experimental qualification of TBM components and sub-components as well as materials and material solutions in fusion spectrum **may not** start before 2035+. As a possible risk mitigation action the contribution of integrated modelling approach has been proposed as result of the WG analysis. One could thus built so-called “virtual qualification’ procedure by means of computational tools. The rationale for this **assurance modelling** approach is as follows:

- The aim is to create a real alternative to full scale testing under target/expected fusion power plant conditions because of time / cost constraints in introducing new materials (variants on tungsten, new RAFM steels, CuCrZr for example).
- The virtual qualification assumes that rigorous models are no better (or worse) than experiments, as ‘renderings of reality’. There is a need to specifically address the fact that the fusion power plant has no precursors: everything prior to the plant operation is a proxy.
- The models rely on 3D constructed microstructures representing real and complex chemistries at polycrystalline scale
- The models must be grounded in a mechanistic (physics based) understanding each time, of how the material – at polycrystalline scale – evolves under irradiation; an empirical understanding should be avoided if possible to substantiate extrapolation power of such tools.

The tools that will constitute such “virtual qualification’ procedure should thereby be thoroughly validated using bespoke experiments involving irradiation campaigns. An

example of such approach to establish constitute model for elastic-plastic response has been presented, and its essence is provided in *Figure 1*.

Outcomes of the discussion held during the WG meetings

1. The current knowledge on the application of modelling tools in EFDA/EUROfusion workprogrammes has been summarized and presented for discussion. It is highlighted that any modelling requires experimental validation. The power of the computational tools to extrapolate beyond available experimental data can be questioned and hence a dedicated interaction with safety and licensing teams is needed to establish the framework of such tools.
2. As a first step towards building the “virtual qualification” tool, the review of the methods, experiments and computational studies applied for the development and validation of the DEMO design rules is needed. This could be a starting point defining the current gaps in terms of experimental data as well as gaps in the material property handbook data. Covering the gaps in the material property hand book data could be the first application of such tool.
3. Given the limited time available to establish the recommendation for the GA, it is proposed to hold further extension of this Annex until the feedback from the GA is received.

$$\dot{\gamma}^k = \rho_m v_g b^k = \rho_m v b^{k^2} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta F}{kT}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{(|\tau^k| - \tau_c^k) \Delta V}{kT}\right) \text{sgn}(\tau^k)$$

Single grain

$$\tau_c^k = (1 - X) \tau_0^k + G b^k \sqrt{\left(\frac{X \tau_0^k}{G b^k}\right)^2 + \alpha^2 \rho_e + P_1 k^2}$$

Calibrate ($\dot{\epsilon}$ & T):

- 3 x (2, 3, 5um) height microcantilever beams with displacement hold segments
- TEM - SFT/loop/precipitate etc. size and number density

Validate:

- Spherical indent load hold tests

Polycrystal

Validate:

- Tensile tests with high resolution digital image correlation and electron imaging

Hardie, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-49585-0>

Figure 1. Example of modelling procedure and its validation at different scales to establish a prediction of the constitute model for elastic-plastic response accounting for the irradiation effect.

Report Annex 7

Matching of neutron-based Breeding Blanket testing / qualification requirements with existing / anticipated neutron exposure facilities

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Date: 29/June/2023

Introductory remarks

This Annex contains a table where irradiation facility types are qualitatively evaluated against the BB maturation technology testing needs. This involves not only the increase of the TRL of the BB systems and components technologies and designs, but also includes the concept of nuclear qualification, which poses more challenging demonstrations from regulatory perspectives. The engineering evaluations account for the identified technological issues, outcomes of Annex 3.1, and for the irradiation capabilities, accordingly with Annexes from 4.1 to 4.5, but including also DEMO itself.

The critical issues reported in the table need testing and/or qualification activities involving fast flux neutron irradiation (up to 20-50 dpa), and representative tokamak facility operating conditions. This means harsh conditions involving the simultaneous presence of high pressure and temperatures, of remarkable temperature gradients, of relevant magnetic fields, of hazardous mechanical and chemical processes occurring in the materials. These critical issues have been divided into 6 groups related to: structure, liquid-metal breeder-multiplier, breeder and purge, coolant/structure interactions, solid breeder/multiplier/structure interactions and general blanket issues.

Then, existing and planned nuclear irradiation infrastructures are evaluated on the basis of their capabilities to cope with each specific critical issue. Their capabilities are evaluated based on the expected performances, but without any direct reference to existing installations. The types of facilities considered in this exercise are those reported in the list below and DEMO itself, where integral tests at full scale are possible.

- **Material Test Reactor.** It is characterized by meaningful irradiation performances in small size capsules, by a different (lower energy) neutron flux spectrum, by no flexibility in hosting mock-ups with relevant geometries or representative temperature gradients, by the impossibility to perform tests under the effect of a magnetic field or vacuum. In general, it is possible to perform separate effect tests in small capsules.

- **Spallation source.** It is characterized by meaningful irradiation performances in small size capsules, by high-energy neutrons, by no capability to irradiate representative mock-ups with relevant dimensions or representative temperature gradients, by the impossibility to perform tests under the effect of magnetic fields or vacuum. In general, it is possible to perform separate effect tests in small capsules.
- **p/d-LINAC.** It is characterized by reasonable irradiation performances in relevant size mock-ups, by an acceptable neutron flux spectrum (with higher energy tails), by the capability to irradiate representative mock-ups with acceptable temperature gradients, by the impossibility to perform tests under the effect of magnetic fields or vacuum. In general, it is possible to perform separate effect tests in scaled mock-ups.
- **IFMIF-DONES.** It is characterized by reasonable irradiation performances in relevant size mock-ups, by a representative neutron flux spectrum, by the capability to irradiate representative mock-ups with acceptable temperature gradients, by the impossibility to perform tests under the effect of magnetic fields or vacuum. In general, it is possible to perform separate effect tests in scaled mock-ups.
- **VNS.** It is characterized by reasonable irradiation capabilities in large size mock-ups, by a representative test conditions in terms of neutron flux spectrum, temperature gradients, magnetic fields and presence of vacuum. In general, it is possible to perform integral effect tests in mock-ups.

Considering the need to provide a simple and easily readable evaluation, the wording already used in Ref. [1] has been adopted (i.e., “small”, “partial” and “substantial”):

- “small” means contribution to one or more aspects from qualitative point of view;
- “partial” means contribution to one or more aspects from qualitative and quantitative point of view, in other terms substantial contribution when supplemented by fusion test; and
- “substantial” is reported for fusion tests, capable of resolving the issue.

In case the irradiation facility type is not reported, this means that no significant information can be obtained.

For sake of clarity, it must be stressed that the evaluation of nuclear testing and qualification needs and the plan for the deployment of research and commercial nuclear fusion power plants with the breeding blanket technology is not available neither part of the present Roadmap exercise and far from being defined: it will require well-defined design specifications, an industrial policy, and the definition of a currently not yet existing regulatory framework.

Table 1. Engineering evaluation of irradiation facilities in addressing BB critical issues

#	BREEDING BLANKET CRITICAL ISSUES	NUCLEAR TESTING / QUALIFICATION NEEDS	EVALUATION OF NUCLEAR TEST FACILITIES	COMMENTS
1	Structure			
<i>1.1</i>	<i>Changes in properties and behaviour of materials</i>			
1.1.1	Deformation and/or breach of components	<p><i>Evaluation of stress history under relevant loads (pressure, EM, thermal gradients, swelling, creep + neutron irradiation).</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source small p/d-LINAC partial IFMIF-DONES partial VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	--
1.1.2	Effect of first wall heat flux and cycling on fatigue or crack growth-related failure	<p><i>Evaluation of cyclic stress due to high temperatures, thermal gradients, coolant pressures, corrosive environments + neutron irradiation.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	--
1.1.3	Magnetic forces within the structure (including disruptions)	<p><i>Evaluation of neutron impact on material property changes and on the material's responses to magnetic loading, including deformation and failure modes. Spectrum, fluence, and flux are important test parameters.</i></p> <p><i>Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification</i></p>	<p>VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	--
1.1.4	Premature failure at welds and discontinuities	<p><i>Evaluation of material damage and determination of the effects of differential swelling between the weld and parent material. Testing parameters including neutron flux, spectrum, fluence, temperature, and atmosphere are required to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>MTR Spallation source small p/d-LINAC partial IFMIF-DONES partial* VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	* IFMIF DONES can be substantial from parameters point of view but it is reported partial because the synergic effect of loads and the size of the mock-up.
1.1.5	Failure due to hot spots	<p><i>Evaluation of failure modes due to material properties changes in relevant environmental condition. The operating environment/parameters necessary for assessing the effects of hot spots on failure include the geometry of the first wall/blanket, expected operating temperature (300-600°C), neutron spectrum, flux, and fluence, heat flux, coolant velocity, and magnetic fields (in liquid metal blankets).</i></p> <p><i>Sample region of hot spots. Coolant maldistributions, Crud formation in cooling channels, Corrosion effects, He bubble(s) formation (WCLL), MHD effect(s) (WCLL), Changes of multiplier/breeder proprieties/geometry/compactness (HCPB).</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>MTR Spallation source small p/d-LINAC partial IFMIF-DONES partial VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	--

1.1.6	Interaction of primary and secondary stresses and deformation	<p><i>Evaluation of possible interaction of primary (pressure, electromagnetic, etc.) and secondary stresses (thermal, swelling, etc.) to guide the BB design. The operating environment/parameters necessary for assessing the effects of such interactions include the geometry of the first wall/blanket, expected operating temperature (300-600°C) and – above all, neutron spectrum, flux, fluence, heat flux, coolant conditions, and magnetic fields.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	partial partial substantial	--
1.1.7	Effect of swelling, creep and thermal gradients on stresses concentrations	<p><i>Evaluation of localized stress due to swelling, creep and thermal gradients. The operating environment/parameters necessary for assessing the effects of such effects include the geometry of the first wall/blanket, expected operating temperature (300-600°C), neutron spectrum, flux, fluence, heat flux, coolant conditions, and magnetic fields.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	small partial partial substantial	--
1.1.8	Failure due to shutdown residual stresses	<p><i>Evaluation of failures due to shutdown residual stresses. Testing parameters including mainly neutron flux, spectrum, fluence, temperature, and electromagnetic field are required to properly resolve this issue. Reproducing the complex geometry of the first wall/blanket is pivotal to accurately assess such failures.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	partial partial substantial	--
1.1.9	Interaction between surface effects and first wall failures	<p><i>Evaluation of failures induced by high primary stresses into the FW surface because of sputtering of atoms, implantation, transmutations resulting from exposure to charged particles, neutrons, neutral atoms, and electromagnetic radiation. Neutrons allow understanding potential material damages. Testing parameters including plasma interactions, surface heat flux, operating time, temperature, stress level in the FW, magnetic field, as well as neutron fluence are required to properly assess these failures.</i></p> <p><i>Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	VNS or DEMO	substantial	--
1.1.10	Self-welding of similar and dissimilar metals	<p><i>Evaluation of self-welding of similar and dissimilar metals because of excessive deformations and other phenomena (e.g., corrosion, etc.). Neutrons allow to properly assess this issue since they are a heating source and can produce specific reactions leading to material damages which affect their response. Testing parameters including plasma interactions, surface heat flux, operating time, temperature, stress level in the FW, magnetic field, as well as neutron fluence are required to properly assess these failures.</i></p> <p><i>Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	VNS or DEMO	substantial	--
1.2	<i>Tritium permeation through the structure</i>				
1.2.1	Effectiveness of tritium permeation barriers	<p><i>Evaluation of the effectiveness of tritium permeation barriers under neutron and gamma irradiation leading to possible changes in the barriers structure.</i></p>	p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES	partial partial	--

		<p>Neutrons allow to properly assess this issue understanding any potential material damages. Testing parameters including mainly neutron flux, spectrum, fluence, temperature, and electromagnetic field are required to properly resolve this issue.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	VNS or DEMO	substantial	
1.2.2	Effect of radiation on tritium permeation	<p>Evaluation of radiation effects on tritium permeation (e.g, trapping, enhancement, etc.) Neutrons and gammas allow to properly assess this issue understanding any potential radiation effect. Testing parameters including neutron flux, spectrum, fluence, temperature are required to properly resolve this issue.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	MTR Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	small partial substantial* substantial* substantial	* The high energy neutrons of > 14 MeV in IFMIF-DONES or p/d-LINAC can cause premature irradiation damage. A suitable design needs a Neutron Spectral Shifter (NSS), moderator/reflector for spectrum tailoring.
1.2.3	Structural activation product inventory and volatility	<p>Evaluation of structural activation product inventory and volatility by means of experiments which verify neutronic calculations. Assessment/reduction of uncertainties in cross sections of long-lived isotopes and the actual levels of impurities in engineered materials. Testing parameters including geometry of the first wall/blanket, functional and structural materials, neutron flux, spectrum and fluence are required to properly resolve this issue.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	small substantial* substantial* substantial	* the high energy neutrons of > 14 MeV in IFMIF-DONES or p/d-LINAC can produce extra activation products. Predictability of this distortion is influenced by the knowledge of the cross sections at high energy neutrons. This critical issue can be in any case addressed in satisfactory way in p/d-LINAC or IFMIF-DONES tests conditions.
2	Metal liquid breeder-multiplier				
2.0.1	Geometric effects on flow distribution	<p>Evaluation of geometric effects on flow distribution assessing possible instabilities which could lead to premature structural failure because of fatigue caused by mechanical stress, fretting or cyclic thermal stresses. Neutrons allow understanding potential material damages.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	partial* partial* substantial	* Volumetric heating in liquid metal can cause flow reversal or flow recirculation or stagnation depending on flow direction and geometry. Moreover, geometrical constraints may limit the representativeness of these effects in scaled-down mock-up.
2.0.2	Activation products in PbLi	<p>Evaluation of activation products in PbLi because of the gradual alteration of its composition over time due to transmutation reactions that result in the formation of various species. Testing parameters including neutron flux, spectrum, fluence, temperature are required to properly resolve this issue.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	small partial partial substantial	* only VNS or DEMO can be fully representative. The p/d-LINAC or IFMIF-DONES will be affected by unavoidable distortions, due to T field in the mock-ups, neutron spectra, etc.
3	Breeder and purge				

3.0.1	Tritium recovery and inventory in solid breeder materials	<p><i>Evaluation of tritium recovery and inventory in solid breeder materials. The operating environment for studying these phenomena shall reproduce the reference temperature field, purge gas chemistry and might include interaction of purge gas with structural components since it effects the thermodynamic environment. Neutrons allow understanding the impact of lithium transmutation, burnup or high local tritium production rates as well as the impact of cracking, grain growth, creep, sintering in tritium transport assessments.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial</p>	--
3.0.2	Liquid breeder tritium extraction	<p><i>Evaluation of tritium extraction from Liquid breeder. The primary variables affecting tritium extraction are tritium concentration and impurity levels in the breeder. Temperature and pressure are also significant if the extractor has to operate at breeder conditions. Neutrons allow understanding the impact of lithium burnup, activation products, helium bubble and material damages in tritium transport assessments.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial</p>	--
3.1 Temperature limits and variability in solid breeder material				
3.1.1	Temperature limits	<p><i>Evaluation upper and lower temperature limits for determining the operating range of a solid breeder blanket. The operating environment for studying these phenomena shall reproduce the expected temperature gradients. Neutron flux, spectrum, fluence are pivotal to properly assess such limits.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial* partial* substantial</p>	* because p/d and IFMIF cannot provide enough volume or representative temperature distribution present in blanket solid breeders.
3.1.2	Thermal conductivity changes under irradiation *	<p><i>Evaluation of thermal conductivity changes under irradiation. Neutron wall loading and temperature are expected to be the dominant factors affecting thermal conductivity damages. Changes in thermal conductivity can begin at low fluence levels and may saturate up to high fluence. In pebble beds, thermal conductivity can be significantly influenced by gas pressure. Testing parameters including neutron flux, spectrum, fluence, temperature are required to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial</p>	* Thermal conductivity changes under irradiation can be obtained as a property (k as a function of irradiation dose and temperature) Thermal conductivity change can be due to pebble relocations, creep that is impacted by the operating conditions
3.1.3	Effect of cracking	<p><i>Evaluation of cracking effects under irradiation. These effects can significantly impact the thermal and mechanical performances. Neutron heating is the driving force for thermal stress cracking, and helium production generates swelling-induced cracking. The operating environment, including neutron wall load, geometry, temperature, stresses caused by temperature gradients, and fluence levels, also plays a crucial role in solid breeder cracking.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial</p>	--

		<i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i>		
3.1.4	Breeder behaviour at high burn-up/high dpa	<p><i>Evaluation of Breeder behaviour at high burn-up/high dpa. The operating conditions should consider hydrogen and oxygen content, radiolytic decomposition, and the solid breeder's geometry which may also play an important role. Testing parameters including neutron flux, spectrum and fluence are required to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>MTR small Spallation source small p/d-LINAC small IFMIF-DONES partial* VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	* if in high flux zone
4	Coolant/structure interactions			
4.1	<i>Mechanical and materials interactions</i>			
4.1.1	Corrosion	<p><i>Evaluation of corrosion phenomena in the coolant. The operating environment for mass transport depends on factors such as neutron fluence, geometry, temperature, velocity, solubilities, and diffusion coefficients. The magnetic field, bulk heating and dissolved hydrogen may substantially change the corrosion mechanism.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source small p/d-LINAC partial IFMIF-DONES partial VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	--
4.1.2	Failure of coolant wall due to stress corrosion cracking	<p><i>Evaluation of failure of coolant wall due to stress corrosion cracking. In testing, neutrons are necessary to produce displacement damage that enhances creep, solute redistribution, and irradiation hardening and softening. Neutrons are also required to study the effects of helium bubbles, dissolved hydrogen, and other species produced via high-energy neutron reactions. Therefore, the neutron spectrum and fluence are important parameters.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source small p/d-LINAC partial IFMIF-DONES partial VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	--
4.1.3	Failure of coolant wall due to liquid-metal embrittlement	<p><i>Evaluation of failure of coolant wall due to liquid-metal embrittlement. The testing requires neutrons for specific reactions and displacement damage. Hence, the neutron spectrum and flux are critical experimental parameters.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source small p/d-LINAC partial IFMIF-DONES partial VNS or DEMO substantial</p>	--
4.2	<i>Thermal interactions</i>			
4.2.1	Flow sensitivity to dimensional changes	<p><i>Evaluation of flow sensitivity to dimensional changes. Tests to address this issue will require simulation of local heating rates, surface heat loads, geometry, temperature, velocity, mechanical stress, and coolant pressure. Neutrons effects in heating and material damage allow to develop realistic dimensional changes.</i></p> <p><i>Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>VNS partial* DEMO substantial</p>	* This is an issue that can be studied only in the prototypical component.
5	Solid breeder/multiplier/structure interactions			

5.1		<i>Solid breeder mechanical and materials interactions</i>		
5.1.1	Clad corrosion from breeder burn-up products	<p><i>Evaluation of clad corrosion from breeder burn-up products. The testing requires neutrons for determining the burnout of lithium and tritium production, as well as controlling heat generation and temperatures at the breeder/structure interface. Other factors such as geometry, spectrum, and any other contributors to local chemistry (e.g. H2 added to purge) are also be significant.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>MTR Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial substantial substantial substantial</p>	This is mainly matter of neutrons and composition.
5.1.2	Strain accommodation by creep and plastic flow	<p><i>Evaluation of strain accommodation by creep and plastic flow. Testing parameters require neutrons to provide heating, specific reactions, helium production and displacement damage. The parameters of temperature, scaled geometric configurations, and fluences are important factors in addressing strain accommodation, with specific considerations for each type of strain. Thermal cycling at low fluences and temperature variability effects are initially important for thermal expansion mismatch strains, with swelling contributing at higher fluences.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small* small* substantial</p>	*The description requires a representative volume, and testing conditions.
5.1.3	Swelling driving force	<p><i>Evaluation of swelling driving force. Testing parameters require neutron fluence, geometric configuration and temperature fields. Low fluence testing is of limited value, however preliminary impact can be assessed.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>partial partial substantial</p>	--
5.1.4	Stress concentrations at cracks and discontinuities	<p><i>Evaluation of stress concentrations at cracks and discontinuities. Testing parameters require to properly reproduce FW and breeding blanket geometries – since expected to control stress concentration, cracking, thermal cycling, temperature gradients, and swelling. Neutron flux, spectrum, and fluence are required to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>partial partial substantial</p>	--
5.1.5	Thermal expansion driving force	<p><i>Evaluation of thermal expansion driving force induced by neutron heating. Testing parameters require to properly reproduce FW and breeding blanket geometries, temperature gradients and thermal cycling. Neutron flux, spectrum, and fluence are required to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>partial partial substantial</p>	--
5.2		<i>Neutron multiplier mechanical interactions</i>		

5.2.1	Beryllium alloys swelling (swelling driving force in beryllium alloys)	<p><i>Evaluation of swelling driving force in beryllium alloys. Testing parameters require neutron spectrum, fluence (> 5 MW-yr/m²) and temperature (400 to 600°C) to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	partial partial substantial	--
5.2.2	Strain accommodation by creep in beryllium alloys	<p><i>Evaluation of strain accommodation by creep in beryllium alloys. Testing parameters require neutron wall loading, spectrum, temperature, and geometric configuration. Prestress in the beryllium alloys has to be considered since might provide an initial driving force for creep. Neutron flux, spectrum, and fluence are required to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	partial partial substantial	--
5.3	<i>Thermal interactions</i>				
5.3.1	Breeder- and multiplier-structure interface heat transfer	<p><i>Evaluation of breeder-and-multiplier-structure interface heat transfer. Testing parameters require local power density, chemical environment, geometry, temperature profiles, purge flow velocity and pressure, mechanical stress/restraint, neutron flux, spectrum, and fluence to properly resolve this issue.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	partial* partial* substantial	* p/d and IFMIF cannot provide enough volume for a meaningful testing/understanding
6	General blanket issues				
6.1	<i>D-T fuel self-sufficiency</i>				
6.1.1	Uncertainties in achievable breeding ratio	<p><i>Evaluation of uncertainties in achievable breeding ratio. Testing parameters require experimental data from the operation of a complete fuel cycle system, which includes nearly all components of the fusion device, particularly plasma, plasma exhaust system, blanket, and tritium processing systems. A fusion neutron spectrum is necessary for verifying the neutronics performance, and a 14 MeV neutron source with sufficient intensity is considered an indispensable means of verification of neutronics methods and data.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	small partial partial substantial	--
6.1.2	Uncertainties in required breeding ratio	<p><i>Evaluation of uncertainties in required breeding ratio. Testing parameters require neutrons features such as the spectrum, the geometry of the neutron multiplier and solid breeder. A fusion neutron spectrum is necessary for verifying the neutronics performance, and a 14 MeV neutron source with sufficient intensity is considered an indispensable means of verification of neutronics methods and data.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO	small partial partial substantial	--

6.2		Tritium permeation		
6.2.1	Permeation from breeder to blanket coolant	<p>Evaluation of permeation from breeder to blanket coolant. Testing parameters require to properly reproduce temperature and tritium pressure, breeder impurities/corrosion, surfaces treatments and burn/dwell cycling. Neutron flux, spectrum, and fluence (material damages) are required to properly resolve this issue.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial*</p>	* VNS and DEMO have simultaneously the effects of all relevant parameters driving the phenomenon
6.2.2	Tritium inventory	<p>Evaluation of tritium inventories in fusion reactor blankets. Testing parameters require to properly reproduce temperature fields (both under normal and accidental conditions), solubility, and diffusion values as well as surface release mechanisms and stresses. Neutron flux, spectrum, and fluence (material damages) are required to properly resolve this issue.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial*</p>	* The size of the mock-up, the representativeness of material combination and the operating conditions (e.g. T field) are relevant for the process
6.2.3	Failure modes and frequencies	<p>Evaluation of failure modes and frequencies in relevant environmental condition. The operating environment/parameters include the geometry of the first wall/blanket, expected operating temperature (300-600°C), neutron spectrum, flux, and fluence, heat flux, coolant velocity, and electromagnetic effects.</p> <p>Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	<p>VNS DEMO</p> <p>partial substantial*</p>	* Meaningful, but still preliminary, partial, and far from mature data will be available only with a tokamak representative in terms of dimensions, complexity, technology, systems and performances.
6.2.4	Nuclear heating rate predictions	<p>Evaluation of nuclear heating rate predictions. Heat deposition during operation is a strong function of neutrons and gamma ray fluxes, spectra, and fluences. Decay heat after shutdown is a strong function of the previous history of operation.</p> <p>Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	<p>VNS or DEMO</p> <p>substantial</p>	This will come only when the plant start-up will occur and will be function of the plasma operation.
6.2.5	Blanket response to near blanket failures	<p>Evaluation of blanket response to near blanket failures. Testing parameters require prototypical temperatures, geometries, stresses, coolant velocities, coolant pressures, transient pressures, and chemical environment. Neutrons are required for the operating environment.</p> <p>Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	<p>VNS DEMO</p> <p>partial substantial*</p>	* This can be afforded in reliable way as statistical experience. Unfortunately, the deterministic tools will not be very reliable nor with the first neither with the second DEMO. Accumulation of data is needed.
6.2.6	Recycling of irradiated lithium and beryllium alloys	<p>Evaluation of recycling of irradiated lithium and beryllium alloys. Testing parameters require expected operating temperature (300-600°C), neutron spectrum, flux, and fluence.</p> <p>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>substantial substantial substantial</p>	--
6.2.7	Prediction and control of normal effluents associated with fluid radioactivity	<p>Evaluation of prediction and control of normal effluents associated with fluid radioactivity. Testing parameters require prototypical fluid systems to determine</p>	<p>p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small small substantial</p>	--

		<p><i>the potential for leaks and radioactivity levels in waste stream. Neutrons are not needed for direct effluent tests, but mainly for sputtering and corrosion tests.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>		
6.3	<i>Tritium processing</i>			
6.3.1	Tritium Monitoring and Accountability	<p><i>Evaluation of tritium monitoring and accountability. Testing parameters require prototypical geometries, tritium carrier conditions, flow rates, concentration and chemical environment. Operational transients, instrumentation response times and monitor lifetime are important parameters to be considered. High tritium accountability requires accurate assessment of regions exposed to neutrons due to neutron heating, specific reactions, and neutron damage.</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial</p>	--
6.3.2	Breeder Tritium Extraction Characteristics	<p><i>Evaluation of breeder tritium extraction characteristics. Testing parameters require purge/breeder flow rate, geometry, tritium concentration and impurities, and breeder temperature. Neutron flux and fluence are additional parameters that determine flow rate, impurity levels, and tritium concentrations</i></p> <p><i>Understanding and knowledge improvements of phenomena/processes, technology enhancements (separate effect tests) in capsules or scaled down mock-ups. Integral testing in mockups (i.e. similar shape) / full component qualification.</i></p>	<p>Spallation source p/d-LINAC IFMIF-DONES VNS or DEMO</p> <p>small partial partial substantial</p>	--

References

- [1] M. A. Abdou, et al, (1995) A volumetric neutron source for fusion nuclear technology testing and development, Fusion Technology, vol. No. 27, 1-43, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0920-3796\(95\)90122-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0920-3796(95)90122-1)